

D2.9: LANDMARC COUNTRY CASE STUDY LEAFLETS

ON LAND-BASED MITIGATION AND NEGATIVE EMISSION SOLUTIONS IN
THE LANDMARC CASE STUDY COUNTRIES

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LANDMARC

Land-use based Mitigation for Resilient Climate Pathways

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Reviewer(s)	Jenny Lieu
Changes with respect to the DoA	Deliverable was submitted with one month delay according to the Grant Agreement. CINEA project Advisor was informed about this delay (with justification). Inclusion of Ukraine as case study country was not foreseen, however the (planned) research activities contribute directly to achieving the objectives of the DoA.
Dissemination and uptake	This deliverable provides an overview of all the case study leaflets on land-based mitigation and negative emission solutions of the LANDMARC project. Aside from this integrated deliverable (includes all leaflets) the individual leaflets will also be used as stand-alone documents to help inform stakeholders (i.e. as pdf/downloadable at case study section at www.landmarc2020.eu).
Short Summary of results	This document provides a status overview of the key research activities that are or will be implemented in the LANDMARC case study countries. This document provides an overview of the (ongoing) research activities within each country, some preliminary results on earth observation monitoring, economic, land-use, soil and climate simulation modelling, as well as qualitative assessments and stakeholder engagement actions.
Evidence of accomplishment	This report and all the individual leaflets.

Preface

Negative emission solutions are expected to play a pivotal role in future climate actions and net zero emissions policy scenarios. To date most climate actions have focussed on phasing out fossil fuels and reducing greenhouse gas emissions in, for example, industry, electricity, and transport. While zero emission trajectories in these sectors will remain a priority for decades to come, it is expected that residual GHG emissions will remain. To be able to fulfil the Paris Agreement and meet the world's climate goals research, policy and markets are increasingly looking at negative emission solutions.

This is why the nineteen LANDMARC consortium partners work together in order to:

- Estimate the climate impact of land-based negative emission solutions, in agriculture, forestry, and other land-use sectors,
- Assess the potential for regional and global upscaling of negative emission solutions,
- Map their potential environmental, economic, and social co-benefits and trade-offs,

LANDMARC is an interdisciplinary consortium with expertise from ecology, engineering, climate sciences, global carbon cycle, soil sciences, satellite earth observation sciences, agronomy, economics, social sciences, and business. There is a balanced representation of partners from academia, SMEs, and NGOs from the EU, Africa, Asia, and the Americas, which ensures a wide coverage of LMTs operating in different contexts (e.g., climates, land-use practices, socio-economic etc.) and spatial scales.

The LANDMARC project consortium:

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1. Purpose of this document

This document (Deliverable 2.9) provides an overview of the various research actions and assessment activities that are (to be) conducted within the various LANDMARC case study countries. Research activities range from earth observation monitoring to simulation modelling, as well as a range of qualitative assessment that build on engagement and co-development with relevant stakeholders.

This document also brings together the three pillars of LANDMARC including I) stakeholder engagement, II) earth observation tools and III) model simulation tools. The first part of this deliverable (see Sections 2.1 to 2.5) provides an overview of the updated country case study leaflets which reflect the status of the ongoing research that has been partly co-developed with stakeholders. The detailed country case study leaflets are included in the Annexed report. The last part of the deliverable (Section 2.6) gives an overview of the (ongoing) cross-cutting research activities within LANDMARC in all the case study countries, ranging from qualitative risk assessments, the application of earth observation tools and model simulation tools that have been and will potentially be applied in the case studies. Finally, we provide some preliminary insights on climate hazard analysis from initial CMIP6-ECEarth3 simulations, which will produce a risk atlas specifying the climate-related risk and anticipated risk changes for the different case study country regions, to guide decisions regarding the most effective implementation and (climate) risk management of LMTs.

Land-based mitigation and negative emission solutions assessed within the (15) LANDMARC case study countries. The document provides a status overview of the research activities on two main elements:

1. **Case study, individual LMT:** Basic information on the application of Earth Observation tools and methods for better measurement/quantification of the climate (emissions, reduction, removal) of specific land-based mitigation (LMT) case studies.
2. **National LMT portfolios:** Information on country-specific portfolios of scalable LMT solutions, combining co-created scaling scenarios, as well as information on country specific qualitative (e.g., climate risk assessment) and quantitative assessment work (e.g., economic, land use change modelling).

Figure 1 (below) provides a visual overview of the specific case studies and national LMT portfolios for each country. Section 2.5 provides country overview sheets, which should help the reader to better understand and navigate through the (ongoing) assessment work that is done within the framework of the LANDMARC project. Annexed to this report (Annex 1 – Case study country leaflets) are the leaflets for all case study countries, which provide more background and detail, and in many cases already some initial results from the (ongoing) assessment work.

Note: This report provides an update of the status and progress of the research activities conducted within the case study countries. This report can be considered as an ‘update’ and extension of the previous report [D2.8 – Case study leaflets](#) published in February 2021.

Figure 1: Overview of LANDMARC case studies (version January 2023)

2. Introduction

2.1 Managing natural carbon sinks

Land and sea represent a large reservoir of stored carbon and other precursors of greenhouse gases, locked in plants, soil, and waters. Anthropogenic activities on land and sea interfere with the natural carbon cycle, eventually leading to more emissions of GHGs than nature can absorb in one or multiple cycles; thereby increasing atmospheric GHG concentrations.

There is a broad consensus among scientists and governments that the way humankind manages land and sea plays a crucial role in achieving serious emission reductions and ultimately net negative emissions (Masson-Delmotte, et al., 2018) ; (European Commission, 2020)). As an example, net stored carbon in the EU AFOLU sector decreased from some 300 million tons CO₂eq. in 2010 to 263 million tons CO₂eq. in 2018, due to changes in land use and climate change effects (European Commission, 2020). By 2030 net stored carbon is expected to decrease even further to 225 million tons CO₂eq. in a business-as-usual scenario. Hence, actions to counteract the degradation of natural carbon sinks and enhance their GHG storage volumes are needed. In these actions, the use of our natural GHG sinks should be included, both in regional and international GHG emission strategies.

2.2 LANDMARC scope of land-based mitigation solutions

The LANDMARC research and innovation project assesses the potential for a broad group of land-based mitigation technologies and practices (LMTs) to either reduce emissions to or remove carbon from the atmosphere. Managing land-based natural carbon sinks, in soils and vegetation can be done in different ways. The LANDMARC project covers a broad range of land-based activities that could aid with reducing land-based GHG emissions and/or remove carbon from the atmosphere. Within this report you will find information about the ongoing assessment work for the following LMTs (**Table 1**).

Forest management	Land management	Biomass-processing based
Afforestation / reforestation	Cropland management <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Organic farming - No tillage - Alternative cropping strategies (e.g., rice management) 	Organic fertilizers (e.g., compost)
Forest conservation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Indigenous forest fire prevention - Forest management 	Grassland / pasture management	Biochar
Agroforestry	Peatland management <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Conservation - Rewetting - Paludiculture 	BECCS (combustion and anaerobic digestion)

Table 1: Overview of LMTs assessed within LANDMARC.

Each LANDMARC country targets a different set of LMTs depending on the specific domestic scaling potential of an LMT, and/or the interests that key stakeholders have expressed to the LANDMARC partners (resulting from the stakeholder engagement actions).

2.3 LANDMARC main research activities and societal relevance

The research activities conducted within the LANDMARC project comprise out of three main pillars (see Figure 2).

Figure 2: Three main pillars of LANDMARC research activities

The *first pillar* captures all the qualitative assessment and stakeholder engagement work that is (being) conducted within the different case study countries and world regions¹ (Figure 2 – orange). Within this pillar the research activities mainly focus on assessing the scaling potential of different LMTs, as well as eliciting any scaling barriers, (climate) risks and co-benefits together with stakeholders. That is, by means of co-design new scaling narratives and scenarios are derived.

- *Societal relevance Pillar I:* The outputs / results from these research activities will be made available for use by stakeholders active in the implementation of LMT within their own communities, countries, and regions. Data and results could be used to, for example inform

¹ Note that within this report we focus solely on the research activities conducted within the LANDMARC case study countries (and thus not at the continental and global level).

regional spatial planning and (disaster) risk management processes with respect to improving the (climate) resilience of land-based activities in relation to nature conservation, agricultural and forest (AFOLU) sector activities.

The **second pillar** comprises LANDMARCs' earth observation program (**Figure 2 – green**) that is set up to improve the monitoring of the carbon cycle and other GHG fluxes from land (soils and vegetation). Here a broad range of earth observation monitoring tools and methods are applied to specific LMT sites to test novel combinations of both remote sensing and in-situ measurements. The experiments (to be) conducted with these novel combinations of EO monitoring tools/methods in the respective countries will inform the further development of a so-called carbon map tool for a range of LMTs.

- **Societal relevance Pillar II:** The outputs / results from these research activities can be used to more accurately and/or more economically provide GHG monitoring services for LMTs to different public and private actors aiming to scale up the deployment of LMTs. (Voluntary) carbon markets (e.g., GHG monitoring protocols), various climate policy initiatives (e.g., the EU's proposal a certification framework for carbon removals)² as well as national authorities looking to better quantify the net climate impacts of LMTs (e.g., national greenhouse gas inventory reports), may benefit from advances in earth observations enabled monitoring of natural carbon sinks in AFOLU sectors.

The **third pillar** hosts a series of simulation modelling activities (**Figure 2 - blue**) that are being used to better understand the (spatial, economic, climate and other) impacts of scaling up LMTs within a specific context (local, national, continental, global). Within this pillar we deploy a range of simulation models ranging from land use models (LandSHIFT, ALCES), economic (E3ME), climate (EC-Earth / CMIP6), to biochemical (DayCent) models. The data and scenario input for these simulation models is collected / co-developed through pillar I and II research activities as well as literature review.

- **Societal relevance Pillar III:** The outputs / results from these research activities can potentially be used to inform policy makers, spatial planners and (rural) communities in their efforts to develop and implement LMTs within their region. A better quantitative understanding of the impacts of scaling up LMTs may contribute to advance the transition process towards more sustainable management of land. In addition to that, the outputs and results may from this work may also be used to inform ongoing or future simulation modelling research projects, focussing on integrated impact assessment (IAM) of scaling up LMT portfolios in different countries and/or world regions.

2.4 LANDMARC research activities at the national level

The LANDMARC project conducts interdisciplinary research program within fifteen case study countries. The LANDMARC project aims to achieve its research objectives by assessing the impacts of land-based mitigation (reduction) and negative emission (removal) technologies and practices by applying a unique mixed-methods approach.

² https://climate.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2022-11/Proposal_for_a_Regulation_establishing_a_Union_certification_framework_for_carbon_removals.pdf

LANDMARC research activity	Case study (single LMT)	National LMT portfolio
A Application of earth observation techniques³ (1) including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Soil sampling and analysis (physical, chemical, biological) - Gas flux measurements - Photogrammetry based in LIDAR - Latent heat flux estimates from satellite data - Satellite monitoring of biomass 	X	
B Climate hazard and sensitivity assessment (2) including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Qualitative climate risk assessment (survey) - Climate hazards analysis (with CMIP6/ECEarth3)⁴ (see Section 2.6.4) 		X
C Scaling scenario co-design (3) with stakeholders including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Co-design of scaling scenarios - Assessing the LMT potential and data/information/knowledge exchange with local stakeholders 		X
D Qualitative risk and impact assessment of scaling (4) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Qualitative socio-economic and environmental risk assessment 		X
E Quantitative impact assessment with simulation models⁵ (5) including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Carbon and nitrogen biochemical simulations (DayCent model) - Land use modelling (LandSHIFT and ALCES models) - Economic modelling (E3ME macroeconomic model) 	X	X
F Capacity building, policy support and business model development		X

The results of this assessment for case study countries concerned are included within a range of (upcoming) deliverables, including:

(1) D3.1 Remote sensing data collection, D3.2 In situ measurement data collection report, D3.3 Prototype model observation system, D3.4 Calibration and validation report, D3.5 Best management practices guide, D3.6 LMTs monitoring effectiveness, D3.7/3.8 on new earth systems monitoring tools.

(2) D4.1 Climate risk assessment and initial risk management plan, D4.2 Summary on sensitivity of LMT approaches, D4.3 Atlas on climate risks.

(3) D2.6 LMT scaling scenarios final report, D2.8 and D2.9 Country case study leaflets version 1 and version 2

(4) D5.2 Results from risk, co-benefit, and trade-off assessments.

(5) D5.3 Model run outputs from model set, D5.5 E3ME model simulations.

Please note that not all the research methods and tools are applied to all the LMTs assessed within the LANDMARC case study countries

Table 2: Overview of LANDMARC research activities at the case study country level

The assessment work performed within the various case study countries provide the necessary bottom-up oriented, empirical evidence needed to validate, verify, and improve top-down oriented integrated assessment work. The mixed-method approach applied within LANDMARC consists of a range of research activities (see **Table 2: A-F**). These research activities will either be applied within a single LMT solution (case study) or can be applied to a selection of LMT solutions within the respective country (LMT portfolio). Most of the earth observation monitoring work will be applied to specific LMT solutions in the respective countries. Also, for some of the countries the (ALCES, LandSHIFT, E3ME, DayCent) simulation modelling (to be) performed covers only a single or more limited set of LMTs, depending on model characteristics and data availability. All the other research methods, and in

³ See for an overview of the LANDMARC Earth Observation tools: <https://www.landmarc2020.eu/landmarc-tools>

⁴ See for an overview of the LANDMARC simulation models: <https://www.landmarc2020.eu/landmarc-tools>

⁵ See for an overview of the LANDMARC simulation models: <https://www.landmarc2020.eu/landmarc-tools>

particular the more qualitative methods in most countries will be applied to the full national LMT portfolios.

There are a few specific case study countries that deviate from the typical case study country, where **a)** earth observation tools are applied to one or more LMTs, **b)** simulation modelling is applied to one or more LMTs, and where **c)** the qualitative assessment work is applied. In these case study countries, a more limited set of tools / methods may be applied, or there may have been a change of LMT scope and focus, largely influenced by the co-design and stakeholder engagement work. In the case of Ukraine a completely new case study country has been included within the LANDMARC research project. These specific research context of each of these country case studies are briefly discussed in Box 1 (below).

Box 1: Specific purpose or changed country case studies

Canada

The Canadian case study shifted from willow based BECCS to reforestation and peatland reclamation. The original willow-based case study scope changed due to changes in access to the parcel linked to a commercial stakeholder. Without this access, we changed our focus on the Athabasca region in Alberta, where oil sands are located in Canada. The core stakeholder group consists of a nearby Indigenous community. They informed us that wetland and reforestation were large issues in the area. The current case study focuses on developing a business model with stakeholders around the potential for reforestation and wetlands reclamation based on model applications including E3ME and ALCES. Earth observation tools (e.g., remote sensing) will also be applied to determine the potential for scaling up.

Germany

The German country case study work focusses specifically on forest management as the main LMT. No specific earth observation (EO) techniques from within the LANDMARC project are applied, but use is made from existing EO data sets (e.g., forest inventory data). The simulation modelling done, makes use of the FABio simulation model, which is only applied within the German context. The simulation modelling performed within the other LANDMARC case study countries, make use of the LANDMARC model suite, including ALCES, LandSHIFT, E3ME, CMIP6-EC-Earth. With respect to the qualitative assessment work all research methods and activities are applied within Germany.

South Africa

The South African case study was designed as a dedicated case study to develop novel earth observation data based GHG monitoring tool for vegetation. A collaboration with a local research project was initiated to be able to obtain access to in-situ gas flux measurement time series data that would be suitable for calibrating and validating a number of remote sensing-based monitoring tools.

Sweden

At an early stage in the stakeholder engagement process it was clear that within the context of the Swedish country case study work there would be a limited relevance for implementing specific earth

observation methods and techniques. This mainly had to do with the key interest of Swedish stakeholders in more engineered negative emission solutions, such as biochar and BECCS.

Ukraine

After the beginning of the Russian invasion in Ukraine on 24 February 2022, LANDMARC has made efforts to reach out to the Ukrainian community,⁶ to seek collaboration and consider Ukrainian refugee researchers during recruitment processes. Within the LANDMARC consortium, lead partner TU Delft (The Netherlands) has been able to (temporarily) recruit Natalia Prozorova within the LANDMARC project a refugee researcher from the National Scientific Centre - Institute for Soil Science and Agrochemistry Research (NSC – ISSAR), based in Kharkiv, Ukraine. During this period, the LANDMARC consortium has also explored opportunities for further research collaboration with NSC – ISSAR to also be able to support the researchers remaining in Ukraine. This has led to a number of specific research collaborations between NSC - ISSAR and several LANDMARC consortium partners, particularly linking to organic plant farming practices. NSC – ISSARs domestic partner network with large-scale organic cropping farms and the availability of long-term time series soil and farm data provided opportunities for expanding the scope of some of the LANDMARC assessment work, particularly in the area of earth observations, but also in the area of simulation modelling.

The agreed / foreseen LANDMARC/NSC – ISSAR research activities include:

- Soil sampling and remote sensing analysis for organic plant farming (agreed and ongoing)
- DayCent simulation modelling in organic farming systems, includes black soils (agreed and ongoing)
- LandSHIFT simulation modelling (under preparation; funding pending)

The specific collaborations, with brief status updates are described in more detail within the Annexed leaflet. The assessment work (to be) done in some cases contributes directly to meeting the LANDMARC research objectives. Where some of the initial LANDMARC case study sites for earth observation monitoring turned out to be less suitable (e.g., size, too limited local data availability), the Ukrainian country case study provides a good alternative site.

Within the country case study leaflets, annexed to this report some initial findings and preliminary results are provided. Table 2 also provides information on a range of project reports (deliverables) that will be produced throughout the course of the LANDMARC project. These reports will include a full overview of the results and findings of the various research activities conducted within the different case study countries.

In the following section 2.5 we provide simplified overview sheets per country. These country overview sheets provide an overview of the current stage of the assessment work, and some next steps to be taken.

⁶ https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/other/comm/solidarity-with-refugee-researchers-of-ukraine_horizon-h2020_en.pdf

2.5 Country overview sheets

Within this section we provide simple overview tables for each LANDMARC country reflecting on which mix of research methods and tools are (to be) applied, either at the level of individual LMTs or at the level of an LMT portfolio.

2.5.1 Germany

- Lead partner: Oeko-Institut
- Contact person(s): Hannes Böttcher and Anke Benndorf

Case study		LMT portfolio
LMT scope	Forest management	N.A.
Methods (to be) applied		
A Application of earth observation techniques	Mainly use made of existing earth observation data (including national forest inventory data)	-
B Climate hazard and sensitivity assessment	Survey interviews: conducted and some initial results presented.	-
C Scaling scenario co-design with stakeholders	Workshop(s) and stakeholder engagement: upcoming stakeholder engagement actions planned.	-
D Qualitative risk and impact assessment of scaling	Survey interviews: conducted and some initial results presented.	-
E Quantitative impact assessment with simulation models	E3ME modelling: to assess the impacts on trade of wood products caused by changes in wood supply from German forests. FABio modelling ⁷ : to estimate carbon stored of wood products, forest litter and soil. Some preliminary scenarios and results are provided.	-
F Capacity building, policy support and business model development	Stakeholder engagement, and further dissemination and exploitation or results	

⁷ <https://www.oeko.de/publikationen/p-details/fabio-waldmodell>

2.5.2 The Netherlands

- Lead partners: Bioclear Earth, JIN Climate & Sustainability
- Contact person(s): Afnan Suleiman, Eline Keuning, Malte Renz, Eise Spijker

	Case study	LMT portfolio
LMT scope	Peatland rewetting	Peatland rewetting
	Agroforestry	Agroforestry
		Afforestation
		BECCS (biogas)
Methods (to be) applied		
A	Application of earth observation techniques	Soil sampling analysis to assess soil functions (GHG storage, (de-) nitrification, methane emissions, etc.) as well as upcoming remote sensing technique applications. Some initial results presented.
B	Climate hazard and sensitivity assessment	Survey interviews: conducted and some initial results presented.
C	Scaling scenario co-design with stakeholders	Workshop(s) and stakeholder engagement.
D	Qualitative risk and impact assessment of scaling	Survey interviews: conducted and some initial results presented.
E	Quantitative impact assessment with simulation models	DayCent modelling: to simulate above-and belowground carbon in agroforestry systems E3ME modelling: Some preliminary results are presented. ALCES modelling: to assess land use change/competition between different LMTs and other land use functions
F	Capacity building, policy support and business model development	Stakeholder engagement, and further dissemination and exploitation or results

2.5.3 Portugal

- Lead partner: AgroInsider
- Contact person(s): Patrícia Lourenço, Vanessa Duarte, José Rafael Marques da Silva

	Case study	LMT portfolio
LMT scope	Pastures (Montado)	Pastures (Montado)
		Agroforestry
		Forestry
		Agriculture
Methods (to be) applied		

A	Application of earth observation techniques	Earth Observation (EO) tools (Sentinel-1, radar sensor and Sentinel-2, optical sensor, and a drone with LiDAR sensor) to characterize, monitor, report and verify vegetation and soil carbon. Based on spectral vegetation indexes, these farms were automatically segmented, and sampling sites were smartly selected for physical, chemical, and microbiological soil analyses.	
B	Climate hazard and sensitivity assessment		Survey interviews: conducted and some initial results presented.
C	Scaling scenario co-design with stakeholders		Workshop(s) and stakeholder engagement
D	Qualitative risk and impact assessment of scaling		Survey interviews: conducted and some initial results presented.
E	Quantitative impact assessment with simulation models	DayCent modelling: to simulate fluxes of carbon and nitrogen between the atmosphere, vegetation, and soil.	
F	Capacity building, policy support and business model development	Stakeholder engagement, and further dissemination and exploitation of results	

2.5.4 Spain

- Lead partner: Ambienta
- Contact person(s): Pilar Martín Gallego, Federico Julian

Case study- individual LMT		LMT portfolio
LMT scope	Pastures (Dehesas)	Pastures (Dehesas)
	Forest management	Forest management
		Grassland management
		Agroforestry
		Afforestation / reforestation
Methods (to be) applied		
A	Application of earth observation techniques	Remote sensing data collection (e.g., from Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2), and in-situ data for above ground biomass and soil sampling.
B	Climate hazard and sensitivity assessment	Survey interviews: conducted and some initial results presented.

C	Scaling scenario co-design with stakeholders		Workshop(s) and stakeholder engagement
D	Qualitative risk and impact assessment of scaling		Survey interviews: conducted and some initial results presented.
E	Quantitative impact assessment with simulation models	DayCent modelling: to simulate fluxes of carbon and nitrogen between the atmosphere, vegetation, and soil in relation to forest management.	E3ME modelling: Some preliminary results are presented. ALCES modelling work is ongoing
F	Capacity building, policy support and business model development	Stakeholder engagement, and further dissemination and exploitation or results	

2.5.5 Sweden

- Lead partner: Stockholm Environment Institute
- Contact person(s): Maria Xylia, Francis X. Johnson, Eileen Torres-Morales

Case study		LMT portfolio	
			Biochar
LMT scope			BECCS
			Forest management
Methods (to be) applied			
A	Application of earth observation techniques		
B	Climate hazard and sensitivity assessment		Survey interviews: conducted and some initial results presented.
C	Scaling scenario co-design with stakeholders		Workshop(s) and stakeholder engagement
D	Qualitative risk and impact assessment of scaling		Survey interviews: conducted and some initial results presented.
E	Quantitative impact assessment with simulation models		E3ME modelling to investigate the impact of scaling up an LMT portfolio consisting of biochar, and BECCS, and their synergies to the forestry sector. Supported with some techno-economic assessment. Some preliminary results are presented.
F	Capacity building, policy support and business model development	Stakeholder engagement, and further dissemination and exploitation or results	

2.5.6 Switzerland

- Lead partner: ETH Zurich
- Contact person(s): Moritz Laub

Case study		LMT portfolio
LMT scope		Organic agriculture
		Reduced tillage
		Agroforestry
		Biochar
Methods (to be) applied		
A	Application of earth observation techniques	
B	Climate hazard and sensitivity assessment	Survey interviews: Initial findings are presented on the assessment climate risks and sensitivities for all Kenyan LMTs.*
C	Scaling scenario co-design with stakeholders	Workshop(s) and stakeholder engagement
D	Qualitative risk and impact assessment of scaling	Survey interviews on (perceived) risks and (co-)benefits of large-scale implementation of LMT portfolio
E	Quantitative impact assessment with simulation models	E3ME modelling: Some preliminary results are presented. DayCent modelling: applied to organic farming and reduced tillage, with aim to link to LandSHIFT modelling ALCES modelling work is ongoing
F	Capacity building, policy support and business model development	Stakeholder engagement, and further dissemination and exploitation or results

2.5.7 Ukraine

- Lead partner: TU Delft, National Scientific Center - Institute for Soil Science and Agrochemistry Research named after O.N. Sokolovsky (NSC-ISSAR)
- Contact person(s): Natalia Prozorova, Jenny Lieu, Eise Spijker, Ruediger Schaldach, Afnan Suleiman, Moritz Laub, Patricia Lourenco

Case study		LMT portfolio
LMT scope	Organic farming	Organic farming
	Conventional crop farming	Agroforestry (shelterbelts),
		Reduced tillage
		Bioenergy

Methods (to be) applied		
A	Application of earth observation techniques	Soil sampling (soil biological monitoring)
B	Climate hazard and sensitivity assessment	N.A.
C	Scaling scenario co-design with stakeholders	Stakeholder engagement (mostly direct and bilateral engagement, due to safety reasons, but also workshops/webinars will be considered)
D	Qualitative risk and impact assessment of scaling	N.A.
E	Quantitative impact assessment with simulation models	DayCent modelling: to simulate fluxes of carbon and nitrogen between the atmosphere, vegetation, and soil; with the aim to also link it to LandSHIFT modelling
F	Capacity building, policy support and business model development	Stakeholder engagement, and further dissemination and exploitation of results
		LandSHIFT modelling: focussing on land use changes.

2.5.8 Burkina Faso

- Lead partner: eLEAF
- Contact person(s): Annemarie Klaasse and Mohamed Ahmed

	Case study	LMT portfolio
	Agroforestry	Agroforestry
LMT scope	Cropland management	Cropland management
		Forest management
		Afforestation, reforestation

Methods (to be) applied		
A	Application of earth observation techniques	Soil sampling and remote sensing to estimate (e.g., Net Primary production in gC/m ² and capacity of carbon storage and CH ₄ emissions)
B	Climate hazard and sensitivity assessment	Survey interviews: conducted and some initial results presented.
C	Scaling scenario co-design with stakeholders	Workshop(s) and stakeholder engagement

D	Qualitative risk and impact assessment of scaling	Survey interviews: conducted and some initial results presented.
E	Quantitative impact assessment with simulation models	DayCent modelling in relation to Aforestation and forest management LandSHIFT modelling ALCES modelling
F	Capacity building, policy support and business model development	Stakeholder engagement, and further dissemination and exploitation or results

2.5.9 Kenya

- Lead partner: ETH Zurich
- Contact person(s): Moritz Laub

Case study		LMT portfolio
LMT scope	Integrated Soil Fertility Management (soil carbon and soil GHG fluxes)	Integrated Soil Fertility Management Agroforestry Afforestation
Methods (to be) applied		
A	Application of earth observation techniques	Soil sampling and soil gas flux emissions monitoring
B	Climate hazard and sensitivity assessment	Survey interviews: Initial findings are presented on the assessment climate risks and sensitivities for all Kenyan LMTs.
C	Scaling scenario co-design with stakeholders	Workshop(s) and stakeholder engagement
D	Qualitative risk and impact assessment of scaling	Survey interviews
E	Quantitative impact assessment with simulation models	DayCent modelling: The preliminary results further show, that ISFM reduces losses compared to the most common farming system, where little to no organic and mineral fertilizer inputs are used.
F	Capacity building, policy support and business model development	Stakeholder engagement, and further dissemination and exploitation or results

2.5.10 South Africa

- Lead partner: eLEAF
- Contact person(s): Annemarie Klaasse, Mohamed Ahmed

Case study		LMT portfolio
LMT scope	Assess the role of vegetation in carbon storage	
Methods (to be) applied		
A	Application of earth observation techniques	Gas flux measurements (eddy Covariance) combined with three remote sensing activities (including ETLook, ESA-TROPOSIF project, and TROPOMI HCHO)
B	Climate hazard and sensitivity assessment	
C	Scaling scenario co-design with stakeholders	
D	Qualitative risk and impact assessment of scaling	
E	Quantitative impact assessment with simulation models	
F	Capacity building, policy support and business model development	Stakeholder engagement, and further dissemination and exploitation or results

2.5.11 Indonesia

- Lead partner: Sustainability and Resilience Company (Su-re.co)
- Contact person(s): Siti Indriana, Takeshi Takama

Case study		LMT portfolio
LMT scope	Agroforestry	Forest management
	Biogas & compost	Peatland management
		Agroforestry
		Organic fertilizers
Methods (to be) applied		
A	Application of earth observation techniques	Soil sampling analysis, and remote sensing (satellite) monitoring
B	Climate hazard and sensitivity assessment	Survey interviews: conducted and some initial results presented.

C	Scaling scenario co-design with stakeholders	Workshop(s) and stakeholder engagement (various stakeholder workshops (co-)hosted).
D	Qualitative risk and impact assessment of scaling	Survey interviews: conducted and some initial results presented.
E	Quantitative impact assessment with simulation models	E3ME modelling: Some preliminary results are presented. ALCES modelling work is ongoing. LandSHIFT modelling: Some preliminary results are presented.
F	Capacity building, policy support and business model development	Stakeholder engagement, and further dissemination and exploitation or results

2.5.12 Nepal

- Lead partner: University of Sussex
- Contact person(s): Lokendra Karki

Case study		LMT portfolio
LMT scope	Dry seeded rice	Rice management
	Wet direct-seeded rice	Agroforestry
	Seeding transplanted rice	Forestry
	Traditional / manual rice transplanting	Organic farming
Methods (to be) applied		
A	Application of earth observation techniques	Soil sampling analysis, and remote sensing (satellite) monitoring
B	Climate hazard and sensitivity assessment	Survey interviews: conducted and some initial results presented.
C	Scaling scenario co-design with stakeholders	Workshop(s) and stakeholder engagement: Conducted a National Stakeholder Consultation Workshop on "Upscaling Land Based Mitigation Technologies and Practices (LMTs) in Nepal" in Kathmandu on 13 December 2022
D	Qualitative risk and impact assessment of scaling	Survey interviews: conducted and some initial results presented.
E	Quantitative impact assessment with simulation models	ALCES modelling to simulate the impact of LMT portfolio on land use change and carbon sequestration.
F	Capacity building, policy support and	Stakeholder engagement, and further dissemination and exploitation or results

business model
development

2.5.13 Vietnam

- Lead partner: International Centre for Tropical Agriculture (CIAT)
- Contact person(s): Tuan Ha, Thao Pham, Eric Rahn

	Case study	LMT portfolio
LMT scope	Agroforestry	Agroforestry Forestry Biochar
Methods (to be) applied		
A Application of earth observation techniques	Soil sampling to compare soil microbial diversity between different coffee systems (agroforestry vs. monoculture), in combination with remote sensing.	
B Climate hazard and sensitivity assessment	Survey interviews: conducted and some initial results presented.	
C Scaling scenario co-design with stakeholders	Workshop(s) and stakeholder engagement	
D Qualitative risk and impact assessment of scaling	Survey interviews: conducted and some initial results presented.	
E Quantitative impact assessment with simulation models	ALCES modelling to visualize the impact of LMTs on land-use change and carbon sequestration.	
F Capacity building, policy support and business model development	Stakeholder engagement, and further dissemination and exploitation of results	

2.5.14 Canada

- Lead partners: Innolab space, TU Delft
- Contact person(s): Luis D. Virla, and Jenny Lieu

	Case study	LMT portfolio
LMT scope	Wetland management (preservation / restoration) Afforestation / reforestation	Wetland management (preservation / restoration) Afforestation / reforestation
Methods (to be) applied		
A Application of earth observation techniques	Soil samples collected and analysed for soil chemical/physical analysis and soil biological analysis	

B	Climate hazard and sensitivity assessment		Survey interviews: conducted and some initial results presented
C	Scaling scenario co-design with stakeholders		Workshop(s) and stakeholder engagement, including discussions with academia, and meetings with indigenous communities
D	Qualitative risk and impact assessment of scaling		Survey interviews: conducted and some initial results presented
E	Quantitative impact assessment with simulation models	Earth observation: potentially remote sensing tool to assess carbon potential for scaling up but tool no confirmed until we can access the land again after April 2023	E3ME modelling: to assess the impact on the economy, land-use change, and GHG emissions at the national scale if community-led restoration efforts based on Indigenous and local knowledge were to be deployed in LAR. ALCES modelling to evaluate the local impact on GHG emissions and co-benefits and trade-offs (land-use change, biodiversity, water, etc.)
F	Capacity building, policy support and business model development	Stakeholder engagement, and further dissemination and exploitation or	results

2.5.15 Venezuela

- Lead partner: COBRA Collective
- Contact person(s): Bibiana Bilbao, Jay Mistry, Rosalba Gómez, Ingrid Lanz, Luis D. Virla

Case study		LMT portfolio
LMT scope		Forest management (Indigenous fire management) Agroforestry
Methods (to be) applied		
A	Application of earth observation techniques	Main focus on remote sensing tools for vegetation monitoring
B	Climate hazard and sensitivity assessment	Survey interviews: conducted and some initial results presented.
C	Scaling scenario co-design with stakeholders	Workshop(s) and stakeholder engagement
D	Qualitative risk and impact assessment of scaling	Survey interviews: conducted and some initial results presented.

E	Quantitative impact assessment with simulation models	ALCES modelling work is ongoing
F	Capacity building, policy support and business model development	Stakeholder engagement, and further dissemination and exploitation or results

2.6 Cross cutting assessments and (ongoing) research activities

2.6.1 *Qualitative assessments and stakeholder engagement*⁸

From Section 2.5 and the Annexed country case study leaflets we can derive that – with the exception of South Africa and Ukraine - the qualitative assessments building upon stakeholder interviews and engagement are being fully implemented within all LANDMARC countries.

2.6.2 *Earth Observations tools and methods*⁹

Table 3, **Table 4**, and **Table 5** provide an overview of the current status of the (intended) application of different earth observation tools and methods within each case study country for specific LMT groups (i.e., forestry/agroforestry, land management, and other). While these are the intended applications, the actual application may vary during implementation as issues may come up with stakeholder engagement and/or land access. Any significant changes will be communicated accordingly in the case study narratives (D2.6).

The information presented in the following tables may be subject to changes/updates due to various reasons. In a few case studies, there have been delays with obtaining the proper permits (e.g., for soil sampling), while in other case studies the focus has had to shift to another LMT technology / practice or an alternative (better) LMT site as a result of the co-creation process with local stakeholders. In other case studies sufficient existing data has been available to perform the required analysis and assessment. The Annexed leaflets provide more context and background information.

⁸ A range of qualitative assessments and stakeholder engagement activities are part of LANDMARC Workpackages 2, 3 and 5 – See **Table 2** in **Section 2.2** for an overview of specific (upcoming / published) research outputs and reports.

⁹ Earth observation monitoring and data collection is part of LANDMARC Workpackage 3 – See **Table 2** in **Section 2.2** for an overview of specific (upcoming / published) research outputs and reports.

Earth Observation tool, method	Case study # and country								
	1: The Netherlands	3: Germany	6: Venezuela	7: Burkina Faso	8: South Africa	13: Spain	16: Spain, Portugal	19: Australia ¹⁰	20: China
In situ									
Soil physical / chemical monitoring	Y	Y	UC			Y	Y		
Soil biological monitoring	Y		UC	IP		Y	Y		
GHG (gas) flux measurements				Y	Y				
Remote sensing									
Latent heat flux estimates	IP			Y	Y				
Biomass monitoring	Y	IP	Y			Y	Y	IP	IP
Sentinel-5P (TROPOMI)					IP		IP	Y	Y
Photogrammetry based in LIDAR		IP				Y	Y		
Field mapping	UC	IP				Y	Y		
CarbonMap Tool based on SARS	Y					Y	Y		

Table 3: Forestry and agroforestry case studies

*Y = Tool (to be) applied; IP = In preparation; UC = Under consideration.

Earth Observation tool, method	Case study # and country							
	4: Switzerland (red. Tillage)	5: Switzerland (organic cropping)	9: Kenya (ISFM)	14: Vietnam (Coffee)	15: Nepal (Rice)	17: Colombia (Oil palm) ¹¹	18: Ukraine (Organic)	2: The Netherlands
In situ								
Soil physical / chemical monitoring	UC	UC	Y		Y	IP	IP	Y
Soil biological monitoring	N	N	Y	IP	Y	IP	IP	Y
GHG (gas) flux measurements	IP							
Remote sensing								
Latent heat flux estimates								
Biomass monitoring						Y	Y	IP
Sentinel-5P (TROPOMI)								
Photogrammetry based in LIDAR								
Field mapping								
CarbonMap Tool based on SARS						IP	IP	

Table 4: Land management case studies (e.g., agriculture, peat soils)

*Y = Tool (to be) applied; IP = In preparation; UC = Under consideration.

¹⁰ China and Australia are added as specific case study countries to be able to implement the LANDMARC EO work with the Sentinel-5p (TROPOMI). The reason for including these case study sites were mainly due to their inherent suitability of the site in relation to the EO tool (e.g., site size to match satellite resolution, availability of time series data, etc.).

¹¹ Both the Colombia and Ukraine case studies have been included to enable to implement part(s) of the LANDMARC research program. The Colombian case study is running in parallel to the LANDMARC work program. Some of the LANDMARC EO tools are or will also be applied there.

Earth Observation tool, method	Case study # and country		
	10: Canada (wetlands & reforestration)	11: Sweden (biochar)	12: Indonesia (biogas)
In situ			
Soil physical / chemical monitoring	IP- TBC after April 2023		Y
Soil biological monitoring	IP- TBC after April 2023		Y
GHG (gas) flux measurements			
Remote sensing			
Latent heat flux estimates			
Biomass monitoring			Y
Sentinel-5P (TROPOMI)			
Photogrammetry based in LIDAR			
Field mapping			
CarbonMap Tool based on SARS			IP

Table 5: Other land-based mitigation solutions

*Y = Tool (to be) applied; IP = In preparation; UC = Under consideration.

2.6.3 Simulation modelling¹²

The following **Table 6** provides an overview of the current status of the (intended) application of different simulation modelling tools and methods (e.g., DayCent, ALCES, LandSHIFT, E3ME, FABio) within each case study country. The Annexed leaflets provide more context and background information.

	Simulation tool/model				
	DayCent	E3ME	LandSHIFT	ALCES	FABio
Germany		Y			Y
The Netherlands	Y	Y		Y	
Portugal	Y				
Spain	Y	Y		Y	
Sweden		Y			
Switzerland	Y	Y	Y	Y	
Ukraine	Y		IP		
Burkina Faso	Y		Y	Y	
Kenya	Y				
South Africa					
Indonesia		Y	Y	Y	
Nepal				Y	
Vietnam				Y	
Canada		Y		Y	
Venezuela	UC			Y	

Table 6: Overview of (intended) application of simulation modelling tools

*Y = Tool (to be) applied; IP = In preparation; UC = Under consideration.

¹² Simulation modelling work is part of LANDMARC Work package 5 – See **Table 2** in **Section 2.2** for an overview of specific (upcoming / published) research outputs and reports..

2.6.4 Climate hazards analysis in CMIP6 simulations of current and future climate¹³

Introduction

(by Paolo De Luca, Markus Donat- BSC)

Within this section we provide an illustration of how the climate risk information can be presented in the upcoming atlas of climate hazards in future climate scenarios (Deliverable D4.3), presenting global maps of projected changes and changes at regional level. For the presentation of regional changes, here we select 3 different reference regions defined for the IPCC 6th Assessment Reports (see Figure 1b in Iturbide et al. 2020¹⁴). We present here preliminary results of the regions MED (Mediterranean), SEA (South-East Asia) and NWN (North-Western North America), in which several of the LANDMARC case studies are located.

Based on the information provided by the stakeholder consultations for qualitative climate risk analysis (D4.1) and the analysis of climate sensitivities (D4.2), as well as the wider literature, hot temperature extremes and drought were identified as important risk factors for LMTs across all regions interviewed in LANDMARC.

We present preliminary results for a range of indices measuring different aspects of **hot extremes** (these are the heatwave amplitude (hwa), heatwave frequency (hwf), heatwave duration (hwd), the temperature of the hottest day of each year (txx) and the annual number of warm days defined as percentage of days per year with temperatures above the 90th percentile derived for the 1981-2010 period) and **dry extremes** (based on lack of precipitation alone (spi3_dry) and based on lack of water availability taking also evaporation into account (spei3-dry)).

The preliminary results illustrate how hot and dry extremes differ in their regional patterns of future changes. While the measures of hot extremes show increases (of different magnitudes) in almost all regions of the globe, the changes in dry extremes are regionally more heterogeneous, and depend on whether only meteorological drought (=lack of precipitation) or water availability (based on lack of precipitation and atmospheric water demand) are considered, which can even lead to different signals of change in some regions (see e.g., NWN).

CMIP6-ECEarth3 earth system modelling

Global climate and Earth System Model simulations typically have spatial resolutions of 50-100km, and simulated climate at small spatial scales of grid cells are subject to substantial unpredictable variability. Therefore, on the one hand, aggregation over larger areas is usually necessary to analyse robust changes in climate, in particular climate extremes. On the other hand, the local climate risk at the scale of LMT implementations is also affected by specific local climate characteristics such as the local

¹³ Assessing climate change related risks is part of LANDMARC Workpackage 4 – See **Table 2** in **Section 2.2** for an overview of specific (upcoming / published) research outputs and reports..

¹⁴ <https://essd.copernicus.org/articles/12/2959/2020/essd-12-2959-2020.html>

climate variability. To better inform the decision making of LMT stakeholders in their efforts to manage climate change related risks, we aim to provide more spatially explicit climate scenarios. These scenarios could provide a complementary, objective background for taking informed decisions on local climate risk management. Climate risk management processes often include assessments of the exposure, vulnerability, severity/magnitude of a specific LMT to a certain set of (climate) risks. Such risk management processes are generally operated and informed by stakeholders, and stakeholder perceptions with respect to as well exposure, vulnerability, and severity. Providing complementary (more spatially explicit) climate scenario information could aid in rationalizing the risk management process, and to prioritize which risks to manage, and which actions to deploy first.

For assessing the risk of climate-related hazards for specific subregions (under current and future climate conditions over the coming decades through late 21st century) we make use of a large ensemble of climate simulations available from the CMIP6, and simulations with LMT implementations performed with the ECEarth3 Earth System Model. To better inform LMT stakeholders on climate risks at higher spatial resolutions, the climate model data will therefore be matched with local observational data including suitable data provided by local country case studies¹⁵.

At the time of preparing this report, the EC-Earth simulation modelling is still ongoing. However, in the section below we provide some initial results based on climate projections provided as part of the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 6 (CMIP6) for 3 different reference regions¹⁶:

- MED (Mediterranean), hosting LANDMARC case study countries Spain and Portugal
- SEA (South-East Asia), hosting LANDMARC case study countries Vietnam and Indonesia
- NWN (North-Western North America), hosting LANDMARC case study country Canada

We assess the changes in hot and dry extremes in simulations following four different scenarios of future anthropogenic emissions, to illustrate the effects of the different pathways and in particular highlight the benefits from strong mitigation efforts. A description of the different scenarios can be found in this paper¹⁷.

Preliminary results

Here we present the results for a range of indices measuring different aspects of **hot extremes** (these are the heatwave amplitude (hwa), heatwave frequency (hwf), heatwave duration (hwd), the temperature of the hottest day of each year (txx) and the annual number of warm days defined as

¹⁵ Based on the information provided by the stakeholder consultations for qualitative climate risk analysis (D4.1) and the analysis of climate sensitivities (D4.2), as well as the wider literature, hot temperature extremes and drought were identified as important risk factors for LMTs across regions.

¹⁶ Regions as defined for the IPCC 6th Assessment Reports (see Figure 1b in Iturbide et al. 2020: <https://essd.copernicus.org/articles/12/2959/2020/essd-12-2959-2020.html>)

¹⁷ O'Neill, B. C., Tebaldi, C., van Vuuren, D. P., Eyring, V., Friedlingstein, P., Hurtt, G., Knutti, R., Kriegler, E., Lamarque, J.-F., Lowe, J., Meehl, G. A., Moss, R., Riahi, K., and Sanderson, B. M.: The Scenario Model Intercomparison Project (ScenarioMIP) for CMIP6, *Geosci. Model Dev.*, 9, 3461–3482, <https://gmd.copernicus.org/articles/9/3461/2016/>

percentage of days per year with temperatures above the 90th percentile derived for the 1981-2010 period) and **dry extremes** (based on lack of precipitation alone (spi3_dry) and based on lack of water availability taking also evaporation into account (spei3-dry)).

These results illustrate how different aspects of hot and dry extremes differ in their regional patterns of future changes. While the measures of hot extremes show increases (of different magnitudes) in almost all regions of the globe. The changes in dry extremes are regionally more heterogeneous, and depend on whether only meteorological drought (=lack of precipitation) or water availability (based on lack of precipitation and atmospheric water demand) are considered, which can even lead to different sign of change in some regions (see e.g., NWN)

The global maps of simulated changes by the end of the 21st century indicate widespread significant increases in the different hot extremes indices, consistent with a warming climate (Figure 1). These results indicate relatively homogeneous patterns of increased heatwave amplitude (Figure 1a), overall large increases in heatwave frequency especially over northern and central parts of South America, northern Africa, the Arabian peninsula and Indonesia (Figure 1b), substantial increase in the duration of heatwaves over northern Africa and the Arabian peninsula in particular (Figure 1d), overall pronounced increase in the frequency of hot days over northern South America, western, central and eastern Africa, the Arabian peninsula, the Tibetan plateau and Indonesia (Figure 1e), and largest increases in the intensity of hot extremes (measured as the hottest day of the year) over central South America, central north America and Europe.

While the different hot extremes measures show simulated future increases across the globe, the magnitude of changes can differ between regions, and differences also exist between the different scenarios of future greenhouse gas emissions.

For example, in the Mediterranean regions (Figure 3), the amplitude of heatwaves is expected to reach 46°C under the highest emission scenario (SSP5-8.5), but the increases are weaker in scenarios with more limited increases in atmospheric greenhouse gasses: for example 44°C in simulations following SSP3-7.0, 41°C in SSP2-4.5, and only 39°C in the lowest emission scenario (SSP1-2.6), which assumes strong mitigation efforts leading to negative CO₂ emissions (i.e. more CO₂ captured than emitted into the atmosphere) in the second half of the 21st century.

In comparison, the increases in the hot extremes measures are somewhat smaller in North-Western North America (Figure 4), where heatwave amplitude is projected to reach 30°C for the highest emission scenario (SSP5-8.5), 29°C for SSP3-7.0, 26°C for SSP2-4.5 and 24°C under the lower emission one (SSP1-2.6).

The simulated changes in dry extremes differ depending on the index used to measure drought. The SPI measures the lack of precipitation, whereas SPEI also takes into account the atmospheric water demand through evapotranspiration, in addition to precipitation.

The end-of-century changes for the spi3_dry under the SSP5-8.5 point toward both drying and wetting in different regions across the globe (Figure 2, left), reflecting the patterns of annual mean precipitation changes. The CMIP6 models simulate an increase in drought occurrence (based on SPI) over central and South America, the Mediterranean basin, southern Africa, and western Australia. Whereas drought occurrence is projected to decrease over China and in high northern latitudes (e.g., Alaska, Canada, Scandinavia and Russia).

The picture is different when considering the count of dry months computed from SPEI and therefore by taking into account the atmospheric water demand along with precipitation (spei3_dry; Figure 2, right). Here, the end-of-century changes for SSP5-8.5 project a drying over much larger areas compared to SPI-based drought, with regions such as northern Africa, the Mediterranean, the Middle East, and central China being the most affected, while only very small regions in high northern latitudes show decreases in drought occurrence based on this measure.

The regional analysis of simulated changes nicely illustrates these differences between drought measures, and the different magnitudes (and signs) of changes across regions. For example, in the Mediterranean region the number of months with drought conditions is expected to double from 2 to 4 months by the end of the 21st century under the scenario with highest increases in atmospheric greenhouse gases (Figure 6a) for drought measured based on precipitation alone. When also taking the evaporation into account, the drought risk more than doubles to on average 7.5 dry months per year (Figure 6b). In both cases the increases in drought are weaker in scenarios with weaker increases in greenhouse gases, highlighting the value of strong mitigation efforts.

In contrast, in North-west North America the CMIP6 models simulate decreased risk of drought when measured based on precipitation alone (from 3 to about 2 drought months per year on average; Figure 6c), which is consistent with increased precipitation in this region under a warming climate. This increase in precipitation is however also compensated by increased evaporation in a warmer climate, so that the simulations show no clear change in drought when measured with SPEI (i.e. based on both precipitation and evapotranspiration).

Please note that the presented results and discussion are preliminary results, intended to be an indication of what the climate risk assessment in Deliverable D4.3 will provide. We hope these initial results are useful for communications with stakeholders, to provide them with an illustration of the kind of information they can expect later in the project, and to invite their feedback how the information can be more useful for them. The final atlas of projected climate risks will cover more regions, aiming to target all regions relevant for the LANDMARC case study countries. It will also include more climate extremes measures, including indices to measure compound hot and dry events.

Global maps of changes

(a) tx90p ssp585 – hist

(b) txx ssp585 – hist

(c) hwa_tx90 ssp585 – hist

(d) hwd_tx90 ssp585 – hist

(e) hwf_tx90 ssp585 – hist

Figure 1. CMIP6 multi-model projections of hot extremes changes. Maps show median changes between the SSP8-8.5 scenario 2081-2100 and historical 1981-2000 time slices, The hot indices shown are: (a) Number of warm days, (b) Hottest daily temperature of the year, (c) Heatwave Amplitude, (d) Heatwave Duration, (e) Heatwave Frequency. Stippling indicates grid points where the difference is not statistically significant ($p \geq 0.05$) or that did not pass the sign-test ($\leq 80\%$).

Figure 2. CMIP6 multi-model projections of drought changes. Maps show median changes between the SSP8-8.5 scenario 2081-2100 and historical 1981-2000 time slices, The drought indices shown are: (left) number of months when SPI3 is smaller than -1. (right) number of months when SPEI3 is smaller than -1. Stippling indicates grid points where the difference is not statistically significant ($p \geq 0.05$) or that did not pass the sign-test ($\leq 80\%$).

Regional time series of changes across the 4 future emissions scenarios

Figure 3. Projected regional changes of hot extremes in the Mediterranean region. Time-series show MME medians (coloured lines) and interquartile ranges (grey shading) for the historical simulations and four different SSP scenarios.

(a) NWN tx90p

(b) NWN txx

(c) NWN hwa_tx90

(d) NWN hwd_tx90

(e) NWN hwf_tx90

Figure 4. Same as Figure 3 but for Northwestern North America.

Figure 5. Same as Figure 3 but for Southeast Asia.

Figure 6. Projected regional changes of drought in (a,b) the Mediterranean region, (c,d) North-western North America, (e,f) Southeast Asia. For drought measures based on precipitation only (left, spi3_dry) and precipitation and evapotranspiration (right, spei3_dry).

Time-series show MME medians (coloured lines) and interquartile ranges (grey shading) for the historical simulations and four different SSP scenarios.

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Annex 1 – Case study country leaflets

LANDMARC

D2.9: LANDMARC COUNTRY CASE STUDY LEAFLETS

ANNEX I: COUNTRY LEAFLETS

LEAD BENEFICIARY: JIN CLIMATE & SUSTAINABILITY
STATUS: PUBLIC

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Purpose of this document

This document is an Annex to the Deliverable D2.9 of the LANDMARC project and provides an overview of all the case study leaflets on land-based mitigation and negative emission solutions of the LANDMARC project.

Germany

How can forestry, forest restoration and conservation contribute to climate change mitigation?

Introduction

What is the realistic potential for agriculture, forestry, and other land-use sectors to reduce emissions from soils, vegetation and livestock and enhance the uptake of CO₂ from the atmosphere? This question will be answered by the LANDMARC research project, which officially started on the 1st of July 2020. Funded by the European Commission, the nineteen LANDMARC consortium partners work during the project period (2020-2024) on:

- Estimating the climate impact of land-based mitigation technologies (LMTs), for example in agriculture, forestry, and other land-use sectors;
- Assessing the potential for regional and global upscaling of negative emission solutions;
- Mapping their potential environmental, economic, and social co-benefits and trade-offs.

The German case study aims at developing an LMT concept for robust forestry, forest restoration and conservation strategies in Germany including results-based finance mechanisms for carbon accounting and crediting.

Different groups of stakeholders will be engaged to contribute to designing forest development scenarios and concepts for finance mechanisms. We model the development of forest dynamics in Germany for different management types and assumptions for climate change impacts. Outputs are scenarios of forest development and robust management strategies, an overall assessment based on specific indicators, and a concept for finance mechanisms.

What are important LMTs in Germany?

In 2021 the German government agreed in its Federal Climate Protection Act on the national target of considerably reducing GHG emissions until 2030 and reaching GHG neutrality by 2045. GHG neutrality is planned to be achieved by compensating remaining emissions in 2045 through CO₂ removals by natural sinks. Therefore, the government has also set up net sink targets to be achieved by the sector of Land Use, Land Use Change and Forestry (LULUCF). LMTs relevant to Germany were identified that provide the potential to reduce emissions and compensate for residual emissions from the agricultural sector. The technological potential for land-based negative emissions is particularly high in the industrial and energy sector by using bioenergy associated with carbon capture and storage (BECCS). The potential for reducing emissions and storing carbon in the LULUCF sector is mostly with the rewetting of organic soils, abandoning peat extraction, avoiding grassland conversion, increasing soil organic carbon on agricultural land, afforestation, and forest management. The German Environment Agency (UBA 2022) reports net removals by land use in Germany to amount to 11.3 Mt CO₂ in 2020. Forests formed a net sink of -45.8 Mt CO₂ that was compensated to a large degree by net emissions from cropland and grassland (37 Mt CO₂), especially caused by the decomposition of organic soils. There has been a decline in the net storage of carbon in recent years. This is due to a decreasing trend in carbon storage in forests and remaining high levels of emissions from soils. This case study investigates opportunities for **forest management** to contribute to the national target of GHG neutrality and natural sink enhancement.

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Forest Management in Germany

Managed forests in the EU and other industrialised countries currently take up more carbon than they emit. This is due to historic effects related to regrowth after overexploitation and reforestation and the resulting age structure. Keeping sequestration rates at current levels or extending them is an effective LMT. It can contribute to national mitigation targets but also bears risks if forests are not sufficiently adapted to climate change. **German forests** are characterized by rather high carbon stocks. Especially small private forest owners have underutilized their forest resources in the past. Currently, few monetary incentives exist for maintaining and enhancing carbon stocks in forests.

The case study covers the whole forest area in Germany, which is 11.4 Mha. Coniferous trees make up 54 % and deciduous trees cover 46 % of the forest area. Half of the forests are privately owned, with an average property size of 3 ha. About 50 % of private forest properties are below 20 ha and only 13 % of private forest owners manage forests of more than 1,000 ha.

Figure 1: Overview of forest cover in Germany.

Modelling

Model descriptions

Forestry model

Oeko-Institut has been developing the Forestry and Agriculture Biomass Model (FABio) since 2015. FABio-Forest describes the growth of individual trees as a distance-independent individual tree growth

model. Parameters for tree growth and mortality are derived from National Forest Inventory (NFI) data. Assumptions on forest management as well as a climate change drive the future development of tree stands (see Figure 2Error! Reference source not found.).

In addition, FABio includes modules for estimating the carbon stored of wood products, forest litter and soil. The model is based on the following components (see Figure 3):

- a model for the characterisation of tree growth based on diameter, height, site productivity and forest stand density,
- an ingrowth model for the characterisation of new trees based on stand density and tree species,

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Figure 2: Work and information flow in the FABio-Forest model.

- a mortality model for the characterisation of dieback processes depending on tree species, site productivity, age and stand density,
- a deadwood model factoring in the decomposition of dead trees,
- a soil carbon model simulating the decomposition of biomass in litter and soil over time depending on climate factors, and
- a model for the sorting and classification of wood products, i.e., to sort harvested trees into use categories and quantify carbon retention times of wood products.

Figure 3: FABio-Forest model structure and modules.

FABio supports scenario analyses for various silvicultural practices and management scenarios and their effects on wood supply, carbon sequestration and aspects of nature conservation.

Economic model

Implementation of LMT measures in forestry can have impacts on the quality and quantity of the supply of wood. For example, wood supply can be reduced when target diameters are increased to increase carbon storage in forests. Supply of coniferous wood could be reduced if species composition in forests changes due to adaptation measures. More disturbances in forests can also lead to a temporarily higher supply of wood to national and international markets. The case study looks at the impacts on the trade of wood products caused by changes in wood supply from German forests. For assessing these impacts, we use the E3ME¹ model developed by Cambridge Econometrics.

E3ME is a global, macro-econometric model designed to address major economic and economy-environment policy challenges. E3ME covers 61 global regions, with a detailed sectoral disaggregation in each one, and projects forwards annually up to 2050. It is frequently applied at the national level, in Europe and beyond, as well as for global policy analysis. The model considers wood and wood products as well as paper and paper products as separate product categories and Germany as an individual country.

Database description

The key input data for the characterisation of the present state of forests (initialisation) and selection of model parameters (parameterisation) of the model were based on the National Forest Inventory (NFI) database, which compiles results of the analyses of the NFI-2 (carried out in 2002) and NFI-3²

¹ <https://www.camecon.com/how/e3me-model/>

² Available from the BWI results database at <https://bwi.info/>

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(carried out in 2012). The National Forest Inventory follows a sampling schedule in a base grid of 4 km by 4 km. This base grid was condensed to a 2.83 km by 2.83 km or a 2 km by 2 km grid in several regions. A square of 150 m x 150 m is located at every node of the grid (section point). The four resulting section points form the sampling sites for the inventory (assuming they are located in the forest). Thus, a total of more than 47,000 section points with tree cover were recorded in the sampling process. At the four section points of every grid node, the NFI records data related to tree species, tree diameter at breast height, tree height etc. Moreover, several additional features are recorded, e.g. deadwood (type of deadwood, degree of decomposition, diameter class), protected habitats and ecologically relevant trees (veteran trees and tree hollows), and nature conservation areas and use restrictions.

For economic modelling, E3ME uses a historical database covering the period 1970-2019 (with estimates for Covid-19 impacts and recovery for 2021). The main data sources for European countries are Eurostat and the IEA, supplemented by the OECD's STAN database and other sources where appropriate. For regions outside Europe, additional sources for data include the UN, OECD, World Bank, IMF, ILO, and national statistics. More information is provided by the model manual³.

Scenario description

Wood demand

Germany's wood demand is a major driver for the harvest intensity in the scenario. Historical wood harvest until 2021 is reported by Jochem et al. (2022). Assumptions for the wood demand until 2050 originate from the reference scenario modelled by the wood demand model TRAW (Total Resource Assessment of Wood; Glasenapp et al. (2017) and updates in the ongoing project BioSINK⁴). The reference scenario in TRAW covers a projection of the wood energy sectors (households and larger plants) and material use sectors (construction, furniture, packaging, paper, and others). The wood energy demand is supposed to reach a maximum of 68 Mm³ in 2022/2023 due to the energy crisis in the course of the Russian aggression in Ukraine. It declines to about 64 Mm³ in 2030 and about 53 Mm³ in 2050. The material use of wood starts with a demand of 71 Mm³ in 2022, and the wood demand for material increases to 74 Mm³ in 2030 and 79 Mm³ in 2050. This development is mainly driven by increasing demand in the construction sector and smaller parts in the packaging and furniture sector. About 55% of the wood demand is supplied by forests and 45% is secondary wood flows. In 2023, the wood demand from forests peaks at 79 Mm³ and declines to a value of about 75 Mm³ in 2030 and 2050 (excluding bark fraction of 11-12%). About 80% of the demand is for conifers and about 20% for deciduous trees.

Forest management assumptions

The presented scenario is based on the forest management assumptions of the Base scenario described in Böttcher et al. (2018) that represents a projection of the present state and expected developments of forest management in Germany. Past forest restructuring efforts already implemented are expected to continue in this scenario. In consequence, changes in tree species composition occur dynamically but without targeted measures such as planting or tending young trees. The Base Scenario assumes that 427,700 ha or 4.1% of the forest area is excluded from forest management and wood extraction. The target diameter for broadleaf tree species is set to 59 cm, and

³ <https://www.e3me.com/wp-content/uploads/sites/3/2022/12/E3MEManual2022-1.pdf>

⁴ BioSINK project: Impact of the use of forest biomass for energy in Germany on German and international LULUCF sinks (FZK: 3720 43 502 0; financed by the German Environmental Agency)

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the intensity of target diameter use is 79%. For conifers, however, a target diameter of 56 cm and an intensity of target diameter use of 100% as assumed in the more intense Timber Scenario (Böttcher et al. 2018) are applied instead of values from the Base Scenario to be prepared for the high demand for coniferous wood. Tree growth tree and tree mortality are derived from the last inventory period 2002 to 2012. Sensitivity analysis for these two parameters may allow estimation of possible effects from increasing natural disturbances, e.g., due to draughts or beetle calamities (not shown).

Wood supply and trade

In a sensitivity analysis, the implication of changes in wood supply on wood trade patterns has been assessed. We assume an increase in forestry sector output, gradually rising to 25% above current levels (about 80 Mm³ in 2020) by 2050, i.e. 2 billion EUR. E3ME builds on the value of traded goods (in EUR) and does not provide estimates in cubic meters. These are calculated using FAOSTAT Forestry Production and Trade data⁵ estimates of export and import products and value data.

Preliminary results

Projected wood supply and CO₂ storage in forests

Figure 4 provides results on projected wood harvest demand and realized wood removals and the deficit compared to projected demand for wood for different wood assortments and species groups. The assumed wood demand during the simulation can mostly be fulfilled from German forests. There is a deficit for the lowest quality of wood from needle-leaved trees. After 2050 a deficit for industry wood of both coniferous and broadleaved trees is expected according to the scenario.

Figure 4: Projected wood harvest demand and realised removals (left panel) and deficit compared to projected demand for wood (right panel) for different wood assortments and species groups, BL – broadleaved trees, NL – needle-leaved trees.

Figure 5 shows the expected development of total growing stock and forest increment for different species groups. While the stock of needle-leaved tree wood (spruce and pine in particular) is declining, especially in the second half of the simulation, broad-leaved trees gain volume over the simulation period. Spruce and pine lose volume due to the implemented intensive management of coniferous stands. Except douglas fir stocks increase. The species has been introduced into German forests over the last decades, thus many stands are still in a premature phase. The increment of coniferous trees in

⁵ <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/FO>

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Germany decreases over time due to the intensive removal of wood. Despite increasing stocks in forests of deciduous tree species that are typically associated with a decrease in increment due to increased density, deciduous tree increment remains stable. This is because their absolute share increases as a result of forest conversion.

Figure 5: Projected development of total growing stock (left panel) and increment of growing stock (right panel) for different species groups.

Figure 6: Projected forest biomass carbon stock expressed in CO₂ (left panel) and its stock change (right panel) for different biomass compartments and species groups, BL – broadleaved trees, NL – needle-leaved trees.

Figure 6 presents the projected forest biomass carbon stock in German forests expressed in CO₂ and its stock change for different biomass compartments and species groups. Analogue to the development of the wood volume, CO₂ stored in needle-leaved trees' biomass decreases over time, while broad-leaved trees store more CO₂ in the future. The differentiation of the net CO₂ stock change, i.e. the net sink forests for the two species groups reveals that due to their decreasing stock, needle-leaved trees constantly lose CO₂. This loss is compensated by a persistent sink of CO₂ by broadleaved trees. In total the forest sink of living and dead biomass in German forests remains relatively stable at around 15 to 20 Mt CO₂ per year until 2070 and drops thereafter towards zero. The late declining trend is very likely due to the continuous reduction of carbon stocks in coniferous forests that are no longer compensated by the rather slow growth of deciduous tree species. To some extent, there might be carbon stocks in forests also reaching an equilibrium under the assumed management and growth conditions, leading to a small decrease in sink strength also in deciduous forest stands.

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In the remaining time of the project, alternative management scenarios will be developed based on stakeholder perspectives and compared with the reference scenario described above.

Implications for wood trade

We tested the implications of changes in wood supply on national consumption and trade of wood products. A preliminary sensitivity analysis assumed an increase in the wood supply of 25% compared to current levels. The results show that the majority of the additional output is consumed domestically, with a small portion (less than 10%) exported abroad. The increased wood harvest results in a small increase in GDP of around 700 million EUR, representing a 0.02% increase above the baseline level. The GDP impact is negligible in percentage terms because forestry is a relatively small sector in the German economy. Almost all of the GDP increase is driven by additional consumer expenditure, which in turn is driven by the employment gains in the forestry sector. There is a small contribution from exports in the forestry sector, although this is offset by a similar-sized increase in consumer imports, so the contribution of net exports is minor. The 200 million EUR additional exports from the German forestry sector by 2050 are spread across several trading partners, including notably Austria, China, Russia as well as other EU countries.

The sensitivity test shows that the impacts of changes in wood supply can be assessed, however, quantitatively rather limited effects are expected concerning the entire German economy. Further simulations will also include reductions in wood supply and a more detailed analysis of impacts on the national economy.

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Earth Observation

Methodology

Data basis

The case study aims at assessing climate change-related impacts on forest management as a climate change mitigation strategy in Germany. For evaluating climate impacts on forest growth, remote sensing information can be an important data source. In the case study, we explore the relationship between data from a terrestrial survey on tree vitality and remote sensing information. This approach can help identify forests with reduced vitality and potentially create a map of stands at risk under changing climate conditions.

We used maps of annual Solar-Induced Chlorophyll Fluorescence (SIF) provided by the TROPOSIF project⁶. SIF is an electromagnetic signal emitted by the chlorophyll of assimilating plants. The SIF signal responds instantaneously to perturbations in environmental conditions such as light and water stress, which makes it a direct proxy for photosynthetic activity. Data for the period 2018-2021 is available.

The field-based survey, the National Forest Condition Survey (WZE)⁷, is a nationwide survey taking place annually on an area-representative sample grid to assess the vitality condition of forest trees in Germany. The crown condition represents the most widely used indicator for the vitality of forest trees. The crown condition survey is based on the visual assessment of the externally visible condition of single trees. The key parameter of the crown condition survey is defoliation, which is assessed as needle/leaf loss in 5% scores concerning a reference tree. Crown conditions are assessed every July and August on a systematic 16 km x 16 km grid at approx. 10,000 trees and provides representative results for the main tree species at the federal level.

Analysis

For test purposes, we identified 4 crown survey plots, representing the four main species present in German forests (spruce, pine, beech and oak), where the defoliation level has changed considerably between 2016 and 2021. One additional spruce plot with constantly good vitality was selected for comparison. From the TROPOSIF data, the 1-km grid cells in which the plots are located were extracted. The approximate location of the five plots is presented in Figure 16.

Figure 7: Approximate location of the five selected plots from the WZE field survey representing the four major tree species.

⁶ <https://s5p-troposif.noveltis.fr/>

⁷ <https://www.thuenen.de/en/fachinstitute/waldoekosysteme/projekte/bodenschutz-und-waldzustand/projekte-waldzustandserhebung/national-forest-condition-survey>

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Results

Figure 17 presents the results of the test comparing defoliation status derived from the WZE field survey and data on the vitality of trees on the five selected sites.

Remote sensing-derived data on tree vitality show a very high interannual and seasonal variability. Despite considerable losses of foliage recorded by the field survey over the period 2017 to 2022, especially for one spruce and the oak site there is hardly any trend visible in the remote sensing data.

There can be several reasons for the missing relationship. One is the size of the TROPOSIF data that covers one square kilometre. The WZE survey assesses only very few trees located around the survey plot.

Another reason can be influenced by the remote sensing signal from vegetation other than the dominating trees at the survey site. The satellite records also understory trees and ground vegetation vitality that can thus influence the vitality assessment based on such data.

Thus, there are limitations to the tested approach for identifying forests with reduced vitality and potentially creating a map of stands at risk under changing climate conditions.

Alternatively, a more generic approach could be considered, as provided by Bolte et al. (2021) using forest vitality and site parameters.

Figure 8: Time series comparisons for the five selected sites comparing defoliation status (left panels) and NDVI derived from remote sensing data (right panels). Source Nikolai Knapp, pers. comm.

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Qualitative assessment

Climate risk and benefit assessment

As part of the LANDMARC project information from stakeholders was collected to assess the LMTs' risks and effects related to climate exposure. In a survey among experts, information on potential impacts on forest management was gathered. The information was complemented by scientific literature and national statistics.

Climate risks

Droughts and heat waves are the main climate risks for forests in Germany and thus for LMT implementation. The risk has increased in the past years as periods of low precipitation and heat waves occur more frequently. This leads directly to a higher vulnerability of forests as they become more fire-prone, and are less vital to stand against storms and to defend themselves against biotic disturbances, such as insects. The severity of climate risks depends also on the management, e.g., species and age composition and stand structure.

Bolte et al. (2021)⁸ report that German forests suffered severe damage due to a series of very dry years from 2018 to 2020. In total 187 Mm³ of salvage logging was recorded and 285,000 ha need to be reforested. In comparison, the amount of salvage logged wood from 2014 to 2017 was 38.5 m³⁹. Extremely affected were spruce stands impacted by bark beetle infestation after being weakened by drought stress. Spruce-dominated stands that can be considered to be exposed to a high risk of drought and insect infestation cover 2.85 Mha (Bolte et al. 2021). Also, beech trees suffer from drought stress in 2019 and 2020, especially in shallow sites. Other factors playing a role in the dynamics of damage according to experts include a lack of evaporative cooling and heat waves causing tissue damage on leaves and branches and cambial damage. The weakened trees are then less resilient regarding secondary threats such as insects or fungi.

The National Forest Condition Survey (WZE)⁷ documented that the recent drought years lead to widespread premature defoliation. In 2021 only 21.3% of the surveyed trees had a complete and intact crown. 42% of mature trees older than 60 years had severely defoliated crowns, while 17% of the trees below that age were severely affected. The mortality rate of all trees reached 1.7% in 2020 in comparison to 1.2% in 2021. The mortality declined for spruce and pine but increased for beech and oak.

Benefits and tradeoffs

The measures to promote carbon sinks in the forest can be implemented in the existing forest area, which means that, compared to other land-based climate protection measures, there is no direct competition for land and thus a limited risk of increasing competition for land. A key conflict of the option to increase carbon stocks in the forest, however, is with economic interests in timber harvesting, especially for conifers. Currently, timber production is the main source of income for forest

⁸https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Andreas-Bolte-3/publication/349440262_Zukunftsaufgabe_Waldanpassung/links/624bea1e21077329f2f380fc/Zukunftsaufgabe-Waldanpassung.pdf?origin=publication_detail

⁹ https://www.destatis.de/DE/Presse/Pressemitteilungen/2022/04/PD22_170_41.html

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owners. Moreover, there can be leakage effects caused by reduced timber supply leading to the increased harvest of forests outside Germany.

Benefits from the protection of biodiversity occur when native deciduous tree species are promoted in the future and a higher proportion of older trees is left in the forest. Old-growth forests with native species composition are basically not existing in Germany. In addition, a higher proportion of deadwood and a higher diversity of deadwood structures (lying, standing, different dimensions) also contribute to improved biodiversity (Reise et al. 2017; Reise et al. 2019). Promoting more deciduous trees in the forest can lead to higher groundwater percolation rates, compared to coniferous stands (Müller 2019).

Stakeholder engagement

The identification of stakeholders followed recommendations given in the LANDMARC project. For the case study, a national stakeholder network was established, including stakeholders from forest authorities, private forests and their associations, and science was identified. Interactions with stakeholders were performed in different formats, such as workshops, phone calls, working sessions, and work meetings but also on more official occasions such as dialogues organized by ministries. Over 20 events were documented since mid-2020.

The main conclusions from the engagement of stakeholders are that a system for ecosystem payments for forests should be established, and that forest owners do have a source of income besides cutting and selling timber. Such a system should reward the efforts and ambitions to develop a forest towards a more climate-resilient ecosystem that further provides society with clean air, water retention capacities, healthy soils, and biodiversity and contributes crucially to the goal of C removal. Forest owners are mostly opposing the idea of set-aside forest areas and take them out of management to let the forest ecosystem develop at its own pace. A lot of open questions remain, such as how to reward a forest owner that already started the development of his forests into climate resilience 30 years ago without having any incentives. What goals can this person still reach and can be rewarded for? Or shall those efforts be rewarded retroactively?

Soon there will be further stakeholder engagement as in the ongoing project DIFENS¹⁰ a Delphi study collects expectations among forest sector representatives regarding major developments in the future.

Policy instruments

Incentive systems for rewarding ecosystem and environmental protection services in land use in general and climate protection services in forest management have been discussed for some years. Several campaigns by stakeholder groups have shown that there is great interest in an incentive system for climate protection in the forest among forest owners. However, there is also a limited understanding of the different options for incentive schemes and the respective implications and requirements for participation.

Funded by the German Environment Agency, a concept for the development of a modular incentive system with two pillars to reward biodiversity and carbon sink services has been developed by Oeko-Institut and colleagues (Böttcher et al. 2022). The two pillars include A) support payments for the implementation of ecological forest management and B) the creation of market-based certificate trading. While Pillar A can build on existing support schemes established by the German government,

¹⁰ <https://www.difens.de>

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including payments for taking forests out of production, retaining old trees in forests, and increasing deadwood in forests. Pillar B requires the establishment of technical infrastructure.

Pillar B represents a largely privately organized remuneration of the carbon sink performance through tradable forest certificates and is not subject to subsidy law. The reference value is the forest area of the farm and a state-determined carbon sink value (t CO₂/ha/a) of the forest certificate. The number of allowances to which a farm is entitled can be determined by a pooled approach (established carbon sink performance of a region considered as a pool) or by other forms of determination (e.g., effects of operational measures for large farms). The implementation of Pillar B requires additional institutions (e.g., registry) and data (e.g., pool allocation) and can therefore probably only be realized in the medium term.

The case study will provide a data basis for assessing the impacts of this policy instrument by simulating the implementation of certain aspects of the incentive schemes in privately owned forests in Germany with a special focus on measures foreseen under Pillar A.

Preliminary conclusions

Measures to increase carbon stocks should therefore be targeted towards more resilient broadleaved forests that are currently mostly used for energy wood and accompanied by measures to a) reduce energy wood consumption and b) establish payment systems for ecosystem services by forests.

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Contact us!

Effective engagement of key stakeholders of the forestry sector enables a better understanding of mitigation options, their potential, and barriers as well as the development of more robust data collection assessment work. This a) helps develop better quality (and more feasible) scaling up and implementation scenarios, and b) improves the uptake of research results and findings in policy and practice.

LANDMARC relies on consultations with stakeholders through the country case studies and our regional engagement activities to link stakeholder knowledge to the application of earth observation techniques and climate, economic and land-use models.

Interested stakeholder are invited to contact us and will be provided with more information. An exchange and a possible engagement into our activities to assess preliminary results will be very much appreciated.

What we provide

Get insights into up-to-date forestry demand scenarios and tools applied for projecting the development of forests under alternative future scenarios. More specifically, we can provide:

- Background information about the applied models and tools;
- Preliminary results from model application and preliminary model runs.

How you can contribute

We are currently looking for stakeholders across the forestry sector (forest practitioners, forest owners, NGOs, researchers, industry, public sector, etc.) to:

- Conduct interviews about expectations among forest sector representatives regarding major developments in the sector;
- Exchange information about the impacts of mitigation and adaptation measures on the national economy;
- Exchange economic information on costs of the implementation of different mitigation and adaptation measures in forests;
- Discuss the specification of alternative management scenarios of forest management to be conducted in the case study.

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The Netherlands

Forestry, Agroforestry, Peatland rewetting/Paludiculture and biogas-based CCS

Introduction

What is the realistic potential for agriculture, forestry, and other land-use sectors to reduce gas emissions from soils, vegetation and livestock and enhance the uptake of CO₂ from the atmosphere? This question will be answered by the LANDMARC research project, which officially started on the 1st of July 2020. Funded by the European Commission, the nineteen LANDMARC consortium partners work during the project period (2020-2024) on:

- Estimating the climate impact of land-based negative emission solutions, for example in agriculture, forestry, and other land-use sectors
- Assessing the potential for regional and global upscaling of negative emission solutions
- Mapping their potential environmental, economic, and social co-benefits and trade-offs

What do we do with Land-based Mitigation Technologies (LMTs) in NL?

1. LMT Earth Observation

In our **Agroforestry** and **Paludiculture/peat soil rewetting** case studies, we directly collect soil samples, analyze them concerning soil health and soil processes and compare the results with an area where LMTs are not applied (benchmark). This is to evaluate if the locations where LMTs are applied score better than usual in terms of soil functions (GHG storage, (de-) nitrification, methane emissions, etc.). Also, it is our ambition to calibrate remote sensing signals with this in-situ data, so that larger areas can be more cost-efficiently monitored.

2. LMT Modelling

Next to the primary data collection in our case studies, we investigate the impact of scaling up an LMT portfolio consisting of (1) agroforestry, (2) forestry, (3) paludiculture/rewetting, and (4) BECCS based on domestic biomass. The impact of scaling up those technologies will be assessed via a qualitative assessment (see next point) and the application of simulation models. For this, we currently apply three different models:

1. **E3ME** to assess the impact on the economy (GDP, employment), land-use change, and national emissions, and
2. **ALCES** to visualize the impact of LMTs on land-use change and carbon sequestration.
3. **DayCent** is a biogeochemical model to simulate carbon and nitrogen fluxes between the atmosphere, vegetation, and soil.

3. Qualitative risk and co-benefit analysis of LMTs

In a series of semi-structured interviews, we ask stakeholders about the (perceived) risks and (co-) benefits of large-scale implementation of our LMT portfolio. We obtain information about how the implementation could be affected by a changing climate (e.g., more droughts, higher precipitation, etc.) but also how we can benefit from it aside from its climate benefit (e.g., more biodiversity, employment, etc.).

Earth Observation

In the Netherlands, we apply innovative methods to assess changes in vegetation, land use and climatic conditions using different Earth Observation (EO) tools *including in-situ and remote sensing techniques to monitor the potential and effectiveness of agroforestry and paludiculture to reduce GHG emission.*

Figure 9: Dutch agroforestry and paludiculture case study sites

Earth Observation – Agroforestry

Afforestation of agricultural land is supported by agricultural policy to make agriculture more environmentally friendly. Both production forests – aimed at generating wood – and food forests - directed at producing food – can be realised. Integrating forestry and agriculture delivers certain benefits over the conventional way of land use such as:

1. **Increase in spatial diversity and biodiversity**
Agroforestry allows for a more attractive habitat for insects, birds and other animals.
2. **Increase in soil structure and health**
Planting trees and shrubs into annual cropping systems can protect the otherwise exposed land and its soil from wind stress and strong precipitation. Additionally, agroforestry increases root diversity that feeds the living organisms within the soil.
3. **Carbon sequestration**
Agroforestry increases the absorption of CO₂ permanently from the atmosphere in soil organic matter and thereby stores it effectively, which contributes to climate change mitigation.
4. **Alternative sources of income**
Agroforestry may generate an alternative income source for land users if benefits exceed costs. These benefits may originate from both product revenues and reimbursements for carbon storage.

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The idea within LANDMARC is also to team up with agroforestry present in Spain, Vietnam, Burkina Faso and Indonesia. At these pilot sites, novel agroforestry technologies are demonstrated to enable the transition from conventional agriculture toward more climate-resilient agroforestry.

Figure 10: Soil sampling locations for agroforestry

For the **in-situ measurements** in the agroforestry case study, soil samples were collected in Alphen, North Brabant. On the case study site, conventional monoculture cropland was converted into an alley-cropping agroforestry system. The sampling was conducted at three sites within the agroforestry system following a satellite-based approach to indicate the sampling points. Figure 2 shows the sampling sites comprising P1 (GL: grassland planted between the walnuts/hazelnut tree rows), P2 (RT: a combination of samples representing plots with flowers and walnuts/hazelnut tree rows) and P3 (GL: grassland planted between the walnuts/hazelnut tree rows in a different location than in P1 and P2). For the analysis of the results, the agroforestry system was compared to two control sites: 1) a monoculture cropland system, in this case, a potato plantation (C|P), and 2) another control site in between the agroforestry and the potato plantation (C|Agrof).

In agroforestry, we focus our analysis on the effect of soil physicochemical properties, which are directly connected with the soil microbial community. Agroforestry is supposed to increase the soil's organic carbon due to plenty of organic matter input in the form of litter falls and fine roots from trees. In our study, organic matter (OM) and nitrogen (N) decreased on average in the agroforestry system (Table 1). One reason can be that samples were taken from crop alleys, which may receive less tree litter or roots since the trees were young. However, with tree growth, the crop alleys will receive more organic matter from the trees. In addition, also the high demand for nutrients for the younger trees to build up their biomass could lead to a decrease in soil nutrients.

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Table 1: Main soil indicators and plant-available nutrients of agroforestry and control sites

Soil factor	Target range	P1/P2*	P3*	C*
		Agroforestry		Control
pH	5,6 - 6,1	5,0	4,7	4,9
Organic Matter				
%	-	1,7	1,8	2
C/OS	0,45 - 0,55	0,50	0,64	0,51
N (kg N/ha)	3750 - 5470	4700	4690	5410
C/N ratio	13 - 17	12	13	12
P	6,1 - 10,1	6,8	17,2	8
K	235 - 370	370	190	215

* P1/P2 represent a composite soil sample. P3 has a different sampling as it has a different location. The C represent the control between agroforestry and potato plantation.

Besides the soil properties, the diversity and biomass of soil microbial communities are the major regulators of fundamental ecosystem processes, such as organic matter decomposition, nutrient cycling, and gaseous fluxes. Specifically, the diversity of bacteria, archaea and fungi was analysed. Bacteria and fungi are the most dominant microbial groups in soils and constitute the base of the soil food web (a community of organisms living all or part of their lives in the soil interacting in an ecological community). Bacteria feed on relatively easily degradable parts of organic matter, while fungi can decompose recalcitrant plant polymers. Archaea occur ubiquitously but are less prominent and less diverse in comparison with other microbes.

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Figure 11: (A) Alpha-diversity including richness and Shannon index of the bacterial, archaeal and fungal soil community. Higher or lower values indicate higher or lower richness or diversity, respectively. **(B)** Bacterial principal coordinate analysis (PCoA) to present similarity and dissimilarity between samples. Samples represented by points close to each other are more similar and more distant from each other are more dissimilar. **(C)** The abundance of the LDA scores for soil functions was computed for groups with differential abundance among the bacterial communities. Higher abundances of the functions are coloured in red. In the graph, functions related to the nitrogen cycle were highlighted with the red square. **(D)** Gene abundance of the RuBisCO gene of bacteria done through quantitative PCR (qPCR) is one measure to express carbon fixation observed in the Agroforestry soil samples.

Within our case study site, the different plots (grassland and rows of trees) exhibited different results. Figure 5A shows a higher bacterial and fungal diversity richness (number of taxonomic groups) in grassland than in the presence of trees. On the other side, the figure shows a slightly higher archaeal and fungal diversity in the tree rows (this is a quantitative indicator of the number of different microbes, considering the uniformity in the distribution of these bacteria in these species). Both controls (C|P and C|Agrof) showed equivalent fungal diversity and richness and the potato soil plantation presented higher bacterial and archaeal diversity. Due to the variability exhibited in the samples, none of the diversity analyses for bacteria, archaea and fungi was significantly different.

Figure 3B shows similarities and dissimilarities of the samples particularly for microbes. The results show that the microbes present in agroforestry and control were not specific to each location, i.e.,

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there was great variability in agroforestry between samples and no clear clusters could be identified for grassland and tree rows. Based on the microbes present in the soil, it is possible to predict what they are doing. This is shown in Figure 3C where one can observe that functions related to nitrification and denitrification have a higher abundance in rows with trees in agroforestry. This means that the nitrogen (N) is being transformed in the soil in a way that could lead to higher nitrogen oxide (N₂O) emissions or greater potential for nitrate removal through denitrification, which may reduce nitrate leaching. Moreover, the analysis shows a higher abundance of degradation routes for tree rows. This is an important contributor to soil health as healthy soils depend on the ability of soil microbes to detoxify toxic pollutants that could reach soil from various routes while grassland in agroforestry showed a higher abundance of functions related to the production of antibiotics and intracellular parasites. Probably the previous presence of antibiotics in this area led to the increase of microbes able to metabolize these molecules.

For a more precise quantification of genes related to carbon sequestration, one of the genes related to Ribulose 1,5-bisphosphate carboxylase-oxygenase (RuBisCO) was assessed (Figure 3D). RuBisCO is an enzyme responsible for the fixation of carbon derived from atmospheric CO₂ as part of the Calvin-Benson cycle that leads to the production of the glucose essential for growth in most photosynthetic organisms. Our results showed that all different locations between agroforestry and controls showed similar abundances related to C fixation and there were no statistical differences (Tuckey test).

Earth Observation – Paludiculture/rewetting peatland strategy

LANDMARC in collaboration with Carbon Connects (CCONNECTS) and stakeholders including the water boards 'Aa en Maas' and land users aims to explore to which extent C losses from peat soils can be reduced by using paludiculture in the Netherlands. Paludiculture is the practice of crop production on wet soils, predominantly occurring in peatlands. Wet soil cannot be used to grow standard crops and has limited capacity to support cattle. When drained for agriculture, stored C from peatlands is released into the atmosphere as CO₂. Therefore, to achieve a zero or negative carbon balance in paludiculture, the water level has to be close to the surface to guarantee water saturation of the peat body. Crops adapted to wet conditions, such as cattail, can grow in peatlands and their biomass can be used for a range of applications, including fodder. In addition, these saturated soils can also be used as wet grasslands (e.g. by light dairy cows). The paludiculture pilot site is located in Swinkels and was implemented in August 2020 with the infilling of the central drainage ditch and construction of low peat bunds as well as the construction of a subsoil irrigation system at the perimeter of the pilot field. Cattail was planted in September 2020, as well as an installation that shall prevent severe damage by geese grazing the young plants. The soil samples were taken from rewetted peatland (soil and water) and a reference site (degraded peatland). The main results related to C sequestration for soil properties (Table 2), soil microbial diversity (Figure 12A) and soil microbial structure and functions (Figure 12B and Figure 12C) are represented in their respective figures or table.

Table 2: Main soil indicators and plant-available nutrients of agroforestry and control sites.

Soil factor	Target range	P1*	P2*
pH	5.1 – 5.7	5.6	5.5
Organic Matter			
%	-	16.2	36.7

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C/OS	0.45 – 0.55	0.48	-
N (kg N/ha)	1,850 – 2,700	23,090	22,770
C/N ratio	13 - 17	12	15
P	3.0 - 5.0	21.6	0.5
K	115 - 185	70	80

*The samples P1 and P2 are representing replicates of the paludiculture soil location.

For the soil properties, the paludiculture soil samples present a high organic matter and the C/OS ratio which indicates organic matter with good properties relating to nutrient supply and stability. Furthermore, the results of the soil analysis show that the C/N ratio fall is moderately low. Still, this indicates a good supply of nitrogen from organic matter (Table 2).

Besides the soil properties, the diversity and biomass of soil microbial communities (bacteria, archaea and fungi) were analysed. In general, soil paludiculture has higher richness and diversity for bacteria, archaea and fungal communities (Figure 12A). Water paludiculture showed lower richness and diversity compared with soil paludiculture except for the archaeal diversity index. The microbes present in paludiculture were specific to each compartment (soil and water) (Figure 12B). Microbial soils were more similar to each other compared to water microbiota, even though paludiculture samples from soil and water were taken from the same location. This is consistent as microbes assemble as a result of dispersal, abiotic and biotic characteristics of the habitat as well as stochasticity. That means that soil and water present different habitats, mainly aerobic for soil and anaerobic for water that makes a different selection for microbial growth. Still, the microbes present in the paludiculture soils are considered different from the control soils.

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Figure 12: (A) Alpha-diversity including richness and Shannon index of the bacterial, archaeal and fungal soil community. Higher or lower values indicate higher or lower richness or diversity, respectively. **(B)** Bacterial principal coordinate analysis (PCoA) to present similarity and dissimilarity between samples. Samples represented by points close to each other are more similar and more distant from each other are more dissimilar. **(C)** The abundance of the LDA scores for soil functions was computed for groups with differential abundance among the bacterial communities. Higher abundances of the functions are coloured in red. In the graph, functions related to the CH₄ emissions and consumption of the C cycle were highlighted with the red square.

Concerning their microbial functions, paludiculture soils significantly promoted functions linked to methanogenesis (Figure 12C). Methanogenesis is anaerobic respiration that generates methane as the final product of metabolism. This indicates that paludiculture potentially promoted an increase in CH₄ production and emission after rewetting. However, at the same time, the analysis shows also an increase in methanotrophy. Methanotrophy can be described as the opposite function of methanogenesis – it is another respiration form that metabolizes methane as its source of carbon and chemical energy indicating the possibility of methane consumption occurring in parallel to emission. Therefore, for a more concise balance of methane consumption and emission, a qPCR analysis was done to clarify which processes are occurring in higher abundances. The analysis confirmed that both processes (emission with the detection of gene *mcrA* and consumption with the detection of gene *pmoA*) are occurring in the soil (Figure 12), however, the ratio of methane consumption is higher than the methane emission (Table 3Table 3).

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Figure 4: Assessment of genes related to methane emissions (left - methanogenesis) and methane consumption (right - methanotrophy) for the different sampling sites (C=Control, P_S=Paludiculture Soil, P_W=Paludiculture Water)

Table 3: Observed number of genes in samples that are responsible for methane consumption and emission

Sampling location	Methane consumption (<i>pmoA</i> gene)	Methane emission (<i>mcrA</i> genes)	Ratio
Peatland Soil	54,666,667	23,766,667	2.30
Peatland Water	900,000	57,000	15.78
Control	33,333,333	14,733,333	2.26

Modelling

Next to the primary data collection in our case studies, we investigate the impact of scaling up an LMT portfolio consisting of (1) agroforestry, (2) forestry, (3) paludiculture, and (4) BECCS based on anaerobic digestion of domestic biomass. The impact of scaling up those technologies will be assessed via a qualitative assessment (see next point) and the application of models. For the LMT portfolio, we currently apply two different models:

- E3ME** to assess the impact on the economy (GDP, employment), land-use change, and national emissions, and
- ALCES** to visualize the impact of LMTs on land-use change and carbon sequestration.

We also assess the feasibility of using the **DayCent** model to evaluate carbon sequestration, particularly in agroforestry.

E3ME preliminary model results

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E3ME is a macro-econometric model designed to assess global policy challenges. It is the most advanced econometric model in the world and is widely used for policy assessment, forecasting and research purposes. The model is owned and maintained by Cambridge Econometrics.

By applying E3ME in the Netherlands, we explore the impact of scaling up the whole LMT portfolio on land-use change (see Figure 5), the economic impact in terms of the national GDP as well as the labour market, and national emissions.

Figure 13: Impact of scaling up forestry, agroforestry, peatland management and AD-based BECCS on the Dutch land use – Increase of increased agroforestry and forestry are likely to limit agricultural land use

Based on the preliminary data, we can observe a slightly negative impact of scaling up the LMT portfolio on the GDP compared to the baseline. This is mainly due to a) reduced agricultural land use that leads to lower agriculture supply and a resulting decrease in exports, and b) Increased prices lead to a slight decrease in consumer expenditure. One factor that has not been accounted for yet is the costs of soil subsidence that can be partly avoided by rewetting peatlands.

Figure 14: GDP, % difference from baseline

Table 4: Sectoral results, % difference from baseline 2050

Sector	Output	Employment
Agriculture, forestry & fishing	-7.1	-0.1

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Mining & Utilities	-0.6	1.4
Manufacturing	-0.3	-0.1
Construction	-0.1	-0.1
Market Services	-0.2	-0.1
Non-market services	0.0	0.0

Table 4 shows the impact of scaling up the LMT portfolio on the Output and labour market of the economic sectors in the Netherlands. What the preliminary model results show is that:

- Agriculture, forestry, and fishing output are expected to be mainly hit because of increased cost and reduced land area impacting the agricultural sector. Employment in agriculture particularly is negatively impacted, but not on the same scale as production.
- Most other sectors see a decline in activity because of higher prices impacting demand:
 - Employment follows a similar trend to output
 - In Mining & utilities, we see an increase in employment because of the energy supply sector
 - Utilities see a decrease in activity mainly because of sewage & wastewater management requirements

Figure 15: Modelled outcomes of Dutch carbon dioxide and methane emissions until 2050

Figure 7 shows the development of Dutch carbon dioxide and methane emissions comparing the LMT scaling-up scenario to the baseline. Overall, a decrease in CO2 emissions can be observed, mainly due

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to increased use of BECCS, afforestation and agroforestry. Methane emissions show a decrease as well due to the increased use of biodigesters, and peatland rewetting.

ALCES application

ALCES simulates changes in landscape composition and related indicators (e.g., wildlife habitat & populations, ecosystem services, & economic performance) in response to land-use scenarios. The model also tracks landscape composition in response to multiple drivers such as land use (forestry, agriculture, etc.), natural disturbance (e.g., fire, insects), and climate. Simulated landscape composition is applied to track indicator response through user-defined equations that can be based on empirical relationships or stakeholder preferences. In the Netherlands, the ALCES modelling focuses on the following questions:

1. Are the LMTs that make up the portfolio compatible with each other? Compatibility may be of concern because the LMTs are directly or indirectly related to livestock production. Some LMTs, such as increasing groundwater levels in peat meadows, afforestation, and agroforestry, have the potential to reduce livestock production whereas the success of BECCS is at least partially reliant on livestock production as a source of biomass. As well, afforestation and agroforestry may compete for pasture that can either be converted to forest or silvopasture. As such, there may be a trade-off between LMTs. Simulations will explore the potential trade-off.
2. To what degree could the LMTs be impacted by other land-use sectors, most notably urbanization? Competition between land uses is intense in the Netherlands due to the relatively small size of the land base. Other land uses, most notably urbanization, have resulted in a gradual decline in the agricultural land base and the decline is likely to continue. The LMTs are reliant on agricultural land and ongoing erosion of the agricultural land base by urbanization could constrain opportunities to implement the LMT portfolio. Simulations will explore how urbanization could constrain LMT implementation.

Figure 16: Snapshot of the ALCES model showing the ecosystem carbon density [ton C/ha] in the Netherlands (the lighter the colour the higher the carbon density)

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DayCent application

DayCent is a Biogeochemical land-use management model that can simulate crop biomass and/or yields, soil carbon and nitrogen dynamics, N₂O emissions, nutrient dynamics and GHG fluxes in different plant or soil systems. The model can simulate long-term ecosystem responses to changes in climate, land use and agricultural management practices in cropland, grassland, forest, and savanna ecosystems.

In the Netherlands, we explore if we can apply the model to simulate above- and belowground carbon agroforestry systems (see Figure 9).

Figure 17: Preliminary DayCent modelling results for above- and belowground carbon development when scaling-up agroforestry

Qualitative Assessment

Climate Risk Assessment

The main objective of an LMTs is to provide a 'climate service' by a) keeping carbon stored (emission reductions by moving from the "baseline" scenario in which carbon would have been emitted to the atmosphere), or b) by absorbing additional carbon from the atmosphere (actual carbon sequestration). To be climate-relevant the net climate impact of an LMT should be **permanent**.

However, **ongoing climate change is one of the key risks** to the LMTs which may limit or prevent the climate service delivered. Well-known risks are the immediate climate risks or hazards, like floods, droughts, and wildfires. For example, peat soil rewetting may prevent oxidation of soil carbon, but with increasing and prolonged droughts periods this climate service may not be delivered.

Next to the climate risks, we also consider the assessment of key risks, co-benefits and trade-offs of LMT scaling up to the national level. **Co-benefits** can be factors such as the diversification of products when implementing agroforestry. In terms of other risks than those directly related to climate change there are e.g., a) **societal risks** such as a lack of social support to implement the technology by threatening societal groups and/or creating inequalities among them, b) **technology/practice risks** such technical challenges when implementing and/or scaling up the technology, and c) **environmental risks** posed by LMT implementation impacting the nature/environment including human, flora and fauna ecosystems.

Our goal of the qualitative risk and co-benefit assessment is to identify and analyse **together with stakeholders** the key socio-economic and environmental risks, co-benefits and trade-offs associated with scaling up LMT. The collected data will be used to advance the development of LMT country narratives and scenarios which among others serve as an input for the applied models.

The initial findings from the stakeholder interviews about climate-change-related risks and sensitivities are described below.

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Climate Change-related risks and sensitivities – initial findings from stakeholder interviews

(Agro-)Forestry

The main benefits mentioned by stakeholders are that agroforestry would allow stabilising the soil, improving the hydric balance, improving nutrient retention (especially in those cases in which agroforestry is paired with livestock farming), making the soil more resilient to floods (especially in hilly areas) and droughts, improving carbon fixation and improving biodiversity. Also, improved resilience to plagues is expected as the insect diversity improves. Agroforestry would moderately make croplands more resilient to climate extremes, as the trees are generally more resilient to climate extremes than crops, and these get protected by the presence of trees.

However, the implementation of agroforestry faces many challenges. **One major challenge is related to the fact that the above-mentioned benefits materialize just in the long term** considering that the period between the plantation of the young tree and the first economically productive harvest ranges between 5 to 15 years. **The other main constraint to the implementation of agroforestry is the policy framework;** current Dutch legislation does not allow the removal of trees from croplands without afforesting with the same amount of trees somewhere else, so once agroforestry is implemented, land owners may feel there is no “way back” in case the system does not work.

Another major constraint is that agricultural lands are considered forest lands once they reach a certain amount of trees per unit area. Once the land is considered forest land, it cannot be used for agriculture anymore.

From the interviewees' perspective of the general public's point of view, the dominant position is to support agroforestry as it would bring benefits in terms of biodiversity.

Peatland Rewetting

Droughts and heavy rainfalls are the main climate risks for peatland rewetting. Droughts decrease water availability so keeping a high water table requires extra water. Heavy rainfall could flood the topsoils and above-ground vegetation more rapidly. Sea level rise could be an important risk factor in the future due to the salination of waters and compromising safety by increasing pressure on dams.

Flooded topsoils can make the fields unworkable and less productive when they are too wet. A crucial part of the rewetting project should thus not be only the water inlet, but also any excess overflow capacity to prevent too high topsoil saturation levels. Peatland rewetting implies a more intensive use of water in case of low precipitations, and that can lead to insufficient water availability in case of drought and extensive use.

The use of this technique reduces greenhouse gas emissions by avoiding the oxidation of the peat layers of the soil.

Peatland rewetting could decrease or even completely stop soil subsidence (of up to 8 meters in the assessed area), especially in areas with clay on peat soils. This is a huge benefit for society, but the costs are incurred by the farmer, so frameworks for re-distributing these benefits are needed.

BECCS

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There are very few climate change-related risks linked to this technology. There may be some more indirect climate change-related risks that could affect the provision of animal feed to livestock. The same applies to environmental risks, with the main concern being the potential leakage of methane.

The main environmental advantage of this technique is a strong decrease in methane emissions and the easy collection of the CO₂ derived from this process. This is particularly interesting when applied to a small scale. Economic feasibility is very dependent on external subsidies. The production of biogas is linked to intensive livestock farming. The more livestock is allowed to graze outdoors, the less the ratio of manure that can be retrieved so it could somehow conflict with a future trend in improving animal wellbeing.

Contact Us

Effective engagement of key stakeholders in LMTs enables a better understanding of LMT feasibility- its potential and barriers to scaling up as well as the development of more robust data collection assessment work. This a) helps develop better quality (and more feasible) LMT scaling up and implementation scenarios, and b) improves the uptake of research results and findings in policy and practice.

LANDMARC relies on consultations with stakeholders through the country case studies and our regional engagement activities to link stakeholder knowledge to the application of earth observation techniques and climate, economic and land-use models.

We invite interested stakeholders to participate in our engagement activities to exchange our (preliminary) assessment results and to contribute to climate change mitigation by sharing their tacit knowledge with us.

Become now part of our project to contribute to climate change mitigation!

What we can provide:

By being part of the national stakeholder network, you will be able to connect to a broad network that includes actors from different backgrounds across agriculture, forestry, and other land-use sectors. Moreover, you can get access to additional data, and literature, and disseminate and exchange relevant results, insights and experiences with a broader group of national stakeholders. Furthermore, by being involved in this European-funded H2020 research and innovation project, you will improve your visibility in an international context. More specifically, we can provide:

- Background information about the applied models and earth observation tools
- Preliminary results from earth observation tool application and preliminary model runs
- Advanced country narratives explaining our current view on LMT deployment in the Netherlands.

How can you contribute?

We are currently looking for stakeholders across all sectors (LMT practitioners, landowners, NGOs, researchers, industry, public sector, etc.) to:

Contact us

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- **Conduct interviews** about general risks and specific climate risks, co-benefits and trade-offs to the implementation and deployment of the individual LMTs (1) agroforestry, (2) forestry, (3) paludiculture, and (4) BECCS based on domestic biomass.
- **Exchange information about Dutch land-use datasets** to augment global data sources used for model initialization. e.g., for the location of pasture/cattle and drained peat areas, and priority areas for afforestation and agroforestry.
- **Exchange economic data about the LMTs, e.g., BECCS cost information** such as component costs of mono manure digestion incl. CCS, Biogas upgrading costs, the potential scale of anaerobic digestion of manure, etc.
- **Discuss technical information about:**
 - Rates of organic and mineral fertilizer on conventional cropland in comparison to agroforestry plots (amount of N most important as it determines AF biomass growth)

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Portugal and Spain

Pastures in Montado/Dehesas

Introduction

What is the realistic potential for agriculture, forestry, and other land-use sectors to reduce emissions from soils, vegetation and livestock and enhance the uptake of CO₂ from the atmosphere? This question will be answered by the LANDMARC research project, which officially started on the 1st of July 2020. Funded by the European Commission, the nineteen LANDMARC consortium partners work during the project period (2020-2024) on:

- Estimating the climate impact of land-based negative emission solutions, for example in agriculture, forestry, and other land-use sectors
- Assessing the potential for regional and global upscaling of negative emission solutions
- Mapping their potential environmental, economic, and social co-benefits and trade-offs

What do we do with Land-based Mitigation Technologies (LMTs) in Portugal and Spain?

1. LMT Earth Observation

The combined Portuguese and Spanish case study carried out by AgroInsider and Ambienta comprises the study on carbon sequestration potential in Montado (Portugal) and Dehesas (Spain). These are a High Nature Value (HNV) system characterised by high complexity because of the interactions between climate, soil, pasture (natural pastures, fertilised natural pastures, and sown biodiverse permanent pastures rich in legumes), trees (e.g., pure or mixed stands of cork oak, holm oak, stone pine), and animals (e.g., sheep, pigs, cows). Montado/Dehesa is one of the most prominent and best-preserved low-intensity farming systems in Europe.

In Portugal, we are analysing three Montado farms (Azinhal, Grous and Padres) and three Dehesa farms (Montehermoso, Montemoheda and Dehesilla Alta) in Spain (Figure 18). The selection of these farms was based on their representativeness of this HNV system, their accessibility to carry out fieldwork, and the willingness of the landowners to work on the project. In these farms, we applied Earth Observation (EO) tools (Sentinel-1, radar sensor and Sentinel-2, optical sensor, and a drone with LiDAR sensor) to characterize, monitor, report and verify vegetation and soil carbon. Based on spectral vegetation indexes, these farms were automatically segmented (Figure 18), and sampling sites were smartly selected for physical, chemical, and microbiological soil analyses.

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Figure 18. Montado/Dehesa farms in Portugal (Azinhal, Grous and Padres) and Spain (Dehesilla Alta, Montehermoso and Montemoheda) of Case Study 16 (CS16).

2. LMT Modelling

Next to the primary data collection in Case Study 16 (CS16), the impact of scaling up an LMT portfolio consisting of (1) agroforestry, (2) forestry, (3) agriculture, and (4) pastures were analysed. The impact of scaling up those technologies is going to be assessed via a qualitative assessment (see next point) and via the application of simulation models. For this, we currently apply the **DayCent** model to simulate fluxes of carbon and nitrogen between the atmosphere, vegetation, and soil. Also, remote sensing data collection (e.g., from TROPOMI, Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2) was used to study plants' biomass and CO₂ sequestration potential and plants' biomass for specific local interventions for climate change adaptation (Deliverable D4.2). In Portugal, the annual Solar-Induced Chlorophyll Fluorescence (SIF) maps (2018-2021) showed that regions with higher SIF values are correlated with the best conditions for growing and hence with higher photosynthetic carbon uptake, i.e., plants with more photosynthetic activity and consequently with more biomass potential. SIF can potentially be used to define bioindicators for specific regions to help better design specific policies in terms of the species (i.e., plant genetics and their resilience to climate change plant-dependent LMTs) that must be considered for future plantations and climate change adaptation.

3. Qualitative risk and co-benefit analysis of LMTs

In a series of semi-structured interviews, we ask stakeholders about the (perceived) risks and (co-) benefits of large-scale implementation of our LMT portfolio. The initial survey results show that heavy rainfalls (unpredictability and/or strong), temperature extremes (heat/cold waves) and drought appear to be identified as the dominant climatic risk factors that could affect the effectiveness of LMT implementation. However, LMT implementation can benefit through the preservation and implementation of ecosystem services, for example, by maintaining physical, chemical and biological conditions such as carbon sequestration, biodiversity, soil protection and erosion prevention, among others.

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Earth Observation

In Portugal and Spain, we are using vegetation spectral indexes (derived from Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 satellite data) to characterize, monitor, verify and report vegetation and soil carbon of Montado farms through a set of tools that are part of the Carbon Map Tool and Biodiversity Tool that are being developed under the scope of Landmarc (Figure 19 and Figure 20).

Figure 19. Earth Observation tools of Carbon and Biodiversity using Carbon Map Tool and Biodiversity Tool in Montado farms. Vegetation structure, Photosynthetic activity and Leaf water content (water stress): Dark green areas - the highest values vegetation structure and with high plant density, very high vegetation photosynthetic activity, very high-water content in leaves and water; Light green areas - vegetation with high structure (Olive/Almond/Montado trees), high vegetation photosynthetic activity, which correspond to trees and/or high plant density (Olive/Almond/Montado trees), and high water content in leaves (very green vegetation and irrigated areas, e.g., vineyards); Yellow areas - vegetation with medium structure (shrubs), medium vegetation photosynthetic activity (shrubs), and medium water content in leaves (Olive and Montado trees, irrigate areas); Brown areas - Vegetation with low structure (pasture), low vegetation photosynthetic activity (pasture), and low water content in leaves (shrubs); Blue areas – water, water (absence of vegetation), and very low water content in leaves (pasture, bare soil).

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Figure 20. a) Carbon map tool. White: very high vegetation structure, chlorophyll and water leaf content. Red: structure (urban). Green: high chlorophyll. Blue: water. Dark areas: very low structure, chlorophyll, and water leaf content; b) Biodiversity tool (see Figure 2 for colour legend).

On one hand, this data is being used to characterize, in time and space, the structure, the photosynthetic activity, and the water stress of the vegetation. On the other hand, this data is being used to calculate the biodiversity indexes (e.g., Farm landscape fractal index and farm landscape Simpson index) to characterize how spectrally biodiverse is a farm. In the first year, soil samples were collected in areas with high, medium, and low values of spectral vegetation indexes to characterize the carbon and biodiversity of the soil. In the second year (2022), soil samples were collected from areas with high, medium, low and no animal intensity, and from a control area (without animals).

Additionally, carbon emission data from the farms was collected, and the diameter at breast height (dbh) of trees was sampled for the calculation of the forest carbon stocks and farm carbon balance to know if the farms are positive, neutral, or negative, in terms of GHG (Figure 21).

The Carbon Map and Biodiversity Tools were developed specifically within the LANDMARC project to measure and monitor carbon sequestration potential and assess the economic value of biodiversity for GHG monitoring of sustainable land management technologies. With the web app that is being developed by AgroInsider to achieve the scope of the project, it is possible to record the field evidence of forest data collection (e.g., dbh) for biomass calculation (Figure 21a), or to verify a set of variables that can change over time through a picture or recording sounds (e.g., fauna and flora diversity, Figure 21b). This information can then be verified through blockchain technology. In this way, all the farmer and/or forestry producer associations' activities are registered and protected for certification, monitoring, and auditing processes.

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a) Carbon: Evergreen oak dbh evidence

b) Recording biodiversity evidence

c) Biodiversity evidence: *Paeonia broteroi*

Figure 21. Registration of evidence of sustainable farm and forestry activities in Forestry Producers' Associations for certification, monitoring and auditing processes using the Agroinsider SmartAG app: a) Carbon: Evergreen oak dbh evidence; b) Recording biodiversity evidence; c) Biodiversity evidence: *Paeonia broteroi*.

In addition, it is important to develop carbon measurement and monitoring technologies capable of proving that plant biodiversity know-how can be documented, monitored, and verified, and that a piece of land is home to several different species at a given time and, in each place (Figure 22). Biodiversity can be a proxy for resilience, that is, the number and distribution of species in the different plant strata information can be included with accredited data. Without biodiversity, the system's resilience, or its ability to respond to climate-related environmental challenges will be insufficient. If grasslands do not include a multi-species mix of pasture species, grass degradation will be faster, and organic matter regeneration will be slower, leading to reduced livestock feeding. If monospecific forests are not complemented by multi-diverse shrub strata, and are mixed with trees of other species, the likelihood of being devastated by a forest fire will be greater. If farms are not able to provide habitats for biodiversity that can be integrated into agricultural landscapes, territories will become more monotonous and lose human population, accelerating the processes of agricultural land abandonment. Plant biodiversity, in this case, is therefore a safe asset for resilient ecosystems, both for adaptation and mitigation.

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Figure 22. Carbon and Biodiversity *in situ* measurements, remote sensing and *in situ* monitoring for robust carbon storage and biodiversity modelling. Automatic segmentation and selection of case study area for soil sampling. The scatter plot shows the relationship between the result of the analysis of the biome, pH and organic matter of the sampled sites with the vegetation index (vegetation structure, productivity and water stress and biodiversity).

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Modelling

From the list of farms in the CS of Portugal and Spain, we selected the Grous farm (Portugal) and an additional Portuguese farm, the Conqueiros that, in addition to the Montado, contains different types of crops to investigate the impact of scaling the LMT portfolio: **1) forestry, 2) agroforestry, 3) pasture and 4) agriculture**. The impact of scaling up those technologies is going to be assessed via a qualitative assessment (see next point) and via the application of models, whenever data is available, and SIF data, when data are not available.

For the **LMT portfolio**, we currently apply the **DayCent** model to evaluate carbon sequestration and **SIF** data to delineate and define areas with higher and lower potential for carbon sequestration (see D4.2).

DayCent application

DayCent is a Biogeochemical land-use management model that can simulate crop biomass and/or yields, soil carbon and nitrogen dynamics, N₂O emissions, nutrient dynamics and GHG fluxes in different plant or soil systems. The model can simulate long-term ecosystem responses to changes in climate, land use and agricultural management practices in cropland, grassland, forest, and savanna ecosystems.

In Portugal, we explore if we can apply the model to simulate above-and belowground carbon in different systems, such as almond and olive groves, maize, and pasture (Figure 23).

Contact us

c)

Figure 23. Preliminary DayCent modelling results for above- and belowground carbon development when scaling-up crops (almond and olive groves and maize) and grassland in the Conqueiros farm: a) Vegetation structure, chlorophyll and water leaf content. White: very high vegetation structure, chlorophyll and water leaf content. Red: structure (urban). Green: high chlorophyll. Blue: water. Dark areas: very low structure, chlorophyll, and water leaf content; b) Total system carbon by component in ton/ha; c) Biomass C in ton/ha.

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Qualitative Assessment

Climate Risk Assessment

The main objective of an LMTs is to provide a “climate service” by a) keeping carbon stored (emission reductions by moving from the baseline scenario in which carbon would have been emitted to the atmosphere), or b) by absorbing additional carbon from the atmosphere (actual carbon sequestration). To be climate-relevant the net climate impact of an LMT should be **permanent**.

However, **ongoing climate change is one of the key risks** to the LMTs which may limit or prevent the climate service delivered. Well-known risks are the immediate climate risks or hazards, like floods, droughts, and wildfires. For example, peat soil rewetting may prevent oxidation of soil carbon, but with increasing and prolonged droughts periods this climate service may not be delivered.

Next to the climate risks, we also consider the assessment of key risks, co-benefits and trade-offs of LMT scaling up to the national level. **Co-benefits** can be factors such as the diversification of products when implementing agroforestry. In terms of other risks than those directly related to climate change there are e.g., a) **societal risks** such as a lack of social support to implement the technology by threatening societal groups and/or creating inequalities among them, b) **technology/practice risks** such technical challenges when implementing and/or scaling up the technology, c) **environmental risks** posed by LMT implementation impacting the nature/environment including human, flora and fauna ecosystems, and d) **economical risks** such as the decrease in the production of food and fodder and forage to feed the animals with a consequent decrease in economic profits.

Our goal of the qualitative risk and co-benefit assessment is to identify and analyse **together with stakeholders** the key socio-economic and environmental risks, co-benefits and trade-offs associated with scaling up LMT. The collected data will be used to advance the development of LMT country narratives and scenarios which among others serve as input for the applied models.

Contact Us

Effective engagement of key stakeholders in LMTs enables a better understanding of LMT feasibility- its potential and barriers to scaling up as well as the development of more robust data collection assessment work. This a) helps develop better quality (and more feasible) LMT scaling up and implementation scenarios, and b) improves the uptake of research results and findings in policy and practice.

LANDMARC relies on consultations with stakeholders through the country case studies and our regional engagement activities to link stakeholder knowledge to the application of earth observation techniques and climate, economic and land-use models.

We invite interested stakeholders to participate in our engagement activities to exchange our (preliminary) assessment results and to contribute to climate change mitigation by sharing their tacit knowledge with us.

Become now part of our project to contribute to climate change mitigation!

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What we can provide:

By being part of the national stakeholder network, you will be able to connect to a broad network that includes actors from different backgrounds across agriculture, forestry, and other land-use sectors. Moreover, you can get access to additional data, and literature, and disseminate and exchange relevant results, insights and experiences with a broader group of national stakeholders. Furthermore, by being involved in this European-funded H₂O₂O research and innovation project, you will improve your visibility in an international context. More specifically, we can provide:

- Background information about the applied models and earth observation tools
- Preliminary results from earth observation tool application and preliminary model runs
- Advanced country narratives explaining our current view on LMT deployment in the Netherlands.

How can you contribute?

We are currently looking for stakeholders across all sectors (LMT practitioners, landowners, NGOs, researchers, industry, public sector, etc.) to:

- **Conduct interviews** about general risks and specific climate risks, co-benefits and trade-offs to the implementation and deployment of the individual LMTs (1) agroforestry, (2) forestry, (3) pastures, and (4) agriculture based on domestic biomass.
- **Exchange information about Portuguese/Spanish land-use datasets** to augment global data sources used for model initialization, e.g., for the location of pasture/cattle and priority areas for afforestation and agroforestry.
- **Exchange economic data about the LMTs, e.g., Montado/Dehesa cost information** such as pasture and soil conservation costs, holm oak and cork oak tree regeneration costs, conservation of ecosystem services, etc.
- **Discuss technical information about the cost of carbon sequestered and stored in the Montado/Dehesa in the voluntary market.**

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Spain

Agroforestry in dehesas, grassland management, forest planning and management, afforestation in agriculture-degraded areas.

Introduction

What is the realistic potential for agriculture, forestry, and other land-use sectors to reduce emissions from soils, vegetation and livestock and enhance the uptake of CO₂ from the atmosphere? This question will be answered by the LANDMARC research project, which officially started on the 1st of July 2020. Funded by the European Commission, the nineteen LANDMARC consortium partners work during the project period (2020-2024) on:

- Estimating the climate impact of land-based negative emission solutions, for example in agriculture, forestry, and other land-use sectors
- Assessing the potential for regional and global upscaling of negative emission solutions
- Mapping their potential environmental, economic, and social co-benefits and trade-offs

What do we do with Land-based Mitigation Technologies (LMTs) in Spain?

1. LMT Earth Observation

Several plant and soil carbon measurement and monitoring techniques are being tested in two case studies, 3 pilot farms for reforestation of agricultural land (Case Study 13) and three pilot farms with different management practices applied in the dehesa agro-ecosystem (Case Study 16), which is also replicated in Portugal.

Soil measurements of physical, chemical and microbiological parameters, at different depths and taking into account the distance from the plants sampled, or forest inventory work to establish patterns relating biodiversity, forest cover structure and the amount of plant biomass with the carbon stored.

The use of remote sensing to first prepare sampling designs and then improve the scaling of the results obtained in the field, thus facilitating the construction of robust models that provide reliable information on the efficiency of land use at a large scale in terms of storing and sequestering carbon.

In addition, work is being carried out in synergy with other grassland management and forestry projects to analyse the effects of different types of land use management on carbon sequestration and storage potential.

2. LMT Modelling

Next to the primary data collection in Case Study 13 (CS13) and Case Study 16 (CS16), the impact of scaling up an LMT portfolio consisting of (1) agroforestry in dehesas, (2) grassland management, (3) forest planning and management, and (4) afforestation in agriculture degraded areas are analysed. The impact of scaling up those technologies is going to be assessed via a qualitative assessment (see next point) and via the application of simulation models.

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For this, we currently apply **DayCent** to simulate fluxes of carbon and nitrogen between the atmosphere, vegetation, and soil. Also, remote sensing data collection (e.g., from TROPOMI, Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2) was used to study plants' biomass and CO₂ sequestration potential and plant biomes for specific local interventions for climate change adaptation (Deliverable D4.2).

In collaboration with LANDMARC, a thesis based on CS13 developed by ETHZ, with the collaboration of Ambienta, assessed the impacts of afforestation of former cropland in Spain. In the pursuance of mitigating climate change by offsetting greenhouse gas emissions, afforestation is increasingly being proposed as a land-use-based strategy to sequester carbon (C) in the biomass of planted trees and the soil. Indeed, the C stored in the biomass of trees is exposed to environmental disturbances and human exploitation, whereas the organic C stored in the soil, in the absence of land use changes, represents a much more stable and long-term C storage. Despite its relevance, there are still uncertainties regarding the precise effects of afforestation, especially regarding how the soil organic C (SOC) changes with time after afforestation. Integrative studies (combining biomass and soil) within the Mediterranean basin are particularly lacking.

3. Qualitative risk and co-benefit analysis of LMTs

In a series of semi-structured interviews, we ask stakeholders related to (1) agroforestry in dehesas, (2) grassland management, (3) forest planning and management, and (4) afforestation in agriculture-degraded areas about the (perceived) risks and (co-) benefits of large-scale implementation of our LMT portfolio. We obtain information about how the implementation could be affected by a changing climate (e.g., droughts, desertification, higher precipitation, etc.) but also how we can benefit from it aside from its climate benefit (e.g., more biodiversity, employment, etc.).

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Earth Observation

In Spain, work is being carried out with different technologies (Table 1) in the case studies of reforestation of degraded agricultural land (CS 13, figure 1) and dehesas management (CS 16, figure 2).

Figure 24: The Spanish case study. Soil and biomass monitoring for the reforestation programme on degraded agricultural land. (Case Study 13)

Table 1: Carbon measurement and monitoring tools (CMMTs) applied in the Spanish case study 13 and case study 16

<i>Pilot Farm</i>	CS 13 - Reforestation of degraded agricultural land			CS 16 – Dehesas management		
	Mariblanca	Los Riscos	Carboneras	Dehesilla Alta	Montehermoso	Montemoheda
<i>Existing soil maps</i>	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
<i>Soil Carbon Measurement (ETHZ Methodology)</i>	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO
<i>Analysis of soil physical and chemical parameters (agronomic methodology).</i>	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
<i>Soil microbiological analysis (BIOCLEAR Methodology).</i>	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
<i>Traditional forestry sampling plots.</i>	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO
<i>Forestry sampling plots with Field Map technology.</i>	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES

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Pilot Farm	CS 13 - Reforestation of degraded agricultural land			CS 16 – Dehesas management		
	Mariblanca	Los Riscos	Carboneras	Dehesilla Alta	Montehermoso	Montemoheda
<i>Plant biodiversity monitoring in sampling plots.</i>	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
<i>Measurement of plant parameters by remote sensing: Multispectral sensor on fixed-wing drone.</i>	YES	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
<i>Measurement of plant parameters by remote sensing: LIDAR Satellite</i>	YES	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
<i>Measurement of plant parameters by remote sensing: Sentinel 1 satellite - Radar.</i>	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
<i>Measurement of plant parameters by remote sensing: Sentinel 2 satellite - Optical.</i>	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES

Figure 2: Work on monitoring and measuring carbon and biodiversity in dehesa agro-ecosystems (Case Study 16)

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Earth Observation – Reforestation of agricultural land and dehesa management.

The reforestation of the agricultural land program is being evaluated 30 years after its beginning on three pilot farms in Extremadura (Spain). The idea behind LANDMARC's work is that apart from the benefits initially envisaged when the reforestations were started, these lands, once the plantations have been well maintained and are stabilized, not only halt the advance of the desert in the Iberian Peninsula and improve the conditions for adaptation to drought but also contribute to climate change mitigation in two ways. Firstly, through the regeneration of new climactic *Quercus* forests where previously there was only degraded land, and secondly, because these forests and their soils have a greater capacity to sequester and store carbon from the atmosphere. Among the benefits of these practices that are being evaluated:

1. ***Increase in spatial diversity and biodiversity.*** Afforestation allows for a more attractive habitat for insects, birds and other animals.
2. ***Increase in soil structure and health.*** Planting trees and shrubs in agricultural degraded areas can protect the otherwise exposed land and its soil from wind stress and strong precipitation. Additionally, the new forests increase root diversity that feeds the living organisms within the soil.
3. ***Carbon sequestration.*** Mediterranean forests increase the absorption of CO₂ permanently from the atmosphere in soil organic matter and thereby store it effectively, which contributes to climate change mitigation.
4. ***Alternative sources of income.*** Mediterranean forests in previously degraded agricultural areas may generate an alternative income source for land users if benefits exceed costs. These benefits may originate from both product revenues and reimbursements for carbon storage.

The idea within LANDMARC is also to team up with agroforestry present in The Netherlands, Vietnam, and Indonesia. At these pilot sites, novel agroforestry technologies are demonstrated to enable the transition from conventional agriculture toward more climate-resilient agroforestry and forestry. Within the approach applied in LANDMARC, we will apply innovative methods to assess changes in vegetation, land use and climatic conditions using different Earth Observation (EO) tools ***including in-situ and remote sensing techniques to monitor the potential and effectiveness of afforestation to reduce GHG emission.***

On the other hand, for the case study of Spanish dehesas, three pilot farms in Spain and three pilot farms in Portugal worked together (Figure 3). The carbon monitoring technologies are applied to different types of management of these farms, and thus obtain results that could be determined depending on the biodiversity, the structure of the forest stands, the grasslands, the presence of shrubs, the soils or the existing livestock on the farms and their type of management.

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Figure 3. Montado/Dehesa farms in Portugal (Azinhal, Grous and Padres) and Spain (Dehesilla Alta, Montehermoso and Montemoheda) of Case Study 16 (CS16).

For the in-situ techniques, soil sampling for **chemical** (soil carbon), and **physical** and **biological** monitoring will be done in the pilot farms. **Smart soil sampling** will be satellite-based using better referenced and new spatial soil data collection to represent the area. The procedure consists in delineating 3 management zones by capturing the variability of soil and agroforestry characteristics based on the big data provided by the Copernicus program (Sentinel 1 and 2) data. **Sentinel 1** is normally used to study *soil texture* to execute soil smart sampling and **Sentinel 2** is used to monitor *chlorophyll and leaf water content*. This strategy will guide to sample in areas that will better represent the variability present in the afforested farms. After this smart sampling, in-situ total organic carbon content together with other soil physical-chemical monitoring across different periods and over time will be measured in the different locations. Furthermore, soil biological monitoring will be done through the identification of soil microorganisms through **DNA-based molecular biology techniques**. Additionally, specific genes related to the C and N cycle will be used to target microbes involved in the emissions of GHG emissions. Therefore, these techniques can be used as a proxy for the detection of soil health and carbon stock quality and flow in the pilot farms.

Another key element is, for example, in the reforestation programme in Spain, to establish a baseline (e.g., degraded agricultural area that has not been reforested) and reference condition (e.g., stable climax Mediterranean forest) control points. These control points allow for the construction of scenarios, (e.g., 0-100 pathways), or well-constructed and reliable stories over large areas of land, and with time frames that can provide trends for decades if the design considers enough ecological factors. Larger scales in space and time can be considered in a well-executed design.

In the case of the Spanish case study (CS13), the baseline and reference conditions (control points) have been selected depending on the state of the forest cover, as this case study assesses the effect of afforestation in degraded agricultural lands. The baseline condition sample was taken in a degraded

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agricultural plot that has not been afforested. The reference condition sample was taken in a climax Mediterranean forest. These control samples were taken in nearby locations, aiming to replicate as much as possible the conditions of the afforested lands before the afforestation program began and to represent a Mediterranean forest in its most pristine condition. Figure 4 shows, when comparing these control points to the samples taken in afforested lands, that the program has been a success in Extremadura from both an adaptation and a mitigation perspective.

Figure 4: Comparison of carbon-related values at different plantation stages in a reforestation programme of agricultural land in Carboneras Farm, Llera (Extremadura, Spain)

In the absence of additional information on vegetation or biodiversity and using only the in situ information from a soil analysis technique and what was observed in the field, we can now begin to verify the carbon stored. Reforestations on degraded Mediterranean land that have been well executed and maintained over time show a halt in erosion and desertification, proving to mitigate the effects of drought and contribute to the sequestration and storage of carbon in the soil.

On the other hand, **to measure the carbon stored in forest biomass in CS13**, forest inventory designs (figures 5, 6, 7 and 8) based on traditional sampling are used, but with the use of more efficient and accurate measurement technologies, supported by Field Map equipment and software for in situ forest monitoring.

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Figure 5: Study area in the Mariblanca farm (Cabeza del Buey) and zoning in various planting years (1998, 2002, 2005 and 2011).

Figure 6: Location of the forest inventory sample plots on the Carboneras farm.

The inventory methodology defined in the Field-Map software is implemented, with a multi-plot and multi-equipment approach, and data collection is carried out in the field in the sampling plots, with a complete team in which several devices work simultaneously connected to a field tablet. Subsequently, the Field-Map software is used to analyse, clean and process the data, until the inventory results are obtained by species, stands and cantons, in the different inventory strata.

The use of various technologies and calculation techniques are integrated, allowing the development of a tool that efficiently and cost-effectively helps to calculate the CO₂ storage potential of forest and agricultural systems.

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Figure 7: General view of the plantation on agricultural land on the Los Riscos estate (Plot R_04).

Figure 8: Forest inventory work on the pilot farms.

In situ biomass monitoring. Data processing and exporting results.

At this stage of the LANDMARC project, a first approximation is made to process the data obtained, and to obtain an estimate of the wood volume (total m³ and m³/ha) in each sampling plot.

In the next phase of the project, with the support of these field data, a criterion will be established in collaboration with other project partners to transform the estimates of wood volume (m³) into tonnes of CO₂ stored in the vegetation.

To determine the wood volume, the equations or models that correlate diameter and height for the species present in the plantations, *Quercus ilex* (main species) and *Quercus suber* (secondary species), were first calculated with the help of the Field-Map CUBICA software.

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The sample of *Quercus ilex* type trees was 85 trees, achieving a correlation coefficient of 0.83, while the number of *Quercus suber* type trees was 19 trees, as this species was less represented in the plantations, with a correlation coefficient of 0.40.

The models obtained for both species are shown below in Figure 9:

Figure 9: Diameter-height models obtained for *Quercus ilex* and *Quercus suber* forest species.

From these equations, the software calculates the missing heights of all the trees measured in the sampling plots of both species.

Earth Observation – Grasslands management and forestry management

LANDMARC collaborates with two Spanish projects working on climate change mitigation technologies. The Ecopraderas Operational Group (figure 10), in which different irrigated grassland pilot farms are being studied, and the ForestechCO2 Project (figure 11), which aims to develop carbon measurement tools in four different types of forest stands (pine forest, oak forest, Mediterranean shrubland and Mediterranean grassland).

For grassland management, the Datagrass tool was developed, based on in situ data collection and remote sensing support, which facilitates field data collection and processing in grasslands so that owners can improve decision-making processes from economic, agronomic and environmental criteria approaches. In this project, the support of the agricultural associations of the Comarca Vegas del Alagón as well as the irrigation community is essential to access the data collection and management plans of the pilot farms.

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Figure 10: Ecopraderas territorial web viewer applied in Vegas del Alagón to the pilot farms La Pulgosa and San Bernardo.

For forest systems, monitoring technologies integrate systems based on in situ forest monitoring and inventory, with remote sensing analysis based on different sensors (LIDAR, multispectral sensor mounted on fixed-wing drone).

Figure 11: In situ monitoring of forest inventory plots and geo-referenced 3D mapping for temporal monitoring model building.

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Modelling

Understanding soil and tree biomass carbon sequestration potential in agricultural degraded reforested areas

The thesis developed by Valeria Renna, ETHZ in collaboration with Ambianta under the LANDMARC framework, assessed the impacts of afforestation of former cropland in Spain. Precisely, this study focused on a private farm located in Extremadura (Case Study 13 – Mariblanca pilot farm), whose area was partly afforested with two native tree species (*Quercus ilex* L. and *Quercus suber* L.), whose ages ranged from 11 to 24 years.

We measured tree height and diameter at the breast height of a total of 337 trees and, via allometric equations, estimated their biomass C stocks. We further collected 186 soil samples (figure 13), using a cylindrical auger, at three different depths (5 cm, 15 cm and 30 cm). We determined the SOC stocks of each of these samples by multiplying their percentage of organic C and their dry mass ≤ 2 mm. The SOC stock of each soil sample was then normalized to a reference soil mass, according to the equal soil mass procedure. Based on the space-for-time approach, we estimated the combined temporal variation of tree biomass C and SOC stocks following afforestation, to understand the magnitude of change of each stock as a function of plantation age.

Figure 12: Schematic overview of C dynamics in terrestrial ecosystems. Own figure adapted from Lorenz & Lal, 2018.

Soil carbon storage is controlled primarily by two processes: photosynthesis (input) and decomposition (output). CO₂ is fixed by plants through photosynthesis and added to the soil through processes such as rhizodeposition and deposition of leaf and root litter. Through these processes, C is made bioavailable to the microbial metabolic “factory” (soil macro- and microfauna), which starts breaking down C inputs. Most of C returns to the atmosphere (mainly via root and heterotrophic respiration). However, some residual C becomes incorporated into the soil and humified, and it eventually ends up in longer-term soil C pools (intermediate or passive carbon pools). Over time, these resistant C pools can become quite large (Figure 12).

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We also studied how the SOC stock was spatially distributed concerning the distance to the trees. The non-afforested agricultural plots, as well as a natural Mediterranean forest (NMF) and an olive grove nearby, served as typical land uses for comparison (figure 14). We found that the oaks' biomass C stock (with an average value of 903.8 g C m⁻²) significantly increased with plantation age. This increase was significantly favoured by low underlying SOC stocks, high elevations, and flat terrains. Given these interactions, the oaks' biomass C accumulation rate ranged from 25.1 to 81.2 g C m⁻² yr⁻¹. All afforested oaks but the youngest (11 years old) showed significantly higher biomass C stocks than the agricultural neighbouring plots.

Hypothetical plot with its three subplots (in pink): A (at the northeast extreme of the plot), B (in the middle) and C (at the southeast extreme of the plot). Subplot B is always in the middle of the plot, subplot A has for example high elevation and low slope, whereas subplot C has low elevation and high slope.

Hypothetical subplot of 400 m² with the locations of the soil sampling.

Figure 13: Schematic illustration of the sampling design. In blue we recognize the plot and in pink we recognize the representative subplots. The different colours of the soil sampling locations (to the right) refer to their position relative to the tree: red = close to the tree (N), blue = in the middle of the inter-rows (M) and black = in between (B). In every subplot, soil was collected in 9 different locations. More specifically, the soil was sampled in N, B and M near every respective tree (in yellow).

The oaks' SOC stock (with an average value of 1313.7 g C m⁻²) was characterized by a trend of decline immediately after afforestation, followed by subsequent gains, suggesting that the afforested plots have only recently started to sequester SOC. The SOC stock change rate of afforested plots ranged from being positive (with a maximum positive value of 10.58 g C m⁻² yr⁻¹) to being negative (with a maximum negative value of -80.43 g C m⁻² yr⁻¹), depending on soil depth and soil texture. SOC accumulation was significantly favoured by low sand and clay content, and it mostly occurred near the soil surface (down to 15 cm) and in proximity (0.5 m) to trees.

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Figure 14: Average cumulative SOC stocks (g C m⁻²) at N distance to the trees for different land uses including different afforestation years. The values are cumulative until 5, 15 and 30 cm of soil depth. Red circles highlight the differences between the plots afforested in 1998 and the cereal control plots. The numbers on the x-axis correspond to the afforestation years of oaks. Vertical bars indicate standard deviations. The same letters indicate the absence of significant differences among afforestation years (Tukey test, $p < 0.05$).

We indeed observed significantly lower SOC stocks between the tree rows, which might be related to the intensive soil management of the farm. The SOC stocks differences related to the tree distance were higher under mature trees compared to young ones. The afforested soils did not show (yet) significantly higher C stocks than the neighbouring plots, which again could be explained by the intensive soil management of the farm. Although our findings indicate that a net C sequestration in the afforested plots of Mariblanca has not occurred yet, the significantly higher total C stocks of the NMF (4280 g C m⁻²) for the agricultural neighbouring plots (1571.9 g C m⁻²) denote a likely C increase at the ecosystem level in the long-term. This future C sequestration becomes even more likely when considering that the oldest afforested plots, with oaks 24 and 20 years old, did not show any significant difference with the total C stock of the NMF.

Our findings regard afforestation as an opportunity to fix organic C in soil and woody tissues to mitigate climate change and highlight the potential to make this opportunity even more substantial by fostering less intensive management of soils, which, in our study, played a similar contribution to total C stock as biomass.

Our results suggest that the afforested soils of Mariblanca are not a net C sink yet, but, given the significantly higher SOC stocks of the natural Mediterranean forest compared to the cereal control plots, they are likely to become it in the future, with a great sequestration potential near the soil surface and near trees.

Overall, for both soil and biomass, we witnessed a high degree of interactions with other covariates (i.e. tree biomass C and SOC stock and their change rate were highly dependent on other variables), which reflects a high site-specificity. This in turn underlines the importance of considering micro-environmental changes when deciding where to plant which trees. So, the tree biomass accumulation rate was positively affected by elevation and negatively by the SOC stock, whereas the tree biomass C stocks across different land uses were negatively influenced by increased slopes and elevations. SOC sequestration was favoured by low sand content, whereas SOC stocks across different land uses were

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negatively influenced by stone content. Both the SOC sequestration rate and stocks showed a negative relationship with clay content, which is against our expectations since mostly proposed to favour soil C stabilization. Our results support the idea of afforesting at high elevations, on land with scant SOC contents, gentle slopes, and low sand and stone content. Regarding clay, it is difficult to conclude, given the substantial discrepancy between our findings and the “status quo”.

At the ecosystem level (i.e. tree biomass C and SOC stocks combined), our findings demonstrate that the afforested plots of Mariblanca have not yet experienced a net C sequestration, which will however likely happen in the next decades, given the significant higher total C stock of the natural Mediterranean forest compared to the cereal control plots and the missing significant difference between the former and 24- and 20-years-old oaks. The probability of future sequestration could be even greater if the soils of Mariblanca were less exposed to disturbance, mainly caused by the tree pruning and soil tillage practices carried out on the farm. Less intensive soil management becomes even more important given the approximately equal contribution of soil and biomass in determining the ecosystem C stock observed in our study, and when considering that C stored in soils is more stable and resistant to sudden changes than that stocked within the tree biomass.

In conclusion, our results show that SOC sequestration was facilitated by the afforested trees, whose positive effect in increasing SOC was however not consistently significant (more prominent near the soil surface and in proximity to the trees) given their young age. Our study results that afforestation practices with native species, such as *Quercus ilex* and *Quercus suber*, hold great potential for C sequestration over the long term in the Mediterranean region. This potential might be further augmented by making a pre-afforestation assessment of the local (a)biotic environmental variables, which in our study were found to highly influence the C stock change rate. Following afforestation, on the other hand, it is important to first keep monitoring C changes, to validate findings and quantify success in offsetting GHG emissions. Second, extensive post-afforestation soil management should be applied, to promote SOC sequestration and avoid the reversibility of C sink into C sources, thus truly a contributor to climate change mitigation.

ALCES application

ALCES simulates changes in landscape composition and related indicators (e.g., wildlife habitat & populations, ecosystem services, & economic performance) in response to land-use scenarios. The model also tracks landscape composition in response to multiple drivers such as land use (forestry, agriculture, etc.), natural disturbance (e.g., fire, insects), and climate. Simulated landscape composition is applied to track indicator response through user-defined equations that can be based on empirical relationships or stakeholder preferences. In Spain, the application of ALCES is being studied for the case studies of reforestation of degraded agricultural land (CS13) and the management of agroecosystems in dehesas (CS16).

DayCent application

DayCent is a Biogeochemical land-use management model that can simulate crop biomass and/or yields, soil carbon and nitrogen dynamics, N₂O emissions, nutrient dynamics and GHG fluxes in different plant or soil systems. The model can simulate long-term ecosystem responses to changes in climate, land use and agricultural management practices in cropland, grassland, forest, and savanna ecosystems.

In Spain, the application of DayCent is being studied for the case studies of reforestation of degraded agricultural land (CS13) and the management of agroecosystems in dehesas (CS16).

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Qualitative Assessment

Climate Risk Assessment

The main objective of an LMTs is to provide a 'climate service' by a) keeping carbon stored (emission reductions by moving from the "baseline" scenario in which carbon would have been emitted to the atmosphere), or b) by absorbing additional carbon from the atmosphere (actual carbon sequestration). To be climate-relevant the net climate impact of an LMT should be **permanent**.

However, **ongoing climate change is one of the key risks** to the LMTs which may limit or prevent the climate service delivered. Well-known risks are the immediate climate risks or hazards, like floods, droughts, and wildfires. For example, successful reforestation without proper management of the plantation over time can become an area of high forest fire risk in two decades due to the accumulated excess forest fuel.

Next to the climate risks, we also consider the assessment of key risks, co-benefits and trade-offs of LMT scaling up to the national level. **Co-benefits** can be factors such as the diversification of products when implementing agroforestry. In terms of other risks than those directly related to climate change there are e.g., a) **societal risks** such as a lack of social support to implement the technology by threatening societal groups and/or creating inequalities among them, b) **technology/practice risks** such technical challenges when implementing and/or scaling up the technology, and c) **environmental risks** posed by LMT implementation impacting the nature/environment including human, flora and fauna ecosystems.

Our goal of the qualitative risk and co-benefit assessment is to identify and analyse **together with stakeholders** the key socio-economic and environmental risks, co-benefits and trade-offs associated with scaling up LMT. The collected data will be used to advance the development of LMT country narratives and scenarios which among others serve as input for the applied models.

The initial findings from the stakeholder interviews about climate-change-related risks and sensitivities are described below.

Climate Change-related risks and sensitivities – initial findings from stakeholder interviews

(Agro-)Forestry in Spanish Dehesas

The main risk factors related to the climate and the management and conservation of the dehesas are drought and temperature variation, i.e. the progressive increase in temperatures, the absence of rainfall and the distribution of the latter. More concentrated and torrential rainfall combined with higher temperatures affects both fauna and flora in the Dehesa as they are not used to it and can lead to alterations in their cycles, such as flowering or acorn production.

In terms of resilience, well-managed dehesas through the implementation of good agricultural practices contribute to better adaptation to climatic conditions, as well as being species adapted to the environment. The resilience or capacity of an agroforestry system to adapt to changing conditions is directly related to the climate and the implementation of good agricultural practices.

Forest planning and management

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The main risk factor related to climate and forest management and development is drought, followed by heatwave events. The effects can be seen for example in the reforestations of 10-15 years ago which were doing well, however, in addition to the effects of natural selection their situation has been aggravated by drought and extreme heat conditions, all of which have led to the death of many established stands. In the north, there are many pines and strawberry trees that have suddenly dried up, which is unusual here given the climatic conditions.

Forest fires are also one of the factors that is having the greatest impact. This year, together with 2003, we have suffered major fires, which in addition to the occasional loss of all the biodiversity of the area, we must take into account the erosion and loss of soil produced, which affects the resilience of the area, which, although we are used to the frequent occurrence of fires, this resilience or capacity for regeneration is diminishing.

Erosion has been reversed in some areas by forest management, but due to the occurrence of fires, droughts and heat waves, this situation has worsened, contributing to the loss of regeneration capacity and soil fertility.

Afforestation in agricultural degraded areas

The main effect of reforestations and their associated pastures on the local environment is primarily related to carbon sequestration, reforestations play an important role as carbon sinks. It can be seen how in soils that were previously bare with poor pasture quality, where, after the reforestation was implemented, the maintenance work carried out between subsequent lanes and the absence of grazing in the first 10 years or so, has led to an improvement in the pasture, soil quality and water balance.

The main risk factor related to climate, forestations and their viability is drought. Most reforestations are of indigenous species, *Quercus* sp., which are adapted to the terrain. However, the increasingly frequent and prolonged drought conditions and heat waves in recent years have led to the appearance of a large number of dry stands. At present, the climatic conditions are not conducive to the good development or optimal establishment of reforestations and densifications, because the soil is not in a suitable condition for this due to the drought.

Forest fires affect reforestation directly, so in the first few years, until the plants are well developed, the scrub and grasses that appear between the lanes and create a permanent cover must be removed, thereby reducing the possibility of forest fires. As well as this maintenance work, the root system must not be affected, as this could damage it considerably.

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Grasslands management

The main risk factor related to climate and pasture management in Spain is drought, both lack of water and inadequate rainfall distribution. Linked to drought are the increasingly frequent and longer heat waves in the summer season. Of course, the pastures are affected by continuous frosts and strong winds, the latter of which, when they occur, reduce the intensity of the rainfall.

The main effect of grassland on the local environment is those related to soil, water and air so a well-managed grassland cover contributes to a higher retention of nutrients in the soil and therefore to an improvement of soil quality and better regulation of the water balance.

In terms of biodiversity, a land with a good grassland vegetation cover, the more balanced it is, the more it affects the scenic landscape value, due to the high biodiversity in terms of plant and bird species, although the contribution of grassland to these factors will depend on the stocking rate of livestock using the land. Grasslands have an important role as carbon sinks as well as buffers for the overall system.

Agriculture best practices and management

Among the progress achieved, in synergies with other projects in Spain, Fact Sheets have been produced, as a result of the collaborations with the Ecopraderas Operational Group for grassland management (figure 15) and the Cereal Water Operational Group for agriculture management (figure 16), which connect the mitigation technologies based on land use developed in LANDMARC, and by both Operational Groups, with agricultural activities in cereal crops and irrigated grasslands. These documents are very useful for disseminating knowledge among stakeholders and farmers in general, which in terms of mitigation and carbon sequestration can generate interesting and productive contributions in agricultural areas of Spain.

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Land Mitigation Technologies - Grupo Operativo Ecopraderas & LANDMARC

SOWING AND ESTABLISHMENT OF IRRIGATED GRASSLANDS

- A) Define type of use (grazing, mowing, mixed).
- B) Preliminary soil analysis to design an amendment and fertilisation programme.
- C) Design of a biodiverse seed mixture, preferably with grasses and legumes, adapted to the soil characteristics and type of use.
- D) Sowing rate: 25-35 kg/ha. Inoculation of legume seeds is compulsory.
- E) Correct preparation of the soil and sowing by appropriate means.
- F) Seed sowing depth: 0.5 - 1 cm. Post-sowing rollers are recommended.
- G) Infrastructure planning (fencing, water points, etc).
- H) Frequent low-flow irrigation, preferably by sprinkling, is recommended at emergence.

SUSTAINABLE MANAGEMENT, MAINTENANCE AND IRRIGATION OF GRASSLANDS

- A) Delay the first use after establishment, with the species at a sufficient stage of development.
- B) First use after establishment, preferably by mowing, to control non-introduced species and improve the botanical composition.
- C) Design grazing plan, applying rotational grazing with short harvesting periods.
- D) The use of electric grazers is recommended to reduce the area of the enclosures.
- E) Avoid any type of grazing with waterlogged ground.
- F) Provide sequestration fencing to accommodate livestock when the pasture is at rest.
- G) After harvesting, ensure that the grassland species are rested, which allows their structures to regenerate and maintain a high level of production.
- H) Installation of drinking troughs to ensure that livestock have access to quality water in the enclosures, avoiding the use of ponds supplied by run-off water.
- I) Soil analysis every 3 years to monitor its evolution and adapt the fertilisation programme.
- J) Maintenance fertilisation adapted to the species present in the meadow.
- K) Training and transfer to irrigators: technology and tools such as probes to measure soil moisture, flow meters to control water volume, or monitoring with aerial or satellite images.
- L) In sprinkler irrigation, with pivots and levelled plots, it is easier to use the technology.
- M) In gravity irrigated meadows with an irregular surface, management is more complex and water optimisation is more difficult, and it is important to zone to direct irrigation and to decide on irrigation doses and times.
- N) Make water available to the crop at the right time, avoiding "calendar" irrigation or irrigation at unknown doses, without taking into account the particular needs of the crop.

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Soil health, the basis for productivity, profitability and sustainability

Investment in soil knowledge is necessary for sustainable and profitable agriculture.

A) For good decision making in agriculture, soil properties must be known. The texture, structure and organic matter content of a soil is fundamental to understand its behaviour in relation to water circulation within it, and thus its storage capacity, erosion risk and contamination power.

B) The productivity, sustainability, resilience, recovery and regeneration capacity of grassland is strongly related to soil health. A healthy soil equals a productive grassland.

C) To reduce the pollution that causes eutrophication and loss of biodiversity, it is recommended to adjust the stocking rate to the forage production of the grassland, and thus reduce the surplus of accumulated nutrients in the soil (mainly nitrogen and phosphorus).

D) The less tillage, the more carbon the soil absorbs and stores. Planting and/or reseeding grasslands using the best tool provided by **conservation agriculture**.

E) Conservation agriculture. Direct sowing, which is a very important agronomic practice, as this technique sequesters and increases the carbon in the soil and reduces greenhouse gas emissions to a greater extent than traditional tillage, which is a great tool **for mitigating climate change**.

Well-managed grasslands strengthen biodiversity and the existence of genetic resources in the environment. They contribute to improved soil structure, increased organic matter content, improved infiltration, increased water retention capacity and reduced runoff, improving surface water quality.

Responsible fertilisation of irrigated grassland.

A) Annual or biannual soil sampling and analysis.

B) Determination of the optimum fertilisation rate based on soil analysis, crop requirements and expected yield.

C) Choice of fertilisers and amendments on the basis of the data obtained in the soil analysis, the time of application of fertilisers (bottom or seeding and/or top dressing) and the price per fertiliser unit.

D) Application of fertilisers and amendments at the recommended doses when rainfall or irrigation is expected, in order to incorporate them into the soil and make them available to the plants. This should be done under the best conditions: good soil temperature, avoid windy days, homogeneous distribution and with appropriate machinery.

E) In irrigated meadows, bottom fertilisation should be carried out in autumn or at the end of winter with nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium, and top dressing in spring, after the first use (tillage or mowing), based on nitrogen, bearing in mind that nitrogen favours grasses.

F) In acid soils, avoid fertilisers with a high N content and use lime-based fertilisers.

G) Mixed grass and legume meadows reduce fertilisation and improve soil structure.

More information.

- Grupo Operativo Ecopraderas. <https://ambientaing.es/index.php/l-d-i/grupo-operativo-ecopraderas>
- Focus Group Profitability of permanent grassland. <https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/focus-groups/profitability-permanent-grassland>
- Focus Group Grazing for Carbon. <https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/focus-groups/grazing-carbon>
- LANDMARC Project. <https://www.landmarc2020.eu/>

Figure 15: Knowledge transfer on carbon storage and land use between the Ecopraderas Operational Group and LANDMARC. Grassland management and mitigation.

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Grupo Operativo Cereal Agua & LANDMARC - Land Mitigation Technologies

CEREAL CULTIVATION IN MEDITERRANEAN EUROPE FACING THE CLIMATE CHALLENGE

In general, agriculture plays a dual role in the face of climate change. On the one hand, it suffers from disturbances caused by extreme weather events that affect crop production, and on the other hand, it sometimes acts as a source of greenhouse gases.

PROBLEMS.

- A) Crop damage and/or losses due to reduced water availability.
- B) Significant economic losses resulting from reduced agricultural production due to weather events such as heat waves, periods of drought, frost or floods.
- C) Losses and/or damage to crops and harvests due to an increase in more frequent and violent torrential rains.
- D) Increased variability of agricultural production and reduced stability of the sector due to fluctuating weather conditions.
- E) Changes in the behaviour of pests and diseases. Their natural control by frost and low winter temperatures may decrease. Also changes in temperatures may cause other diseases to move to higher latitudes.
- F) Soil erosion and degradation due to increased heavy rainfall events.
- G) Increased vulnerability of soils and irrigation systems to salinisation.
- H) Shortening of crop growing cycles and changes in the timing of the different phases of these cycles (germination, ripening, flowering, etc.).
- I) Acceptable levels of agricultural insurance take-up.

ALTERNATIVES.

- A) Sustainable and efficient use of water, energy and soil resources, seeking savings and efficiency in their use, as well as the use of renewable energies as alternative sources.
- B) The use of good agricultural practices towards a conservation agriculture that allows maintaining soil fertility and the incorporation of landscape elements of high diversity such as multifunctional margins, living hedges, vegetation islands, walls, terraces, ponds, etc.

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Climate change adaptation and mitigation in cereal crops

Climate, adaptation to its changes, and the potential for mitigating its effects from agriculture, is a cross-cutting challenge that must be addressed from different perspectives that work synergistically. With the final objective of knowledge transfer between the scientific community, agricultural companies, agronomic engineering and farmers, agricultural associations are involved, and through their own experiences in the network of pilot farms, the Cereal Water Operational Group and LANDMARC project tests different techniques and farm management. The results are analysed in the actions underway, which focus on soil, water, energy resources and ecosystem services. A manual of good practices is drawn up to provide tools for viable and profitable adaptation and mitigation to climate change in cereal cultivation, in accordance with current social and economic needs.

A challenge integrating soil, biodiversity, energy, technology and economics

Soil conservation actions.

- Reduced tillage: soil disturbance is minimised and less carbon is released into the atmosphere, thus reducing the accumulation of GHGs (Greenhouse Gases).
- Cover cropping: protects the soil between cropping seasons, provides organic matter and increases the biological activity of the soil, which favours its regeneration.

Energy saving actions.

- Photovoltaic panel system for energy generation. Assessment of the energy savings produced through the use of solar energy.
- Self-guiding system in agricultural machinery: reduces consumption of fertilisers and diesel.
- Hydropropelled irrigation pumping without greenhouse gas emissions. As an innovation, the installation and monitoring of physical and commercial hydropropelled irrigation pumping system without greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions is proposed.

Valuation of ecosystem services.

- Landscape elements in agricultural environments are part of the green infrastructure. They provide ecosystem services that buffer and mitigate the effects of climate change, such as conservation and ecological connectivity between ecosystems, CO₂ sequestration capacity, combating desertification or increasing biodiversity.
- The valuation and monetisation of these ecosystem services is not an easy challenge. Monitoring and modeling to estimate the economic value of carbon sequestration and ecological connectivity of cereal agroecosystems, using tools implemented in software, Geographic Information Systems and new applications.

More information.

- Grupo Operativo Cereal Agua. <https://cerealagua.es/>
- Focus Group Agua y Agricultura. <https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/publications/eip-agri-focus-group-water-and-agriculture-final>
- LANDMARC Project. <https://www.landmarc2020.eu/>

Figure 16: Knowledge transfer on carbon storage and land use between the Cereal Water Operational Group and LANDMARC. Cereal crop management and mitigation.

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Contact Us

Effective engagement of key stakeholders in LMTs enables a better understanding of LMT feasibility- its potential and barriers to scaling up as well as the development of more robust data collection assessment work. This a) helps develop better quality (and more feasible) LMT scaling up and implementation scenarios, and b) improves the uptake of research results and findings in policy and practice.

LANDMARC relies on consultations with stakeholders through the country case studies and our regional engagement activities to link stakeholder knowledge to the application of earth observation techniques and climate, economic and land-use models.

We invite interested stakeholders to participate in our engagement activities to exchange our (preliminary) assessment results and to contribute to climate change mitigation by sharing their tacit knowledge with us.

Become now part of our project to contribute to climate change mitigation!

What we can provide:

By being part of the national stakeholder network, you will be able to connect to a broad network that includes actors from different backgrounds across agriculture, forestry, and other land-use sectors. Moreover, you can get access to additional data, and literature, and disseminate and exchange relevant results, insights and experiences with a broader group of national stakeholders. Furthermore, by being involved in this European-funded H2020 research and innovation project, you will improve your visibility in an international context. More specifically, we can provide:

- Background information about the applied models and earth observation tools
- Preliminary results from earth observation tool application and preliminary model runs
- Advanced country narratives explaining our current view on LMT deployment in the Netherlands.

How can you contribute?

We are currently looking for stakeholders across all sectors (LMT practitioners, landowners, NGOs, researchers, industry, public sector, etc.) to:

- **Conduct interviews** about general risks and specific climate risks, co-benefits and trade-offs to the implementation and deployment of the individual LMTs (1) agroforestry in dehesas, (2) grassland management, (3) forest planning, and (4) afforestation in agriculture degraded areas.
- **Exchange information about Spanish land-use datasets** to augment global data sources used for model initialization. e.g., for forestry planning, priority areas for afforestation, or grassland and biomass management in dehesas.
- **Exchange economic data about the LMTs, e.g.**, forest management and costs of implementing fire prevention measures, economic costs of sowing and grassland management etc.
- **Discuss technical information about** the monetisation of implementation of mitigation measures based on carbon sequestration and storage by farm or forest owners interested in taking action on their farms.

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Sweden

Biochar, Bioenergy with Carbon Capture and Storage (BECCS), forestry

Introduction

What is the realistic potential for agriculture, forestry, and other land-use sectors to reduce emissions from soils, vegetation and livestock and enhance the uptake of CO₂ from the atmosphere? This question will be answered by the LANDMARC research project, which officially started on the 1st of July 2020. Funded by the European Commission, the nineteen LANDMARC consortium partners work during the project period (2020-2024) on:

- Estimating the climate impact of land-based negative emission solutions, for example in agriculture, forestry, and other land-use sectors
- Assessing the potential for regional and global upscaling of negative emission solutions
- Mapping their potential environmental, economic, and social co-benefits and trade-offs

What do we do with Land-based Mitigation Technologies (LMTs) in the Swedish case study?

1. LMT Modelling

Next to the primary data collection in our case studies, we investigate the impact of scaling up an LMT portfolio consisting of (1) biochar, (2) BECCS, and its interactions with the forestry sector and biomass. The impact of scaling up those technologies is going to be assessed via a qualitative assessment (see next point) and via the application of simulation models. For this, we currently apply:

- a) **E3ME** to assess the impact on the economy (GDP, employment), land-use change, and national emissions, and
- b) **Techno-economic analysis** of the combination of biochar and BECCS

2. Qualitative risk and co-benefit analysis of LMTs

In a series of semi-structured interviews, we ask stakeholders about the (perceived) risks and (co-) benefits of large-scale implementation of our LMT portfolio, knowledge gaps and the potential they see with the implementation of LMTs in the country. We obtain information about how the implementation could be affected by a changing climate (e.g., more droughts, higher precipitation, etc.) but also how we can benefit from it aside from its climate benefit (e.g., more biodiversity, employment, etc.). We discuss what kind of applications would have the most potential to decrease emissions while being a cost-competitive alternative and we gather information on regulatory and market gaps that need to be addressed.

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Modelling

Next to the primary data collection in our case studies, we investigate the impact of scaling up an LMT portfolio consisting of **biochar, and BECCS**, and their synergies to the **forestry** sector.

E3ME preliminary model results

E3ME is a macro-econometric model designed to assess global policy challenges. It is the most advanced econometric model in the world and is widely used for policy assessment, forecasting and research purposes. The model is owned and maintained by Cambridge Econometrics.

The scenario modelling inputs are summarised in Table 5 below. In general terms, the scenario design was formulated such that:

- Scenario impacts begin in 2026
- CO₂ removals assumptions are based on targets set for 2045, the year of Sweden's national net zero emissions target.
- It is assumed a linear rollout of CO₂ removal capacity year-on-year.

Table 5. Scenario inputs

Variable	BECCS	Biochar	Comment
CO₂ removal¹¹	10.7 MtCO ₂ by 2045	1.8 MtCO ₂ by 2045	BECCS CO ₂ removals are assumed to be split across combined heat and power (CHP) plants and paper/pulp sectors, according to the relative shares of biofuel use by these sectors in the E3ME baseline. ¹²
CAPEX¹³	540 SEK/tCO ₂ = 52 €/tCO ₂ ¹⁴	318.9 €/tCO ₂	Paid for through new loans/ financing, doesn't affect industry unit costs or prices. The total annual investment is proportional to capacity additions, rather than levels. ¹⁵
OPEX (incl. transport)	560 SEK/tCO ₂ = 53 €/tCO ₂	31.89 €/tCO ₂	Includes CO ₂ transport & storage costs for BECCS. Increases unit costs and output prices for the industry.
CO₂ price	2025: 24 €/tCO ₂ 2045: 42 €/tCO ₂		CO ₂ removals incur carbon credits, which reduce OPEX costs and reduce government revenues. We assume a neutral fiscal impact, so government must raise other taxes (income tax, VAT) to balance the budget. CO ₂ prices are assumed to follow PRIMES projections of the EU ETS price.

¹¹ These CO₂ removal assumptions represent a high-end estimate of the potential of these technologies in Sweden by 2045.

¹² E3ME baseline data on biofuel consumption by sector is based on IEA energy balances in the historical period, and is projected forward in the baseline forecast using projections from the PRIMES model.

¹³ Investment costs are assumed to be fixed (in real terms) throughout the scenario period.

¹⁴ All financial values in this section are assumed to be in constant 2022 prices, unless otherwise stated.

¹⁵ That is, if CO₂ removals increase linearly by 1 MtCO₂ each year, and CAPEX costs are €1/tCO₂, then annual investment will remain static at €1m in every year. Since investment takes place throughout the scenario period (rather than being concentrated in year 1), no discount rate is applied to investment costs.

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Results

Environmental impacts

- The emissions impacts are dominated by the assumed 12.5 MtCO₂ of removals from the rollout of BECCS infrastructure and biochar application. This represents around 25% of total greenhouse gas emissions in Sweden in 2019 (in CO₂-equivalent terms, excluding LULUCF).¹⁶
- The small economic impacts mean that there are **negligible second-order impacts on CO₂ emissions**, as shown by the (almost invisible) “Other” category in Figure 25. This suggests that there would be no rebound effects from the assumed CO₂ removals, nor would there be any synergies in terms of further reductions in emissions from other sectors.

Figure 25: CO₂ emissions, LMT scenario, absolute differences from baseline, MtCO₂e

Economic impacts

- The **macroeconomic impact of these LMTs would be small** in the context of the Swedish economy, with an absolute GDP impact smaller than 0.05% relative to the baseline, as shown in Figure 26.
- This suggests that the **substantial environmental benefits** from increased BECCS and biochar removals would come at a **relatively small cost** to the Swedish economy (at worst), and could even bring a small economic benefit (under certain assumptions – see rest of this section).
- The macroeconomic **impact would be positive in the short run, and negative in long run** – assuming that tax credits are provided for carbon removals, and governments adjust other taxes to maintain fiscal neutrality (**With revenue recycling**). If this assumption is removed (**No revenue recycling**), then there would be a **small positive GDP impact** throughout the scenario period.¹⁷

¹⁶ According to Sweden's 2021 [National Inventory Report](#) (p23) submitted to the UNFCCC, Sweden emitted 50.9 MtCO₂e of GHG emissions in 2019.

¹⁷ The concept of “revenue recycling” refers to the idea that additional government revenues from carbon taxes are recycled into the economy, through either spending increases or reductions in other tax rates. Without these counterbalancing measures, the net effect of a higher carbon tax would be a fiscal contraction. In our “With revenue recycling” scenario, carbon revenues are *reduced* (in line with lower CO₂ emissions), so revenue recycling implies that other tax rates must be *raised* to maintain a balanced budget (in our scenario, we achieve this through increases in income tax, VAT and employers' social security rates). In the “No revenue recycling” scenario, the government does not raise these taxes, and so is effectively pursuing an expansionary fiscal policy, i.e. an unfunded subsidy to industry via carbon credits.

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Figure 26: GDP and components, LMT scenario, differences from baseline, 2020 €m and %

- In both scenarios, the **initial positive GDP impact is driven by investment** in CCS and biochar capacity. This investment boost persists throughout the scenario period due to the linear rollout of capacity.
- However, in the “**With revenue recycling**” scenario the investment impact is soon outweighed by the **negative impact on consumer expenditure**. This drop in spending is driven by falling disposable incomes, which are attributable to **increasing income tax rates**, as the government attempts to replace lost carbon tax revenues with increased revenues elsewhere.
- At the same time, in both scenarios, **carbon credits push down industry costs, and thus industrial prices**, and therefore tend to increase the real value of consumers’ disposable income.
- However, in the “**With revenue recycling**” scenario this is outweighed by **rising VAT and social security rates**, which are driven by the same dynamics as the raise in income tax rates mentioned above. The net effect is an **increase in consumer prices**, which reduces the real value of disposable incomes even further.
- On the whole, in the “**With revenue recycling**” scenario lower disposable incomes and higher consumer prices drive a relatively strong reduction in consumer spending. This impact becomes stronger throughout the scenario period, as carbon prices rise and CO₂ removals increase in quantity.
- If we remove the assumption of fiscal neutrality (and therefore the increase in income, VAT and social security rates), as in the “**No revenue recycling**” scenario, then **falling industrial prices (from carbon credits) increase the real value of consumer income**.¹⁸ Consumer spending would see a small corresponding boost, and the overall macroeconomic impact would be marginally positive.
- The trend in other GDP components mostly represents the import share of consumption. Higher consumer demand is met in part by **imports**, and these purchases are subtracted from GDP (as they represent domestic demand rather than domestic *product*). Hence the results broadly show that “**other GDP components**” **fall as consumption rises, and vice versa**.

¹⁸ As prices increase (i.e. with higher inflation), the “real” value (i.e. purchasing power) of consumer incomes is correspondingly diminished, even if the “nominal” value remains unchanged. By the same token, falling prices tend to increase the real value of income.

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Techno-economic analysis results

Furthermore, in a case study focusing on the feasibility of BECCS and biochar in the electricity and heating sector, we estimated economic performance for different deployment scenarios (unfavourable – average– favourable) (see Figure 27). Heat sales are the main source of income for both LMTs, but in the favourable BECCS scenario, carbon sales become almost equally important. For biochar systems, the sales of biochar are more important than carbon sales to their economic performance. While Figure 27 suggests that both technologies are viable even under average conditions, it is also slightly misleading to analyse on its own. In reality, most BECCS and biochar systems will replace an already existing CHP plant which means that the system needs to perform on a similar level or better economically after the NET investment for it to be a viable investment for the project owner. The net NPV is positive for both technologies in the average and favourable scenarios (Figure 27), which would suggest that BECCS and biochar systems under the conditions set in these two scenarios can be profitable. However, looking at the NPV relative to the reference system makes the profitability less obvious (Figure 28).

Figure 27. NPV of BECCS and biochar systems. Each income and expense are expressed per MWh of input energy to the systems.

Replacing a CHP plant with a pyrolysis plant or retrofitting it with a CCS system, results in a net loss in both the unfavourable and the average scenarios (Figure 28). The effect of the energy penalty can be noted in the negative heat and electricity sales since they show that the energy sales are lower in the NET systems compared to the reference ones. We do see that if the biochar price and the CO_2 price are high enough, BECCS and biochar become profitable. Profitability is only reached in the “Favourable” cases which reflects the picture painted in the literature study as well as in the stakeholder interviews, where the need for more robust economic incentives for these technologies is highlighted as the most important factor in making NETs attractive.

Figure 28. NPV of BECCS and biochar systems relative to the reference case of maintaining a CHP plant with the same feedstock volume. Each income and expense are expressed per MWh of input energy to the systems.

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Qualitative Assessment

Climate Risk Assessment

The main objective of an LMTs is to provide a 'climate service' by a) keeping carbon stored (emission reductions by moving from the "baseline" scenario in which carbon would have been emitted to the atmosphere), or b) by absorbing additional carbon from the atmosphere (actual carbon sequestration). To be climate-relevant the net climate impact of an LMT should be **permanent**.

However, **ongoing climate change is one of the key risks** to the LMTs which may limit or prevent the climate service delivered. Well-known risks are the immediate climate risks or hazards, like floods, droughts, and wildfires. For example, peat soil rewetting may prevent oxidation of soil carbon, but with increasing and prolonged droughts periods this climate service may not be delivered.

Next to the climate risks, we also consider the assessment of key risks, co-benefits and trade-offs of LMT scaling up to the national level. **Co-benefits** can be factors such as the diversification of products when implementing agroforestry. In terms of other risks than those directly related to climate change there are e.g., a) **societal risks** such as a lack of social support to implement the technology by threatening societal groups and/or creating inequalities among them, b) **technology/practice risks** such technical challenges when implementing and/or scaling up the technology, and c) **environmental risks** posed by LMT implementation impacting the nature/environment including human, flora and fauna ecosystems.

Our goal of the qualitative risk and co-benefit assessment is to identify and analyse **together with stakeholders** the key socio-economic and environmental risks, co-benefits and trade-offs associated with scaling up LMT. The collected data will be used to advance the development of LMT country narratives and scenarios which among others serve as input for the applied models.

What have stakeholders said so far?

Risks to LMTs from climate change are not talked about extensively among stakeholders, but it is an important topic. These risks may cause a big uncertainty, but as long as an offset claim has not been made on the affected land, the problems of that uncertainty can be minimized. There is indeed an increased risk of disturbances from a changing climate, e.g. from pests (in Sweden the spruce bark beetle), storms, wildfires, drought etc. which means that storing carbon in forests is an uncertain climate mitigation strategy associated with risk. What happens if a forest owner gets paid to store carbon in the forest and then the carbon is lost due to e.g. a storm or fire? There is always a risk that forest owners will suffer from such disturbances.

There needs to be a larger awareness of the importance of biological systems to enable a fossil-free future. This includes aspects related to energy and material but is broader than that and includes poverty alleviation, food provision and a broad set of factors related to sustainable development in general. A key general advantage of managed forests, compared to unmanaged, is a decrease in risks of fire and other damages and that it allows for more adaptation opportunities, i.e., in response to changing climate conditions.

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Biochar

Biochar has a dual role in the land use sectors in that agriculture and forestry can be both sources of feedstock for biochar production, but also that biochar can be added to lands to sequester carbon and improve growing conditions. However, agriculture and forestry play somewhat different roles here. In forestry, biochar is unlikely to come with many co-benefits (e.g., improved yields) in that there is no carbon deficiency in forest lands. Biochar from forestry by-products & residues can however be valuable in agriculture. Biochar can have some potential as a means to improve yields in agriculture, although not so much in Sweden.

BECCS

As for bio-CCS, this has substantial potential in Sweden, not least in the pulp & paper industry and district heating plants. It is technologically quite feasible, but the business case is more challenging. The bio-CCU business case looks more promising though. In other parts of Europe, the pulp & paper industry is more dependent on natural gas for process energy which naturally limits the opportunities for bio-CCS. BECCS is a measure that becomes necessary because it is assumed that it will not be possible to reduce emissions at the pace required to meet global climate goals. BECCS is promising but also expensive and will probably only be a small piece of the overall mitigation puzzle. It is however important to begin the deployment of full-scale supply chains for BECCS to get an accurate idea of what the costs are in practice. If viable and with policy incentives in place, BECCS can enable new revenue streams for both energy companies and forest industries.

Knowledge gaps

A problematic issue is found in the carbon accounting frameworks, where the land use sector (LULUCF) has been separated as an accounting category in itself. This is what at its core has led to the concept of "net-zero" where residual fossil emissions are expected to be compensated for by the land use sector. A telling example is that the CO₂ uptake in land biomass (forest growth) is often seen as a natural process whereas removals (harvest) are seen as an anthropogenic process, in reality, the carbon uptake is an anthropogenic process as well because it depends on forest management.

In terms of capacity gaps, the scientific understanding of carbon cycles is fairly well established, but there are greater uncertainties as to what the actual carbon flows are, as current reporting and accounting are primarily based on models rather than direct measurements. Similarly, when it comes to making the most of land-based biological systems for climate change mitigation, factors related to technology and biology are well-understood and the key remaining challenges are primarily related to markets and policy. However, markets for carbon credits are counterproductive as they primarily incentivize sequestration in standing biomass. While it is important to ensure that landowners are rewarded for their climate change mitigation services, this is better done via a premium added to the retail price of wood products and then transferred upstream to the landowner.

The main uncertainty for the upscaling of biochar and BECCS is the economical and policy aspects, especially for BECCS because of the large amount of capital that's needed. The question of how to make these technologies economically viable remains unanswered.

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We invite interested stakeholders to participate in our engagement activities to exchange our (preliminary) assessment results and to contribute to climate change mitigation by sharing their tacit knowledge with us.

What we can provide:

By being part of the national stakeholder network, you will be able to connect to a broad network that includes actors from different backgrounds across agriculture, forestry, and other land-use sectors. Moreover, you can get access to additional data, and literature, and disseminate and exchange relevant results, insights and experiences with a broader group of national stakeholders. Furthermore, by being involved in this European-funded H2020 research and innovation project, you will improve your visibility in an international context. More specifically, we can provide:

- Background information about the applied models and earth observation tools
- Preliminary results from earth observation tool application and preliminary model runs
- Advanced country narratives explaining our current view on LMT deployment

How can you contribute?

We are currently looking for stakeholders across all sectors (LMT practitioners, landowners, NGOs, researchers, industry, public sector, etc.) to:

- **Discuss with LANDMARC researchers** about general risks and specific climate risks, co-benefits and trade-offs to the implementation and deployment of the individual LMTs (1) biochar, and (2) BECCS.
- **Exchange information about Swedish land-use datasets** to augment global data sources used for model initialization. e.g., for biomass availability and biochar production capacity.
- **Provide economic data about the LMTs, e.g., BECCS cost information** such as component costs of biochar, carbon storage and transport costs for BECCS, carbon market pricing etc.
- **Participate in regional dialogues** discussing upscaling of LMTs from Sweden to Northern Europe.

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Switzerland

Organic agriculture, Reduced tillage, Agroforestry, Biochar

Introduction

What is the realistic potential for organic agriculture, reduced tillage, agroforestry, and other land-use sectors to reduce emissions from soils, vegetation and livestock and enhance the uptake of CO₂ from the atmosphere? This question will be answered by the LANDMARC research project, which officially started on the 1st of July 2020. Funded by the European Commission, the nineteen LANDMARC consortium partners work during the project period (2020-2024) on:

- Estimating the climate impact of land-based negative emission solutions, for example in agriculture, forestry, and other land-use sectors
- Assessing the potential for regional and global upscaling of negative emission solutions
- Mapping their potential environmental, economic, and social co-benefits and trade-offs

What do we do with Land-based Mitigation Technologies (LMTs) in CH?

1. LMT Modelling

Next to the primary data collection in our case studies, we investigate the impact of scaling up an LMT portfolio consisting of (1) organic agriculture and (2) reduced tillage and potentially also (3) agroforestry and (4) biochar application. The impact of scaling up those technologies is going to be assessed via a qualitative assessment (see next point) and via the application of simulation models. For this, we will apply four different models:

- a) **E3ME** to assess the impact on the economy (GDP, employment), land-use change, and national emissions.
- b) **ALCES** to visualize the impact of LMTs on land-use change and carbon sequestration.
- c) **LANDSHIFT** to assess potential changes in landscape composition in a demand-driven fashion.
- d) **DayCent** to assess the impact on yields, long-term soil fertility and greenhouse gas emissions at both the local and national scale.

2. Qualitative risk and co-benefit analysis of LMTs

In a series of semi-structured interviews, we ask stakeholders about the (perceived) risks and (co-) benefits of large-scale implementation of our LMT portfolio. We obtain information about how the implementation could be affected by a changing climate (e.g., more droughts, higher precipitation, etc.) but also how we can benefit from it aside from its climate benefit (e.g., more biodiversity, employment, etc.).

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Modelling

Next to the primary data collection in our case studies, we investigate the impact of scaling up an LMT portfolio consisting of **(1) organic agriculture and (2) reduced tillage and potentially also (3) agroforestry and (4) biochar application**. The impact of scaling up those technologies is going to be assessed via a qualitative assessment (see next point) and via the application of models. For the **LMT portfolio**, the first application of two of the four different models has already started:

- c) **E3ME** to assess the impact on the economy (GDP, employment), land-use change, and national emissions, and
- d) **DayCent** to assess the impact on yields, long-term soil fertility and greenhouse gas emissions at both the local and national scale.

E3ME preliminary model results

E3ME is a macro-econometric model designed to assess global policy challenges. It is the most advanced econometric model in the world and is widely used for policy assessment, forecasting and research purposes. The model is owned and maintained by Cambridge Econometrics. By applying E3ME in Switzerland, we explore the impact of scaling up Organic Agriculture and No-Tillage, i.e. the economic impact in terms of the national GDP as well as the labour market, and national emissions. Both land-uses were allowed to scale to a maximum of 20 percent of agricultural land for cereals ,15% for Maize and Soy, and 10% for other crops.

Figure 29: GDP, % difference from baseline

Based on the preliminary model outputs, we can observe that there is only a very limited negative impact of scaling up the LMT portfolio on the GDP compared to the baseline. However, also the GHG savings are small. Import of agricultural goods would need to be increased by 0.2%, which is mainly due to reduced outputs of agriculture (Table 4). This is mainly due to lower productivity per area in organic farming.

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Table 6: Sectoral results, % difference from baseline 2050

Sectors	Output		Employment	
	No tillage	Organic farming	No tillage	Organic farming
Agriculture	-0.70%	-8.19%	-0.54%	-5.22%
Mining & Utilities	0.01%	0.04%	0.00%	0.00%
Manufacturing	0.00%	-0.04%	0.00%	0.01%
Construction	-0.01%	-0.11%	0.00%	0.00%
Market Services	0.00%	-0.02%	0.00%	-0.02%
Non-market services	0.00%	-0.02%	-0.01%	-0.04%

The labour market would only be affected by organic farming, first outputs indicate a reduction in employment in the agricultural sector, however at a lower rate than output reduction, potentially due to higher added value in organic agriculture. Interestingly, the results also indicate a slight decrease in consumer expenditure, which could be related to the fact that more imported goods are consumed, having a cheaper production cost.

DayCent application

DayCent is a Biogeochemical land-use management model that can simulate crop biomass and/or yields, soil carbon and nitrogen dynamics, N₂O emissions, nutrient dynamics and GHG fluxes in different plant or soil systems. The model can simulate long-term ecosystem responses to changes in climate, land use and agricultural management practices in cropland, grassland, forest, and savanna ecosystems.

In Switzerland, we will use it to explore the potential for mitigating soil carbon losses in agricultural soils due to improved management systems. Our first simulation runs are conducted at a national scale but with a simplified baseline scenario (see Figure 30). Also, the efficiency of N in agriculture was assessed (see Figure 25). We aim to improve upon this by combining the LANDSHIFT model, which is good at demand-driven land-use allocation with DayCent, which is superior in estimating greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions including N₂O.

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Figure 30: Modelled mean differences in GHG emission from Swiss agricultural soils (top-left), as a result of organic resource amendment, reduced tillage and cover crops in different combinations compared to cropping only applying mineral fertilizer. (*Slurry & easily decomposable organic inputs/ ^xCompost & partly composted organic inputs; source: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agry.2020.102822>).

The first results showed that the combination of composted inputs, as coming in organic farming, together with reduced tillage and cover crops represents the biggest potential in reducing GHG emissions from Swiss agriculture. This is due to a combination of increased SOC stocks and lower N₂O emissions. The highest effect thereof comes from the input of composted organic matter. Hence it is important in the next step to determine the amount of unused organic resources that could be additionally turned into compost and soil carbon.

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Figure 31: Modelled in and outputs of Nitrogen at the Swiss national scale (kg N ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹). About half the inputs at the current rate are expected to be lost due to leaching and as N-gas emissions. (source : <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10705-020-10078-6>)

Another interesting finding by a modelling exercise at the national scale was that only about half of the input of Nitrogen is found in the harvested crops. The rest is lost, most of it by leaching of NO₃⁻. This calls for a more efficient N fertilization scheme to reduce losses that lead to the eutrophication of water bodies (NO₃⁻) and additional highly potent GHG (N₂O).

ALCES application

ALCES simulates changes in landscape composition and related indicators (e.g., wildlife habitat & populations, ecosystem services, & economic performance) in response to land-use scenarios. The model also tracks landscape composition in response to multiple drivers such as land use (forestry, agriculture, etc.), natural disturbance (e.g., fire, insects), and climate. Simulated landscape composition is applied to track indicator response through user-defined equations that can be based on empirical relationships or stakeholder preferences. In Switzerland, the ALCES modelling focuses on the following questions:

1. Are the LMTs that make up the portfolio compatible with each other? Compatibility may be of concern because the LMTs compete for land or resources (e.g. feedstock for biochar). Organic agriculture and no-till are likely not possible on the same piece of land, and they may also compete for land with agroforestry. However, there may also be synergies, e.g. the additional wood biomass from agroforestry could be used for biochar generation. Hence, there may be both synergies and trade-offs between LMTs. Simulations will explore this.

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- Given the scarcity of suitable land in Switzerland – the maximum potential of combined LMTs could be considered, exploring limitations related to scarcity of land.

Figure 32: Snapshot of the ALCES model application in Switzerland. This example is showing the ecosystem aboveground carbon density [ton C/ha] in the baseline case.

Qualitative Assessment

Climate Risk Assessment

The main objective of an LMTs is to provide a 'climate service' by a) keeping carbon stored (emission reductions by moving from the "baseline" scenario in which carbon would have been emitted to the atmosphere), or b) by absorbing additional carbon from the atmosphere (actual carbon sequestration). To be climate-relevant the net climate impact of an LMT should be **permanent**.

However, **ongoing climate change is one of the key risks** to the LMTs which may limit or prevent the climate service delivered. Well-known risks are the immediate climate risks or hazards, like floods, droughts, and wildfires. For example, peat soil rewetting may prevent oxidation of soil carbon, but with increasing and prolonged droughts periods this climate service may not be delivered.

Next to the climate risks, we also consider the assessment of key risks, co-benefits and trade-offs of LMT scaling up to the national level. **Co-benefits** can be factors such as the diversification of products when implementing agroforestry. In terms of other risks than those directly related to climate change there are e.g., a) **societal risks** such as a lack of social support to implement the technology by threatening societal groups and/or creating inequalities among them, b) **technology/practice risks** such technical challenges when implementing and/or scaling up the technology, and c) **environmental risks** posed by LMT implementation impacting the nature/environment including human, flora and fauna ecosystems.

Our goal of the qualitative risk and co-benefit assessment is to identify and analyse **together with stakeholders** the key socio-economic and environmental risks, co-benefits and trade-offs associated with scaling up LMT. The collected data will be used to advance the development of LMT country narratives and scenarios which among others serve as input for the applied models.

Summary of first results:

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In general, the Swiss policy landscape has a high level of awareness of the existence of negative emission technologies (NET) and is at the forefront of the development, aiming to become an exporter of the NET technology. The tendency is thus towards technological solutions at the moment, e.g. DACCS and BECCS and less on land-based mitigation technologies (LMT). Swiss policy banks on the notion that NET will become available to compensate “residual hard-to-avoid emissions” (e.g. from agriculture). On the other hand, the potential in Switzerland is seen as limited (e.g. no definite CO₂ storage reservoir in saline aquifers), and thus Swiss policy looks specifically at options to offset own emissions in foreign countries through cooperation. Yet, LMTs are also of interest in Switzerland, mainly as they are immediately available before the economy can scale the technological solutions.

Organic Agriculture

Climate Risks

As stated by most interview partners, the climate-related risks that could affect organic agriculture most severely are drought, heat waves and heavy rainfall events leading to erosion. The first two are mainly a threat to yields, while erosion threatens soil fertility by a loss of the most fertile topsoil.

Higher resilience of organic agriculture

Organic agriculture is seen as a solution for many climate-related risks to the cropping system. Through increased humus contents, the system becomes more resilient and heat waves are less severe. Higher soil carbon stocks improve almost all soil functions, from better water infiltration and holding capacity, to better nutrient retention and a more resilient soil microbiome. Also, nutrient cycles are tightened, and the soil provides sufficient nutrients to the plants, leading to a local circularity of nutrients. All these factors add up to a higher climate resilience of agriculture in general, especially toward extreme events, such as severe rainfall or drought.

Political barriers to upscaling

The main barriers to scaling up are economic forces. First of all, the market demand for organic products limits the scale of production. Further, not considering externalities suggests that organic agriculture is too expensive, while all costs are considered this may not be the case. The market also does not reward additional ecosystem services and does not penalize conventional agriculture for external costs they produce. Finally, the subsidy structure is not in alignment. Subsidies are paid for techniques that increase yields in the short term, but not necessarily in the long term. The same is true for changing to organic agriculture, where farmers must be able to deal with reduced income for some years why they change and already have lower yields, but cannot sell their products as organic, yet.

Reduced tillage / No-till

No-till has to be seen in the context of conservation agriculture, which focuses on three pillars: 1) letting the soil undisturbed (no tillage at all, not even reduced) 2) having the soil covered with plants or mulch at all times and as a result of that 3) increasing the amount of plant material input into the soil, to increase soil organic matter.

No-till as a solution to climate Risks

The greatest climate-related risks to no-till carbon sequestration are the things that affect plant growth, i.e. extreme droughts. However, no-till is seen as reducing the climate risks that tillage-using practices are subject to. The continuous cover of the soil increases C input and can sequester soil carbon. Also, the soil is less prone to erosion as a consequence. The main advantage of no-till is the

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improved soil structure due to minimal disturbance. The soils can have an almost grassland-like natural structure with a lot of soil life, such as earthworms. This improves water infiltration and reduces run-off and the constantly present mulch reduces the impact of raindrops, effectively reducing soil erosion. Reduced tillage in that sense was said to be much less efficient as keeping a cover is the most important principle of no-till.

Political barriers to upscaling

In general, there is an enabling subsidy environment with 250CHF per ha and year additional subsidies for reduced/no-till systems. However, these two are not distinguished and reduce the likelihood of no-till uptake, as the machinery is more expensive than for conventional field preparation. Another barrier in Europe is that no-till equipment is difficult to find. On a global level, very advanced no-till technology (e.g. cross-slot, Novak) is available, but for some reason, even companies that have the technology in their portfolio (e.g. Amazone) do not sell and promote it in the European market. A final barrier in Switzerland is the perception that fields need to be "clean" and that mulch on the field is "dirty" and means the farmer is sloppy. This wrong perception is linked to farmer schools paying way too little attention to soil health and soil processes.

Contact Us

Effective engagement of key stakeholders in LMTs enables a better understanding of LMT feasibility- its potential and barriers to scaling up as well as the development of more robust data collection assessment work. This a) helps develop better quality (and more feasible) LMT scaling up and implementation scenarios, and b) improves the uptake of research results and findings in policy and practice.

LANDMARC relies on consultations with stakeholders through the country case studies and our regional engagement activities to link stakeholder knowledge to the application of earth observation techniques and climate, economic and land-use models.

We invite interested stakeholders to participate in our engagement activities to exchange our (preliminary) assessment results and to contribute to climate change mitigation by sharing their tacit knowledge with us.

Become now part of our project to contribute to climate change mitigation!

What we can provide:

By being part of the national stakeholder network, you will be able to connect to a broad network of national and international actors from different backgrounds across agriculture, forestry, and other land-use sectors. Moreover, you can get access to additional data, and literature, and disseminate and exchange relevant results, insights and experiences with a broader group of national stakeholders. Furthermore, by being involved in this European-funded H2020 research and innovation project, you will improve your visibility in an international context. More specifically, we can provide:

- Background information about the applied models and earth observation tools
- Preliminary results from earth observation tool application and preliminary model runs

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- Advanced country narratives explaining our current view on LMT deployment in Switzerland.

How can you contribute?

We are currently looking for stakeholders across all sectors (LMT practitioners, landowners, NGOs, researchers, industry, public sector, etc.) to:

- **Conduct interviews** about general risks and specific climate risks, co-benefits and trade-offs to the implementation and deployment of the individual LMTs (1) organic agriculture and (2) reduced tillage and potentially also (3) agroforestry and (4) biochar application.
- **Exchange information about Swiss land-use datasets** to augment global data sources used for model initialization. e.g., in which locations organic agriculture and reduced tillage practices are most common and where most animal manure is available.
- **Exchange economic data about the LMTs, e.g., cost information on Biochar**, at the current production level, as well as cost-reduction potential when economies of scale come into play.

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Case study: Reduced tillage

Large-scale potential to improve soil carbon storage and reduce soil N₂O emissions in Switzerland

Photo credit Paul Mäder (FiBL, Switzerland)

About the initiative

Together with relevant stakeholders, including Agroscope and partners from the [LANDMARC H2020 research project](#) on land-based negative emission solutions, we will explore the long-term and large-scale potential and limitations of reduced tillage to provide sufficient and economically viable crop production and to mitigate soil GHG emissions through the improved soil carbon storage and reduction of soil N₂O emissions in Switzerland. Ecosystem, land use and economic modelling research complemented with stakeholder engagement activities will be implemented in the 2021-2024 period.

Additional information - Reduced tillage

Reduced tillage is a soil management strategy used to achieve reduced soil disturbance in arable fields while preparing the soil for row cropping, thereby limiting or reducing the need for the deep inversion tillage. It involves a variety of practises represented by lower tillage intensity, shallower tillage depth or reduced tillage frequency (e.g., in the crop rotation) leading to less soil disturbance, either in the seedbed, field or across the farm.

Reduced soil disturbance due to reduced tillage can promote a higher soil organic matter content in the surface layer, which is beneficial for soil structure and stability, soil biological activity and seedling emergence. It can also reduce soil erosion (tillage erosion) and preserve soil fertility. Furthermore, more continuous soil pores developed in response to this practice allow for increased rainfall infiltration, which is beneficial for water availability for crops and thus climate change adaptation.

Reduced tillage might lead to long-term increases in crop yields and thus farm income in some environments, but this is not valid for all soils and climates. Nevertheless, it contributes to savings of labour, time and fuel through the elimination or reduction of intensive tillage operations. The adoption of reduced tillage has been hindered due to a yield reduction and consequently an income loss in the short-term as well as due to weed management problems, which might need extra labour or use of herbicides for weed control. Furthermore, reduced tillage might increase soil bulk density, inhibiting root growth in some environments.

Focus Area

The long-term ongoing experiment evaluating the effects of several soil tillage management options differing in tillage depth on crop yields and various soil properties was established in Changins, Switzerland in 1969 (Fig. 1, 46°24' N, 06°14' E, 430 m above sea level). The experiment follows a

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randomized complete block design with four main treatments of soil tillage related to conventional deep inversion tillage on the one hand, and reduced tillage treatments on the other hand. Until 2007, the following treatments were applied: deep inversion tillage (plough to 25 cm), deep non-inversion tillage (chisel to 25 cm), reduced tillage (cultivator to 10 to 15 cm) and minimum tillage (rototiller to 8 cm). In 2007, the deep non-inversion tillage treatment was converted into a no-till treatment (last tillage: autumn 2006). Each treatment is replicated three times on clayey soil (46% clay, 16% sand) and four times on silty soil (26% clay, 30% sand). A four-year crop rotation has been implemented at this site, consisting of rapeseed (*Brassica napus*), winter wheat (*Triticum aestivum*), grain maize (*Zea mays*) and winter wheat. Research management and regular data collection (yields, soil properties) at the plot level allowed the development of a long-term dataset spanning 54 years. The experiment is aligned with a network of farmers and local stakeholders, which will provide a valuable asset for the LANDMARC project.

Figure 33: a) Location of the P29C long-term experiment in Changins, close to Nyon and b) a photograph of the experiment. Photo credit Lucie Büchi (Natural Resources Institute, UK)

What LANDMARC offers

LANDMARC complements the ongoing work on reduced tillage practices in Switzerland through:

1. **Complementary data collection:** Human systems data for reduced tillage (i.e., local contextual data, socio-economic data such as costs, markets, policies, social acceptance, and land use competition) will be collected through reviews of scientific literature, local/national databases, survey tools and stakeholder workshops.
2. **Assessment of climate vulnerability/risk and potential effectiveness of the large-scale implementation of reduced tillage:** A climate risk and sensitivity analysis of reduced tillage in Switzerland will be performed based on stakeholder knowledge, locally available data and by analysing the results from the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project, phase 6.
3. **Ecosystem and socio-economic impact assessment of reduced tillage:** A qualitative and quantitative exploratory assessment of potential co-benefits and trade-offs related to nationwide scaling-up of reduced tillage will be performed through the stakeholder engagement and by employing ecosystem (DayCent), land-use (ALCES, LandSHIFT) and macro-economic (E3ME) simulation models across the medium to long term. The outcomes of these analyses will have implications for the national climate change mitigation policy strategy development.

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Case study: Organic cropping

Large-scale potential to improve soil carbon storage and reduce soil N₂O emissions in Switzerland

About the initiative

Together with relevant stakeholders, including Agroscope, the Research Institute of Organic Agriculture (FiBL) and partners from the [LANDMARC H2020 research project](#) on land-based negative emission solutions, we will explore the long-term and large-scale potential and limitations of organic cropping to provide sufficient and economically viable crop production and to mitigate soil GHG emissions through the improved soil carbon storage and reduction of soil N₂O emissions in Switzerland. Ecosystem, land use and economic modelling research complemented with stakeholder engagement activities will be implemented in the 2021-24 period.

Additional information - Organic cropping

Organic cropping can preserve natural resources from degradation and promote long-term environmental health and economic profitability based on resilient agroecosystems. It is defined as crop production using animal or green manures, or diverse crop rotations with the aim to conserve soil structure and functions as well as biodiversity, improve the sustainability of crop production, and control weeds and pests. The use of agricultural chemicals (synthetic fertilizers, herbicides, and pesticides) is strictly avoided. Instead, animal manures are used, or leguminous cover crops and green manures are integrated into the crop rotation to provide nutrients for the crop and to suppress weeds and pests. This crop production relies in large part on more closed nutrient cycles by returning plant residues and manures from livestock back to the land and/or by integrating perennial plants, mainly grass-clover mixtures or forage legume leys, into the system. It has been often combined with reduced tillage practices to preserve soil fertility, despite known disadvantages such as high pressure from enhanced weed infestation.

As a systems approach, organic cropping can provide many benefits, such as increased biodiversity at different trophic levels, improved soil quality (fertility, structure and soil biological activity) and adaptation to climate change. Numerous studies show that organic cropping can lead to a reduction of soil organic carbon losses or even to higher soil organic carbon concentrations and net carbon sequestration over time and lower soil N₂O emissions compared to conventional systems per hectare.

Nevertheless, organic cropping generally leads to weed management problems, which might require extra labour or an occasional use of a deep inversion tillage, and a delay in soil nitrogen mineralization in spring, which might together contribute to a crop specific yield reduction (by 20% in general). On the other hand, organic products receive a price premium. The adoption of organic cropping might be hindered by a lack of organic manures due to a limited number of animal husbandries in the area. In summary, despite lower yields, organic farming can deliver more ecosystem services and social benefits and could lead to an improvement of rural livelihood.

Focus Area

The long-term ongoing experiment evaluating the effects of several agricultural input systems on crop yields and various soil properties was established in 1977 in Therwil, Switzerland (Fig.1, 47°30'9.6" N, 7°32'21.0" E) as a result of a collaboration between Agroscope Reckenholz-Tänikon station and the Research Institute of Organic Agriculture (FiBL). Initially, the main goal was to investigate the feasibility of organic farming systems. Nowadays, the main research questions are related to soil and product quality. The experiment compares farming systems differing concerning fertilization and plant protection management: a) biodynamic and organic systems fertilized with farmyard manure and

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slurry at the typical intensity of Swiss organic farms (at 1.2, later at 1.4 LU ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹); b) conventional system with the same organic fertilizer input and additional mineral fertilization up to recommended plant-specific levels (on average 149 kg N ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹); c) mineral conventional system fertilized with mineral fertilizers, representing a stockless system (on average 125 kg N ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹); and d) unfertilized system. The N, P and K inputs in the biodynamic and organic systems are 34-51% lower than in the conventional systems. Organic and conventional systems are managed at two fertilization levels, corresponding to 100% and 50% of typical fertilization. Systems are arranged in a split-split-plot design with four replicates. A seven-year crop rotation consists of potatoes (*Solanum tuberosum*), green manure, winter wheat (*Triticum aestivum*), fodder intercrop, white cabbage (*Brassica oleracea*), winter wheat, winter barley (*Hordeum vulgare*) and a two-year grass-clover ley (*Trifolium pratense*, *Trifolium repens*, *Dactylis glomerata*, *Festuca rubra*, *Phleum pratense*, *Lolium perenne*, *Poa pratensis*, *Festuca pratensis*). White cabbage was replaced with beetroot (*Beta vulgaris*) and soybeans (*Glycine max*), and one winter cereal with silage maize (*Zea mays*) in later years. As fodder intercrops, rye and vetch or sunflower and vetch mixtures are planted. The crop rotation is planted with a temporal shift on three rotation subplots so that three crops are grown simultaneously in each system each year. Soils are managed with conventional tillage and cereal straw is removed. Plant protection in the organic and unfertilised systems is based on mechanical weeding, indirect disease control measures and plant extracts together with bio-controls against insects, while in the non-organic systems herbicides, fungicides and pesticides are applied. Research management and regular data collection (yields, soil properties) on a plot level allowed the development of a long-term dataset spanning 43 years. The experiment is aligned with a network of farmers and local stakeholders, which will provide a valuable asset for the LANDMARC project.

Figure 34: a) Location of the DOK long-term experiment in Therwil close to Basel (Switzerland) and b) a photograph of the experiment. Photo credit Paul Mäder (FiBL, Switzerland)

What LANDMARC offers

LANDMARC complements the ongoing work on organic cropping in Switzerland through:

1. **Complementary data collection:** Human systems data for organic cropping (i.e., local contextual data, socio-economic data such as costs, markets, policies, social acceptance, and land use competition) will be collected through reviews of scientific literature, local/national databases, survey tools and stakeholder workshops.
2. **Assessment of climate vulnerability/risk and potential effectiveness of the large-scale implementation of organic cropping:** A climate risk and sensitivity analysis of organic cropping in Switzerland will be performed based on stakeholder knowledge, locally available data and by analysing the results from the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project, phase 6.

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- Ecosystem and socio-economic impact assessment of organic cropping:** A qualitative and quantitative exploratory assessment of potential co-benefits and trade-offs related to nationwide scaling-up of organic cropping will be performed through the stakeholder engagement and by employing ecosystem (DayCent), land-use (ALCES, LandSHIFT) and macro-economic (E3ME) simulation models across the medium to long term. The outcomes of these analyses will have implications for the national climate change mitigation policy strategy development.

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Ukraine

Management of soil organic carbon sequestration using organic agriculture in chernozems (black soils)

Introduction

What is the realistic potential for agriculture, forestry, and other land-use sectors to reduce emissions from soils, vegetation and livestock and enhance the uptake of CO₂ from the atmosphere? This question will be answered by the LANDMARC research project, which officially started on the 1st of July 2020. Funded by the European Commission, the nineteen LANDMARC consortium partners work during the project period (2020-2024) on:

- Estimating the climate impact of land-based negative emission solutions, for example in agriculture, forestry, and other land-use sectors
- Assessing the potential for regional and global upscaling of negative emission solutions

Mapping their potential environmental, economic, and social co-benefits and trade-offs

What do we do with Land-based Mitigation Technologies (LMTs) in Ukraine?

The Ukrainian case study - executed by TU Delft and the National Scientific Centre Institute for Soil science and Agrochemistry (NSC-ISSAR) together with LANDMARC partners - can help fill knowledge gaps in the global scenarios for scaling up LMTs, as Eastern Europe is not very well represented yet. Due to its large area, Ukraine has a huge potential for LMT implementation; identifying implementation challenges on time and making Ukrainian agriculture more resilient to the future (including climate change). In addition, the case study work can help to identify both co-benefits and trade-offs of the implementation of LMTs that could affect global food security and climate resilience.

Ukraine has a large territory of black soil and conducting research on its territory will allow us to gain in-depth knowledge about the territory within Eastern Europe to identify existing problems for implementing tools that promote sustainable land management and climate change resilience.

LMT Earth Observation

At the location of the Ukrainian case study, we directly collect soil samples along with measurements of dry bulk density and laboratory to determine SOC content and soil moisture (to assess SOC sequestration). The large-scale farm hosts sizeable plots where both conventional and organic farming has been conducted for 40 years and 10 years. These different types of land use will be analysed and compared for SOC sequestration processes. In addition, historical SOC content data from the selected fields, soil properties, soil management type, crop rotation, and crop yield data are collected and processed. This is to evaluate if LMTs' different durations in the chernozems have better results than conventional agriculture in terms of maintaining soil properties to ensure high crop yields and SOC sequestration. This work will be conducted by NSC-ISSAR in collaboration with LANDMARC consortium partner Bioclear Earth.

LMT Modelling

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Next to the primary soil data collection in our case studies, we investigate SOC sequestration using the **DayCent** agroecosystem model. The LMT portfolio for Ukraine consists of Organic farming, Agroforestry (shelterbelts), Reduced tillage, Bioenergy, and background scenario (considering the development of the agricultural sector, urbanization, nature protection, etc.). The impact is to evaluate how well the DayCent model represents changes in SOC and yield by comparing organic to conventional agriculture in the Chernozems. If DayCent proves to work well in Chernozems, we will up-scale the potential of organic agriculture to (sub-)national scales, potentially using scenarios generated with the **LANDSHIFT** modelling. The DayCent simulation modelling work will be conducted by NSC-ISSAR in collaboration with LANDMARC consortium partner ETH Zürich. The potential LANDSHIFT simulation modelling work will be conducted by NSC-ISSAR in collaboration with LANDMARC consortium partner, the University of Kassel.

Earth observation

In our short-term trials in north-eastern Ukraine (Poltava region), we are collecting soil samples to analyze dry bulk density and laboratory determinations of SOC content and soil moisture.

Earth Observation – SOC sequestration management

Soils of Ukraine are characterized, in general, by average (2-3%) and high (3-4%) humus content in the arable layer. The soil area with this content is 16.4 mil. ha, or about half of the arable land. The depth of Ukrainian soil profiles varies very widely, and for chernozem soils, depending on geographical, climatic, and other factors, it is between 50 and 150 cm. Stocks of humus (SOC) in the main Ukrainian soils also vary widely: humus 100-720 t/ha, SOC 60-420 t/ha.

Soil fertility management aims to restore/maintain soil fertility and ecosystem functions through proper land use management. In our case study, research is going on four farms with different types of land use management (Table 1).

Type of management	Farm name	Farm area [ha]	Farm location	Soil tillage equipment	Crops
1) Organic farming + Mini-Till	Farm 1 (F1)	7,700	Myrhorod area, Poltava region	Disk harrows of the company Gregoire Veesson (DXRV, DXRV-HD), peelers Vänderstadt Carrier – CR 820, cultivators Horsch-Agrosoyuz, Scorpio, KVANT-12	<u>Crop Rotation:</u> 1) Winter wheat; 2) Sunflower; 3) a) Green manure (buckwheat + legumes, or oats, rye, alfalfa), b) occupied steam (vetch oats for hay); 4) Winter wheat; 5) Corn for silage; 6) Barley + esparcet; 7) Winter wheat
2) Organic farming + Ploughing	Farm 2 (F2)	525	Kremenchutsky area, Poltava region	-	winter wheat, spring wheat, rye, barley, oat, corn, millet, buckwheat, linen, white mustard, coriander, chickpeas, soy, sunflower, vetch

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3) Conventional + No-Till	Farm 3 (F3)	1,600	Kremenchutsky area, Poltava region	No-Till planters; VHB; John Deere	<u>Crops of 2022:</u> winter wheat – 550 ha; winter barley – 72 ha; spring barley – 30 ha; corn – 700 ha; rapeseed – 280 ha; soybeans – 200 ha; peas – 20 ha; sunflower – 830 ha; sugar beet - 265 ha.
4) Conventional + Ploughing	Farm 4 (F4)	1,600	Kremenchutsky area, Poltava region	For the cultivation of sugar beet, there is a separate crop rotation, where ploughing is used.	

Table 1. – Research objects characteristics

*Soil type, is common for each farm – chernozem (black soil)

According to preliminary expert estimates of NSC ISSAR researchers, total SOC stocks in Ukrainian soils are about 7 Gt. This compares with 1/3 of SOC in agricultural soils of the EU, which are estimated at 18 Gt in 0-30 cm layer (figure 1). The potential of SOC stock increasing by using the best agricultural technologies and balanced application of fertilizers is quite high.

Figure 1. Ukrainian soil organic carbon stock map

Agricultural yields

The impact of the LMT application on agricultural yield is the main concern of farmers.

1. Increase in soil structure and health

External inputs provide nutrition for soil life. An alive soil has increased soil organic matter, which leads to increased water and nutrient storage and better infiltration of water. Moreover, high soil

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organic matter is crucial for climate resilience. Hence it provides the basis for the long-term sustainability of a cropping system.

2. Carbon sequestration and potential trade-offs with N₂O emissions

The external inputs and the higher productivity of the system increase the absorption of CO₂ from the atmosphere, storing it for decadal periods in soil organic matter. Next to improving climate resilience, this contributes to climate change mitigation.

In LANDMARC, will apply innovative methods to assess changes in soil functionality. These Earth Observation (EO) tools include in-situ and remote sensing techniques to monitor the potential and effectiveness of LMTs to reduce GHG emissions. Soil biological monitoring has been done by identifying soil microorganisms through DNA-based molecular biology techniques. Specific genes related to the C and N cycle were used to target microbes involved in the emissions of GHG emissions. Therefore, these techniques can be used as a proxy for detecting soil health and carbon stock in the Ukrainian case study.

Dissemination of the case study results among stakeholders in Ukraine will contribute to implementing organic cropping systems and practices of reduced tillage in Ukraine. It will reduce GHG emissions from agricultural soils, increases the share of organic production, and ensures sustainable soil management. In a changing climate, the resilience of specific cropping methods will be relevant to consider if SOC levels stabilize or increase and what the permanence of the C accumulation is. Organic cropping may have soil hydrological benefits, e.g., soil moisture, evapotranspiration will then be things to look at.

Figure 2. Soil sampling location for SOC sequestration management

Modelling

Next to the primary data collection in our case studies, we investigate the impact of scaling up the most efficient SOC sequestration management practices to the national level.

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DayCent application

DayCent is a land-use management model that can simulate crop biomass and/or yields, soil carbon and nitrogen dynamics, N₂O emissions, nutrient dynamics and GHG fluxes in different plant or soil systems. The model can simulate long-term ecosystem responses to changes in climate, land use and agricultural management practices in cropland, grassland, forest, and savanna ecosystems.

In Ukraine, we want to understand the potential of DayCent to simulate SOC sequestration with organic agriculture in Chernozems, which due to lower SOC decomposition in these soils, may follow different patterns than most European soils. Because this soil has a slower turnover than other soils, it will be needed to test the potential of DayCent to represent SOC dynamics well in Chernozems and to evaluate if calibration of SOC turnover rates in DayCent will be needed. This study thus will have a combined approach using data from past studies and locally taken SOC samples from the case study in north-eastern Ukraine.

In our case study, research is going on a large organic farm (Farm 1), where organic production has been carried out for 40 years on an area of 7.7 thousand hectares (Fig.3). Farm soils are chernozems and meadow-chernozem soils. The farm has not been surveyed, but there is data from studies of individual fields since 2012. Next to this farm, there is a traditional large farm with the same soils, we use them as a comparison.

The main impact is to evaluate how well the DayCent model represents changes in SOC and yield due to organic compared to conventional agriculture in the Chernozems. Then we can calibrate the DayCent model with the combined sampled and literature data to represent SOC stock changes and yield well and upscale the potential to (sub-)national levels.

Figure 3. Soil plots for DaySent data modelling on the scheme of Farm 1

If DayCent proves to work well in Chernozems, we will up-scale the potential of organic agriculture to (sub-) national scales, potentially using scenarios generated with the LANDSHIFT model.

LandSHIFT application

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National Scientific Center "Institute for Soil Science and Agrochemistry Research named after O.N. Sokolovsky"

LANDMARC has received funding from the European Union's Horizon2020 Grant Agreement No 869367

LandSHIFT is a land use change model for global and regional scale simulation experiments. Its principal objective is to simulate the interactions of socio-economic drivers and the biophysical environment determining land use and land use changes and to assess the impacts of these changes on human society and the environment. The model design aims at delivering a tool that can play a central role in scenario analysis projects. The main objective is to identify a portfolio of land-based mitigation technologies (LMTs) in Ukraine and analyse their respective climate mitigation potential under consideration of other potentially contradicting land-use requirements.

The expected and potential impacts of this work are:

1. Identification of possible LMTs that might be of interest in Ukraine for reducing CO₂ emissions to achieve net carbon uptake from the atmosphere.
2. Definition of a national LMT portfolio (Organic farming, Agroforestry (shelterbelts), Reduced tillage, Bioenergy) and background scenario (taking into account development of the agricultural sector, urbanization, nature protection etc.).
3. Modelling of land-use scenarios until 2032 and 2050 to reflect future land-use changes with different levels of implementation of the LMT portfolio.
4. Analysis of potential land-use constraints and effects of LUCC on the carbon balance.
5. Derivation of policy implications.

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Effective engagement of key stakeholders in LMTs enables a better understanding of LMT feasibility- its potential and barriers to scaling up as well as the development of more robust data collection assessment work. This a) helps develop better quality (and more feasible) LMT scaling up and implementation scenarios, and b) improves the uptake of research results and findings in policy and practice.

LANDMARC relies on consultations with stakeholders through the country case studies and our regional engagement activities to link stakeholder knowledge to the application of earth observation techniques and climate, economic and land-use models.

We invite interested stakeholders to participate in our engagement activities to exchange our (preliminary) assessment results and to contribute to climate change mitigation by sharing their tacit knowledge with us.

What we can provide:

By being part of the national stakeholder network, you can connect to a broad network of national and international actors from different backgrounds across agriculture, forestry, and other land-use sectors. Moreover, you can get access to additional data, and literature, and disseminate and exchange relevant results, insights, and experiences with a broader group of national stakeholders. Furthermore, by being involved in this European-funded H2020 research and innovation project, you will improve your visibility in an international context. More specifically, we can provide:

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- Background information about the applied models and earth observation tools
- Preliminary results from earth observation tool application and preliminary model runs
- Advanced country narratives explaining our current view on LMT deployment in Ukraine.

How can you contribute?

We are currently looking for stakeholders across all sectors (LMT practitioners, landowners, NGOs, researchers, industry, public sector, etc.) to:

- **Conduct interviews** about general risks and specific climate risks, co-benefits and trade-offs to the implementation and deployment of the individual LMTs.
- **Exchange information about Ukraine land-use datasets** to augment global data sources used for model initialization. e.g., for the location of agricultural land, and priority areas for organic farming.
- **Exchange economic data about the LMTs**, e.g., information on the labour cost of organic farming.
- **Discuss social information about:**
 - The main interest of stakeholders in LMTs (in Ukraine often perceived to be food security) and how to align climate goals with national and stakeholder goals
 - The main limitations for broader adoption of suitable technologies (e.g., lack of knowledge, access to inputs, lack of compensation for provided ecosystem services)
 - Post-war soil recovery based on LMTs technologies.

Ukraine is the second largest supplier of organic products to the EU. In 2021, 3.24 million tons of organic agri-food products were imported into the EU, more than 10% of which came from Ukraine (fig. 4). Ukrainian exports to the EU increased by 27% - from 265,817 tons in 2020 to 337,856 tons in 2021. (Grains (except rice and wheat, 76.9% of grains of Ukrainian origin), wheat (31.8% from Ukraine), oilseeds (except soybeans, 18.2% and second only to Turkey) are mainly exported to the EU from Ukraine, soybeans (4th place and 13% of soybean imports from Ukraine), fruits (11% and 3rd place).)

Thus, sharing knowledge about Ukrainian soils is needed to understand their unique productive and ecological potential in the context of their significance for the whole world.

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Figure 4. Organic map of Ukraine, 2021

This case study in LANDMARC will broaden the testing ground for land-based mitigation solutions (aiming to promote soil carbon conservation and accumulation) in the Ukrainian agriculture system, open discussions and share lessons to provide the basis for developing upscaling scenarios in Eastern European Countries.

Because of the harmful effects of the war on among others Ukrainian soil, and its importance to the food security of Europe and other continents, it is now very important for the whole world to understand the state of Ukrainian soil, and how to quickly restore it in a post-war period.

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Burkina Faso

Cropland management, Afforestation and reforestation, Agroforestry, Forest Management.

Introduction

What is the realistic potential for agriculture, forestry, and other land-use sectors to reduce emissions from soils, vegetation and livestock and enhance the uptake of CO₂ from the atmosphere? This question will be answered by the LANDMARC research project, which officially started on the 1st of July 2020. Funded by the European Commission, the nineteen LANDMARC consortium partners work during the project period (2020-2024) on:

- Estimating the climate impact of land-based negative emission solutions, for example in agriculture, forestry, and other land-use sectors
- Assessing the potential for regional and global upscaling of negative emission solutions
- Mapping their potential environmental, economic, and social co-benefits and trade-offs

In Burkina Faso, eLEAF uses satellite earth observations combined with in-situ measurements, and land use models to monitor and quantify the carbon sequestration associated with cropland management, afforestation and reforestation, agroforestry, and forest management techniques. eLEAF is working closely with stakeholders from Burkina Faso, including the World Bank, and the FIP Coordination and REDD+ Technical Secretariat under the Ministry of the Environment to assess the impact of the interventions conducted under the Forest Investment Program (FIP). FIP is one of the three programs established under the Strategic Climate Fund (SCF) to support policy measures and investments that target the reduction of deforestation and forest degradation and support sustainable forest management, leading to reduced emissions, protection of carbon stocks, and poverty reduction.

What do we do with Land-based Mitigation Technologies (LMTs) in Burkina Faso?

1. LMT Earth Observation

We are using a satellite remote sensing-based algorithm developed by eLEAF called ETLook to retrieve the evapotranspiration and vegetation growth parameters such as Net Primary Production (NPP in gC/m²) at high resolution spatially and temporally. We are also planning to collect soil samples from Agroforestry and cropland management locations and compare them with an area where LMTs are not applied. These results will give us more insights into the soil functions (capacity of GHGs storage, methane emissions, etc.) and the potential of scaling up LMTs at a national scale.

2. LMT Modelling

Next to the primary data collection, we will investigate the impact of scaling up an LMT portfolio consisting of (1) agroforestry, (2) afforestation and reforestation, (3) cropland management, and (3) forest management. The impact of scaling up those technologies is going to be assessed via a qualitative assessment (see next point) and via the application of simulation models. For this, we currently apply three different models:

- a) **Daycent** to stimulate fluxes of carbon from the soil and aboveground biomass and compare the results with our ETLook model outputs,

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- b) **LANDSHIFT** to simulate the interactions of socio-economic drivers and the biophysical environment determining land use and land use changes and to assess the impacts of these changes on human society and the environment, and
- c) **ALCES** to visualize the impact of LMTs on land-use change and carbon sequestration. The ALCES tool will be utilized with the stakeholders to get feedback about the co-benefits and barriers of upscaling LMTs.

3. Qualitative risk and co-benefit analysis of LMTs

In a series of semi-structured interviews, we ask stakeholders about the (perceived) risks and (co-) benefits of large-scale implementation of our LMT portfolio. We obtain information about how the implementation is affected by a changing climate (e.g., more droughts, higher precipitation, etc.) and how it can benefit society and the environment (e.g., more biodiversity, employment, etc.).

Earth Observation

In Burkina Faso, we collect primary earth observation data from agroforestry and cropland management case studies. The focus area will be on the local Forest Investment Program (FIP) interventions that were implemented as a pilot operation in 32 municipalities and 12 protected forests distributed across 5 regions of Burkina Faso: Boucle du Mouhoun, Center-West, South-West, Center-South, East (Figure 1). The interventions included the creation of conservation areas and silvo-pastoral zones, afforestation, reforestation, fencing, drilling wells and training on good management practices (stone and soil walls, support natural regeneration).

Figure 1: Overview of the PIF interventions in Burkina Faso (data accessed on July 2022 from PIF-Burkina Faso website: www.pif-burkina.org).

Net Primary Production (NPP) is a fundamental characteristic of an ecosystem, expressing the conversion of carbon dioxide into biomass driven by photosynthesis minus the carbon dioxide released

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through autotrophic respiration. NPP is a measure of plant growth and a major process influencing net carbon sequestration at the ecosystem level. ETLook model developed by eLEAF uses a combination of daily weather data and solar radiation, decadal fAPAR and soil moisture stress data and land cover information to estimate NPP ($\text{gC m}^{-2} \text{ day}^{-1}$) at high spatial (10-100 meters) and temporal (weekly to monthly) resolution.

eLEAF calculates time-series data of NPP in these FIP intervention areas to provide new Project Development Objective (PDO) indicators and evaluates the short-term and long-term impacts of the FIP investments. NPP will be calculated monthly to visualize trends in carbon uptake from 2014 to 2022. The extent and spatial resolution of the NPP maps are also pre-determined based on the application and user needs. For analysis at the local scale, (e.g., plot, farm, small-size forest), a high level of detail is required whereas, at the regional or continental scale, a coarser resolution allows fewer details but larger spatial coverage. We can study patterns of change through time in different areas. For example, Figure 3 shows the difference in averaged NPP values and evolution between two protected forest areas of Burkina Faso.

Figure 2: Monthly NPP averaged over two protected forest areas near Koudougou, Burkina Faso: Conservation space of Bachoucorepoun (top left) and the classified forest of Tiogo (top right).

Farmers in Burkina Faso who successfully grow food on degraded lands with low-quality soils and inadequate rainfall are providing useful insights into how climate-smart agricultural methods can help address food insecurity. One of these practices is growing trees around crops (Agroforestry). Integrating forestry and agriculture delivers certain benefits over the conventional way of land use such as:

1. Increase in spatial diversity and biodiversity

Agroforestry allows for a more attractive habitat for insects, birds and other animals.

2. Increase in soil structure and health

Planting trees and shrubs into annual cropping systems can protect the otherwise exposed land and its soil from wind stress and strong precipitation. Additionally, agroforestry increases root diversity that feeds the living organisms within the soil.

3. Carbon sequestration

Agroforestry increases the absorption of CO₂ permanently from the atmosphere in soil organic matter and thereby stores it effectively, which contributes to climate change mitigation.

4. Alternative sources of income

Agroforestry may generate an alternative income source for land users if benefits exceed costs. These benefits may originate from both product revenues and reimbursements for carbon storage.

The idea within LANDMARC is also to team up with agroforestry present in Spain, Vietnam, Burkina Faso and Indonesia. At these pilot sites, novel agroforestry technologies are demonstrated to enable the transition from conventional agriculture toward more climate-resilient agroforestry. Within the approach applied in LANDMARC, we will apply innovative methods to assess changes in vegetation, land use and climatic conditions using different Earth Observation (EO) tools **including in-situ and remote sensing techniques to monitor the potential and effectiveness of agroforestry to reduce GHG emissions**. For the in-situ techniques, soil sampling for **chemical** (soil carbon), and **physical** and **biological** monitoring will be done in the three pilot locations in Burkina Faso. We will measure in-situ total organic carbon content together with other soil physical-chemical parameters. Soil biological monitoring will be done through the identification of soil microorganisms through **DNA-based molecular biology techniques**. Additionally, specific genes related to the C and N cycle will be used to target microbes involved in the emissions of GHG emissions. Therefore, these techniques can be used as a proxy for the detection of soil health and carbon stock quality and flow in the pilot farms.

Modelling

Next to the primary data collection, we will investigate the impact of scaling up an LMT portfolio consisting of (1) agroforestry, (2) cropland management, and (3) forest management. The impact of scaling up those technologies is going to be assessed via a qualitative assessment (see next point) and via the application of simulation models. For this, we currently apply three different models:

1. **Daycent** to stimulate fluxes of carbon from the soil and aboveground biomass and compare the results with our ETLook model outputs,
2. **LANDSHIFT** to simulate the interactions of socio-economic drivers and the biophysical environment determining land use and land use changes and to assess the impacts of these changes on human society and the environment, and

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3. **ALCES** to visualize the impact of LMTs on land-use change and carbon sequestration. The ALCES tool will be utilized with the stakeholders to get feedback about the co-benefits and barriers of upscaling LMTs.

DayCent application

DayCent is a Biogeochemical land-use management model that can simulate crop biomass and/or yields, soil carbon and nitrogen dynamics, N₂O emissions, nutrient dynamics and GHG fluxes in different plant or soil systems. The model can simulate long-term ecosystem responses to changes in climate, land use and agricultural management practices in cropland, grassland, forest, and savanna ecosystems.

In Burkina Faso, we will compare the outputs from Daycent (aboveground biomass, NPP) with the ETLook aboveground biomass at the FIP intervention areas and see how they are correlating better in specific ecosystems. While NPP provides useful insights into carbon uptake by plants, Net Ecosystem Production (NEP) is a better measure of carbon storage by an ecosystem and the ecosystem's potential to act as a carbon "sink" or "source". NEP can be derived from NPP by estimating and subtracting the heterotrophic respiration i.e., the soil carbon flux created from the decomposition of soil organic matter and hummus. eLEAF will use the soil carbon estimates calculated from Daycent and combine them with the aboveground biomass estimated to develop a more comprehensive carbon monitoring tool throughout the country.

LANDSHIFT application

LandShift integrates model components to account for the interactions of socioeconomic drivers and the biophysical environment, which both determine land use change processes. Examples include the influence of local crop production on land use decisions and water availability on irrigation. Furthermore, LandShift is the first large-scale model that emphasizes a detailed representation of the competition for natural resources between the major land use sectors "settlement and industrial", agriculture and forestry. The model input is a set of exogenous drivers, including time series on societal and economic data like population and production of agricultural commodities (crops and livestock). Model output is a time series of raster maps of the changing land use pattern in 5-year time steps, which will be used in Burkina Faso for environmental impact assessment. Moreover, the model generates a set of indicators (like rates of deforestation), documenting the land use change processes in an aggregated form.

ALCES application

ALCES simulates changes in landscape composition and related indicators (e.g., wildlife habitat & populations, ecosystem services, & economic performance) in response to land-use scenarios. The model also tracks landscape composition in response to multiple drivers such as land use (forestry, agriculture, etc.), natural disturbance (e.g., fire, insects), and climate. Simulated landscape composition is applied to track indicator response through user-defined equations that can be based on empirical relationships or stakeholder preferences. In Burkina Faso, the ALCES modelling focuses on the following questions:

1. Are the LMTs that make up the portfolio compatible with each other? Compatibility may be of concern because the LMTs are directly or indirectly related to livestock production. Some LMTs, such as afforestation and agroforestry may compete for pasture that can either be

converted to forest or silvopasture. As such, there may be a trade-off between LMTs. Simulations will explore the potential trade-off.

2. To what degree could the LMTs be impacted by other land-use sectors, most notably urbanization? The LMTs are reliant on agricultural land and ongoing erosion of the agricultural land base by urbanization could constrain opportunities to implement the LMT portfolio. Simulations will explore how urbanization could constrain LMT implementation.

Qualitative Assessment

Climate Risk Assessment

The main objective of an LMTs is to provide a 'climate service' by a) keeping carbon stored (emission reductions by moving from the "baseline" scenario in which carbon would have been emitted to the atmosphere), or b) by absorbing additional carbon from the atmosphere (actual carbon sequestration). To be climate-relevant the net climate impact of an LMT should be **permanent**.

However, **ongoing climate change is one of the key risks** to the LMTs which may limit or prevent the climate service delivered. Well-known risks are the immediate climate risks or hazards, like heavy rainfall events, droughts, and wildfires. For example, heavy rainfall events harm soil fertility as it is washing away the minerals and cause soil degradation.

Next to the climate risks, we also consider the assessment of key risks, co-benefits and trade-offs of LMT scaling up to the national level. **Co-benefits** can be factors such as the diversification of products when implementing agroforestry. In terms of other risks than those directly related to climate change there are e.g., a) **societal risks** such as a lack of social support to implement the technology by threatening societal groups and/or creating inequalities among them, b) **technology/practice risks** such technical challenges when implementing and/or scaling up the technology, and c) **environmental risks** posed by LMT implementation impacting the nature/environment including human, flora and fauna ecosystems.

Our goal of the qualitative risk and co-benefit assessment is to identify and analyse **together with stakeholders** the key socio-economic and environmental risks, co-benefits and trade-offs associated with scaling up LMT. The collected data will be used to advance the development of LMT country narratives and scenarios which among others serve as input for the applied models.

What have stakeholders said so far?

- Cropland management and land agriculture are good practices for carbon sequestration and reducing carbon sequestration. Cropland management should also integrate Agroforestry that helps increase CO₂ absorption and increase soil fertility (planting trees with crops). This is a good practice, so farmers do not cut trees.
- The population is growing in Burkina Faso and cropland management is needed to provide enough yield without the need for cutting forest trees. Planting trees with crops will diversify the farmers' production and source of income.

- Farmers have difficulty with water scarcity, and this is a challenge for them to plant trees and some of them are dying. Farmers need some support and resources to develop practices on their farms to feed their animals without the need of destroying crop residuals and trees.
- Farmers are facing the challenges of climate change issues. If we can link the practices and climate change, the farmers will engage and would like to use these practices. We need the policy to show the benefits of using these practices. This policy could be started by the government or NGOs and have case studies to show the farmers the successful stories.
- Farmers are still not sure about using commercial seeds as they need to witness and see how good it is before applying them. Farmers are conscious of the impact of fertilizers and try to cope with the reality of not having a good yield during the harvest season.
- The farmers are very keen to learn new practices and move forward. It is important to state that the process of scaling up LMTs should involve farmers. The ministry of agriculture in Burkina Faso can play a very important role in this through better training of its technical agents who spend time on the field supporting farmers on daily basis.
- Land tenure insecurity discourages investment in planting trees, resulting in unsustainable natural resource use and extensive agricultural and pastoral practices.
- There is a barrier related to Urbanization as landowners sell the land to build buildings and homes. In addition, the low security and safety in the country led to people moving from the north to the south and needing more space to settle.

Figure 3: Meeting with farmers and stakeholders in Burkina Faso to discuss the co-benefits and challenges associated with using LMTs.

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Effective engagement of key stakeholders in LMTs enables a better understanding of LMT feasibility- its potential and barriers to scaling up as well as the development of more robust data collection assessment work. This a) helps develop better quality (and more feasible) LMT scaling up and implementation scenarios, and b) improves the uptake of research results and findings in policy and practice.

LANDMARC relies on consultations with stakeholders through the country case studies and our regional engagement activities to link stakeholder knowledge to the application of earth observation techniques and climate, economic and land-use models.

We invite interested stakeholders to participate in our engagement activities to exchange our (preliminary) assessment results and to contribute to climate change mitigation by sharing their tacit knowledge with us.

Become now part of our project to contribute to climate change mitigation!

What we can provide:

By being part of the national stakeholder network, you will be able to connect to a broad network that includes actors from different backgrounds across agriculture, forestry, and other land-use sectors. Moreover, you can get access to additional data, and literature, and disseminate and exchange relevant results, insights and experiences with a broader group of national stakeholders. Furthermore, by being involved in this European-funded H2020 research and innovation project, you will improve your visibility in an international context. More specifically, we can provide:

- Background information about the applied models and earth observation tools
- Preliminary results from earth observation tool application and preliminary model runs
- Advanced country narratives explaining our current view on LMT deployment in Burkina Faso.

How can you contribute?

We are currently looking for stakeholders across all sectors (LMT practitioners, landowners, NGOs, researchers, industry, public sector, etc.) to:

- **Conduct interviews** about general risks and specific climate risks, co-benefits and trade-offs to the implementation and deployment of the individual LMTs: (1) agroforestry, (2) afforestation and reforestation, (3) cropland management, and (3) forest management.
- **Exchange information about sustainable management of natural resources** to accelerate growth and reduce poverty in Burkina Faso.
- **Address the direct and indirect drivers of soil and forest degradation** to develop an integrated approach within the context of a broader development and climate change agenda.
- **Participate in regional dialogues** discussing upscaling of LMTs in Burkina Faso and the neighbour countries in Africa.
- **Discuss an innovative approach with the long-term impact** that targeted communities adopt development paths that will lower carbon emissions while ensuring that adequate resources are available to help these communities.

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Kenya

Integrated soil fertility management, Agroforestry, Afforestation

Introduction

What is the realistic potential for agriculture, forestry, and other land-use sectors to reduce emissions from soils, vegetation and livestock and enhance the uptake of CO₂ from the atmosphere? This question will be answered by the LANDMARC research project, which officially started on the 1st of July 2020. Funded by the European Commission, the nineteen LANDMARC consortium partners work during the project period (2020-2024) on:

- Estimating the climate impact of land-based negative emission solutions, for example in agriculture, forestry, and other land-use sectors
- Assessing the potential for regional and global upscaling of negative emission solutions
- Mapping their potential environmental, economic, and social co-benefits and trade-offs

What do we do with Land-based Mitigation Technologies (LMTs) in Kenya?

1. LMT Earth Observation

In our **integrated soil fertility management (ISFM)** case study, we directly collect soil samples together with measuring soil greenhouse gas emissions. The different treatments, including one that applies maize straw to the soil, one that applies farmyard manure, and one with only mineral N application only were analyzed concerning microbial diversity and soil health and processes. This is to evaluate if the locations where LMTs are applied score better than usual in terms of soil functions (GHG storage, (de-) nitrification, methane emissions, etc.).

2. LMT Modelling

Next to the primary data collection in our case studies, we investigate the impact of scaling up ISFM using the DayCent agroecosystem model. The LMT portfolio for Kenya is consisting of (1) ISFM (2) agroforestry, and (2) afforestation. The impact of scaling up those technologies is going to be assessed via a qualitative assessment (see next point) and via the application of simulation models (at the moment for ISFM only). For this, we currently apply the **DayCent** model to assess the impact on yields, long-term soil fertility and greenhouse gas emissions at both the local and national scale and under climate change scenarios

3. Qualitative risk and co-benefit analysis of LMTs

In a series of semi-structured interviews, we ask stakeholders about the (perceived) risks and (co-) benefits of large-scale implementation of our LMT portfolio. We obtain information about how the implementation could be affected by a changing climate (e.g., more droughts, higher precipitation, etc.) but also how we can benefit from it aside from its climate benefit (e.g., more biodiversity, employment, etc.).

Earth observation

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In our long-term trials in western Kenya (Siyaya district), we collected soil samples to analyze microbial communities and their relation to GHG emissions.

Earth Observation – ISFM

Integrating soil fertility management aims to recover/maintain soil fertility and ecosystem functions by combining the input of external high-quality organic material input (e.g. manure) with mineral fertilizer and improved varieties. In our research sites, we compare mineral N application only, to the application of manure, and maize straw that either receives no or 120kg N per ha and season. The aim is to show how the application of manure in combination with mineral fertilizer increases:

1. Agricultural yields

The impact of the LMT application on agricultural yield is the main concern of farmers.

2. Increase in soil structure and health

External inputs provide nutrition for soil life. An alive soil has increased soil organic matter, which leads to increased water and nutrient storage and better infiltration of water. Moreover, high soil organic matter is crucial for climate resilience. Hence it provides the basis for the long-term sustainability of a cropping system.

3. Carbon sequestration and potential trade-offs with N₂O emissions

The external inputs and the higher productivity of the system increase the absorption of CO₂ from the atmosphere, storing it for decadal periods in soil organic matter. Next to improving climate resilience, this contributes to climate change mitigation.

In LANDMARC, will apply innovative methods to assess changes in soil functionality. These Earth Observation (EO) tools **include in-situ and remote sensing techniques to monitor the potential and effectiveness of LMTs to reduce GHG emissions**. Soil biological monitoring has been done through the identification of soil microorganisms through **DNA-based molecular biology techniques**. Specific genes related to the C and N cycle were used to target microbes involved in the emissions of GHG emissions. Therefore, these techniques can be used as a proxy for the detection of soil health and carbon stock. In the case of ISFM, we have analyzed the bacterial and archaeal community of the different treatments of ISFM compared to only applying mineral fertilizer. We found that the application of farmyard manure for 15 years significantly shifted the microbial community to a more diverse one (Figure 35). Furthermore, we found a clear connection between treatments where high N₂O emissions were measured and the dominance of denitrification and nitrification-related genes in these treatments. This shows the importance of the microbial community for these processes (Figure 36).

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Figure 35: (Top) Principal coordinate analysis of farmyard manure treatments with (+N) compared to without N fertilizer (-N). Samples that are far apart from each other are very different in the microbial community. (Bottom) Shannon diversity index for bacteria is highest under farmyard manure application without N addition. Treatments: C, control (no organic input); F(YM) farmyard manure application (equivalent to 1.2 t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹); M, maize stover addition (1.2 t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹)

Figure 36: (Left) Flushes of N₂O emissions over time were strongest in farmyard manure treatments. The prediction of NGS (next generation sequencing) showed significantly increase activity in these treatments of genes related to nitrification and denitrification. Treatments: C(ON), control (no organic input); F(YM) farmyard manure application (equivalent to 1.2 t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹); M(S), maize stover addition (1.2 t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹).

Modelling

Next to the primary data collection in our case studies, we investigate the impact of scaling up the most efficient ISFM practices to the national level. The impact of scaling up those technologies is going to be assessed via a qualitative assessment (see next point) and via the application of models. For the **LMT portfolio**, we currently apply the **DayCent** model, to assess the impact of ISFM on yields, long-term soil fertility and greenhouse gas emissions at both the local and national scale and under climate change scenarios.

DayCent application

DayCent is a land-use management model that can simulate crop biomass and/or yields, soil carbon and nitrogen dynamics, N₂O emissions, nutrient dynamics and GHG fluxes in different plant or soil systems. The model can simulate long-term ecosystem responses to changes in climate, land use and agricultural management practices in cropland, grassland, forest, and savanna ecosystems.

In Kenya, we will use it to explore the potential of ISFM for mitigating soil carbon losses due to maize cropping at scale. Our first simulation runs are conducted at field scale in four reference sites, representative of different soils and climates (see Figure 9 and Figure 38).

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Figure 37: Preliminary DayCent modelling results for soil carbon stock development for different ISFM treatments receiving different types and amounts of organic resources compared to the control with (+N) and without (-N) 120 kg N applied per ha and season. Modelling results were compared to measurements in four different reference locations of sandy and clayey soil, with humid to semi-arid climates (MAP in brackets). The grey bands represent the uncertainty of the simulation. Black dots represent measured data with error bars representing the 95% confidence intervals. The dashed horizontal line is the initial carbon stocks.

Our first results of DayCent, show that DayCent can predict soil organic carbon trends due to different ISFM inputs at the field scale (Figure 9). The results further show, that ISFM reduces losses compared to the most common farming system, where little to no organic and mineral fertilizer inputs are used. However, as in most sites, even treatments with high farmyard manure inputs (about 10t dry matter per year) lose soil carbon, ISFM belongs clearly to the GHG mitigation techniques, but not to the carbon sequestration techniques. This is at least true for sites that start at a high initial carbon content, while already degraded sites with low contents may gain soil carbon. However, ISFM has a second important effect. It drastically increases yields compared to a low input system, between a factor of two to three (Figure 38). Thus, successful ISFM reduces losses of soil carbon while on average doubling yield and thus reducing pressure on other lands, which could then for example be used for afforestation.

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Figure 38: Preliminary DayCent modelling results for maize grain yields (top) and yield-scaled GHG emissions (bottom) for different ISFM treatments receiving different types and amounts of organic resources compared to the control with (+N) and without (-N) 120 kg N applied per ha and season. Modelling results were compared to measurements in four different reference locations of sandy and clayey soil, with humid to semi-arid climates (MAP in brackets).

Our comparisons of measured to modelled changes in soil carbon storage and yield show that overall DayCent is suitable to represent the effects of ISFM at a range of agroecological conditions. It is thus deemed suitable to upscale simulations of DayCent ISFM to the national level. The model outputs also show, that without sufficient nutrient inputs, maize yields will be very poor. At the same time, no inputs also mean the highest soil carbon loss and thus the highest GHG emissions per kg of maize grain yield. There is also clearly a fertility gradient, and the site with higher yields corresponds to suitable climates with ~1,700 mm of rainfall per year. Hence, cropping on unsuitable sites produces significantly higher GHG emissions. An interesting note is that while higher inputs of organic material and mineral fertilizer can stabilize the soil carbon (reduce emissions in 3 and sequester C in 1 site), the higher inputs lead to higher N₂O emissions. This trade-off is not visible when measuring only soil carbon, and hence both CO₂ and N₂O emissions need to be considered in analysing the impact of ISFM.

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Qualitative Assessment

Climate Risk Assessment

The main objective of an LMTs is to provide a 'climate service' by a) keeping carbon stored (emission reductions by moving from the "baseline" scenario in which carbon would have been emitted to the atmosphere), or b) by absorbing additional carbon from the atmosphere (actual carbon sequestration). To be climate-relevant the net climate impact of an LMT should be **permanent**.

However, **ongoing climate change is one of the key risks** to the LMTs which may limit or prevent the climate service delivered. Well-known risks are the immediate climate risks or hazards, like floods, droughts, and wildfires. For example, peat soil rewetting may prevent oxidation of soil carbon, but with increasing and prolonged droughts periods this climate service may not be delivered.

Next to the climate risks, we also consider the assessment of key risks, co-benefits and trade-offs of LMT scaling up to the national level. **Co-benefits** can be factors such as the diversification of products when implementing agroforestry. In terms of other risks than those directly related to climate change there are e.g., a) **societal risks** such as a lack of social support to implement the technology by threatening societal groups and/or creating inequalities among them, b) **technology/practice risks** such technical challenges when implementing and/or scaling up the technology, and c) **environmental risks** posed by LMT implementation impacting the nature/environment including human, flora and fauna ecosystems.

Our goal of the qualitative risk and co-benefit assessment is to identify and analyse **together with stakeholders** the key socio-economic and environmental risks, co-benefits and trade-offs associated with scaling up LMT. The collected data will be used to advance the development of LMT country narratives and scenarios which among others serve as input for the applied models.

Summary of first findings

Afforestation/Agroforestry

Climate Risks

The main risks cited by the interviewees are drought and the unpredictability of rains, which is increasing, following the pattern of stronger rain concentrated in fewer days, leading to an increase in death rates of young trees, landslides and erosion (a major concern in the area, as all interviewees, emphasize it). On the other hand, agroforestry and afforestation protect against erosion and landslides, once fully established. High pressure on land for agricultural production, and free-roaming animals, resulting from high population increases, possess a risk. Therefore, only a portfolio with agricultural management that produces a high yield at low emissions is promising.

Climate Sensitivities

The implementation of agroforestry improves nutrient and water balance and retention, especially when combined with mulching. Certain tree species, such as gliricidia or calliandra, can be used to fix nitrogen, and their prunings can be used as animal fodder. At the same time, they increase resilience by providing a habitat for birds, bees and another macrofauna, as well as diversifying the source of income for farmers. Carbon sequestration in biomass in agroforestry systems is important, but the soil may contain more carbon than biomass, so the role of agroforestry in avoiding the degradation of soils is even more relevant in terms of mitigation than the negative emissions. As a general note, activities

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that require long-term thinking and investments (such as agroforestry) struggle to succeed in poor areas due to the poverty trap; the dominating mindset is survival and getting by, so solutions that do not yield short-term rewards are difficult to implement.

Soil Fertility

Integrated Soil Fertility Management (ISFM) is seen as an LMT, mainly due to making agriculture more sustainable in terms of long-term soil fertility. The higher land productivity has indirect benefits, alleviating the pressure on forest areas to be taken into cultivation. In certain soils, ISFM can lead to carbon sinks, but not in all soils. The main focus of the farmer is, however, the increase and maintenance of yields, so the role of ISFM in an LMT portfolio is mainly that of relieving the pressure of other land uses and mitigating GHG emissions (per yield) from agricultural production.

Climate Risks

Climate risks are mostly related to less predictability of rainfall and less uniform distribution. In western Kenya, these irregularities happen only occasionally, but in central Kenya much more. Rainfalls starting too late, or drought in the middle of the season in vulnerable phases for maize present a risk, both for crop failure and management timing. In the case of manure management, climate-related risks are the potential of increased on-farm emissions from manure heaps during heat waves. After application, a second climate-related risk is the risk of very high N₂O emissions from manure in the case of heavy rainfalls that follow after a prolonged dry spell at the beginning of the rainy season. Such spontaneous rewetting of the soil can lead to pulses in heavy N₂O emissions if there is a loss of ammonia in the soil, hence the timing of manure application is critical.

Climate Sensitivities

ISFM can also have a positive impact on plant diversity, making the land more productive and fitting well with other agronomic practices such as hedgerows, to produce the organic inputs needed for ISFM. Manure application to agricultural systems helps to close nutrient cycles, especially in smallholder agriculture systems, where a lot of nutrients are not in balance, especially if manure application is not evenly distributed on the land. A second advantage of proper manure management is that it reduces emissions (of GHG and ammonia, which is an air pollutant) compared to if the manure is not applied to the soil.

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Effective engagement of key stakeholders in LMTs enables a better understanding of LMT feasibility- its potential and barriers to scaling up as well as the development of more robust data collection

LANDMARC relies on consultations with stakeholders through the country case studies and our regional engagement activities to link stakeholder knowledge to the application of earth observation techniques and climate, economic and land-use models.

We invite interested stakeholders to participate in our engagement activities to exchange our (preliminary) assessment results and to contribute to climate change mitigation by sharing their tacit knowledge with us.

Become now part of our project to contribute to climate change mitigation!

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assessment work. This a) helps develop better quality (and more feasible) LMT scaling up and implementation scenarios, and b) improves the uptake of research results and findings in policy and practice.

What we can provide:

By being part of the national stakeholder network, you will be able to connect to a broad network of national and international actors from different backgrounds across agriculture, forestry, and other land-use sectors. Moreover, you can get access to additional data, and literature, and disseminate and exchange relevant results, insights and experiences with a broader group of national stakeholders. Furthermore, by being involved in this European-funded H2020 research and innovation project, you will improve your visibility in an international context. More specifically, we can provide:

- Background information about the applied models and earth observation tools
- Preliminary results from earth observation tool application and preliminary model runs
- Advanced country narratives explaining our current view on LMT deployment in Kenya.

How can you contribute?

We are currently looking for stakeholders across all sectors (LMT practitioners, landowners, NGOs, researchers, industry, public sector, etc.) to:

- **Conduct interviews** about general risks and specific climate risks, co-benefits and trade-offs to the implementation and deployment of the individual LMTs (1) ISFM (2) agroforestry, (2) afforestation.
- **Exchange information about Kenyan land-use datasets** to augment global data sources used for model initialization. e.g., for the location of agricultural land, and priority areas for afforestation and agroforestry.
- **Exchange economic data about the LMTs**, e.g., information on the labour cost of afforestation and agroforestry.
- **Discuss social information about:**
 - The main interest of stakeholders in LMTs (in Kenya often perceived to be food security) and how to align climate goals with national and stakeholder goals
 - The main limitations for broader adoption of suitable technologies (e.g. lack of knowledge, access to inputs, lack of compensation for provided ecosystem services)

Case study: ISFM - Integrated soil fertility management

Large-scale potential to improve soil carbon storage and reduce soil N₂O emissions in Kenya

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Photo credit Johan Six (ETH, Switzerland)

About the initiative

Together with relevant stakeholders, including the International Institute of Tropical Agriculture (IITA) and partners from the [LANDMARC H2020 research project](#) on land-based negative emission solutions, we will explore the long-term and large-scale potential and limitations of Integrated Soil Fertility Management (ISFM) to provide sufficient and economically viable crop production and to mitigate soil GHG emissions through enhanced soil carbon storage and reduction of soil N₂O emissions in Kenya. Ecosystem, land use and economic modelling research complemented with stakeholder engagement activities will be implemented in the 2021-24 period.

Additional information - Integrated soil fertility management (ISFM)

Integrated Soil Fertility Management combines agronomic practices that include the use of mineral fertilizer, organic inputs, and improved germplasm combined with the knowledge on how to adapt these practices to local conditions with the aim of maximizing the agronomic use efficiency of applied nutrients and increased crop productivity, and thus profitability for smallholder farming systems (i.e., achieving a sustainable intensification). ISFM pursues that all inputs are managed following sound agronomic practices and promotes the use of:

- a) Locally available organic resources such as crop residues, manure, compost and other types of organic wastes, rotation or intercropping with legumes;
- b) Nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium mineral fertilizers and practices that enhance nutrient uptake such as micro-dosing, deep placement, banding, and harmonizing of inputs with rainfall and nutrient demands;
- c) An improved germplasm (involves the selection of early maturing and drought tolerant varieties, spacing and harmonizing of planting time with rainfall predictions);
- d) Liming to address soil acidity;
- e) Inputs of sulphur, calcium, zinc and other nutrients to counteract nutrient deficiencies;
- f) Deep tillage to resolve soil compaction;
- g) Pesticides or herbicides to combat severe insect and weed infestations.

ISFM can lead to short and long term increases in crop productivity, enhanced stability of yields under adverse rainfall oscillations, increased input use efficiency and profitability of food production as related to use of land, labour, fertilizer inputs and financial investments and therefore can lead to major improvements of livelihoods. Combining mineral fertilizers and organic inputs provides conservation and build-up of soil carbon stock and reduction in soil greenhouse gas emissions due to a greater uptake of nitrogen fertilizers by crops and soil carbon sequestration. ISFM practices are designed to limit soil nutrient depletion and thus have the potential to reduce deforestation.

Despite the potential significant benefits of ISFM for food security, household income and environmental protection, the adoption of practices by farmers is usually low and incomplete, especially in African smallholder systems, due to high costs of inputs (i.e., improved varieties and mineral fertilizers require a significant investment), scarcity of organic residues and competition for residues with livestock, and low awareness about the benefits of ISFM.

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Focus Area

The long-term ISFM experiment was established at four research farms with continuous maize (*Zea mays*) in 2002 in central Kenya (Embu and Machanga) and 2005 in western Kenya (Sidada and Aludeka). The experiment has a randomized complete block design set up in a split-plot arrangement with three factors: a) quality (main plot) and b) quantity of organic resources (main plot), and c) quantity of N mineral fertilizer (subplot). The organic resources are incorporated at the beginning of the long rain season in two different quantities (1.2 vs 4.0 t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹) in combination with mineral N fertilization at 0 vs. 120 kg N ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹. Five types of organic resources, classified in quality classes according to their lignin-, phenol- and N-content, are used: *Tithonia diversifolia* (class I), *Calliandra calothyrsus* (class II), *Zea mays* stover (class III), *Grevillea robusta* sawdust (class IV) and farm-yard manure of local quality. Research management and regular data collection (yields, soil properties) on a plot level allowed the development of a long-term dataset spanning 30-36 growing seasons. The experiment is aligned with a network of farmers and local stakeholders, which will provide a valuable asset for the LANDMARC project.

Figure 39: a) Location of the long-term ISFM experiment in Kenya and b) a photograph from the experiment in Embu. Photo credit Johan Six (ETH, Switzerland)

What LANDMARC offers

LANDMARC complements the ongoing work on ISFM practices in Kenya through:

1. **Complementary data collection:** Human systems data for ISFM (i.e., local contextual data, socio-economic data such as costs, markets, policies, social acceptance, and land use competition) will be collected through reviews of scientific literature, local/national databases, survey tools and stakeholder workshops.
2. **Assessment of climate vulnerability/risk and potential effectiveness of the large-scale implementation of ISFM:** A climate risk and sensitivity analysis of ISFM in Kenya will be performed based on stakeholder knowledge, locally available data and by analysing the results from the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project, phase 6.
3. **Ecosystem and socio-economic impact assessment of ISFM:** A qualitative and quantitative exploratory assessment of potential co-benefits and trade-offs related to nationwide scaling-up of ISFM will be performed through stakeholder engagement and by employing ecosystem (DayCent) models across the medium to long term. The outcomes of these analyses will have implications for the national climate change mitigation policy strategy development.

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South Africa

Calibrate and validate satellite-based estimates of carbon sequestration

Introduction

With this case study, the LANDMARC H2020 partners focus on further developing the methodology to estimate carbon sequestration and by doing so, better understanding the role that vegetation plays in carbon storage. The research is executed in a two-step approach. First, in situ EC flux measurements are collected from expert scientists and used to calibrate and validate satellite-based estimations of energy balance and carbon fluxes. Second, the calibrated inputs are used to estimate carbon sequestration in vegetation for larger areas.

Eddy Covariance (EC) is a micrometeorological method that is popular for direct observations of the exchange between the ecosystem and atmosphere in terms of gas, energy, and momentum. Typically, EC provides in-situ continuous observations of the net ecosystem CO₂ exchange, evaporation, and energy fluxes at hourly or half-hourly temporal resolution. The EC observations are considered a good in situ reference that is commonly used for calibration and validation of remote sensing estimates.

What LANDMARC offers

LANDMARC offers the opportunity to improve the current tools to model carbon fluxes and exchange between vegetation and the atmosphere and to develop a robust methodology to estimate carbon sequestration by crops and trees.

Linking remote sensing models and observations with in-situ eddy covariance observations

Although Earth Observation (EO)-based models are an efficient way to simulate carbon fluxes between vegetation and atmosphere spatially and temporally, they require proper parametrization.

In this case study, the LANDMARC partners will use the EC flux measurements collected in South Africa for three main activities:

1. **ETLook:** Calibrate and validate the estimation of carbon fluxes from the ETLook energy balance model developed by eLEAF; develop a prototype model to improve ETLook outcomes and use it to estimate long-term carbon sequestration. If the prototype is operational, it will be assessed and tested on the Land-use Mitigation Techniques of other case studies (e.g., interventions of the World Bank Forest Investment Program (FIP) in Burkina Faso).

2. ESA-TROPOSIF project. Offer calibration and validation data to the solar-induced chlorophyll fluorescence (SIF) observations from the TROPOMI (TROPOspheric Monitoring Instrument) aboard the Copernicus Sentinel-5 Precursor; further, establish the link between SIF and the carbon cycle.

3. TROPOMI HCHO. Improve TROPOMI retrieval of formaldehyde gas fluxes as a proxy for volatile organic compounds (VOC) emissions from vegetation. and observe changes due to land use changes.

Figure 1: Energy fluxes measured by ETLook (top left); TROPISIF project (top right, source: www.noveltis.fr); Global HCHO concentrations created with TROPOMI L2 data (bottom, source: <http://www.tropomi.eu>).

We collected eddy covariance data from different 5 locations in south Africa to validate and improve the estimates of biomass production (i.e, NPP) and evapotranspiration estimated by our methods (Figure 2). Fluxes of water vapour, sensible and latent heats (H and LE), net solar radiation (Rn), and soil heat flux (G) were measured continuously with the EC method between 2017 and 2021 in South Africa. The selected EC flux datasets are diverse in terms of geographic location, site land use (natural vegetation and orchards) and measurement periods; see Table 1 for a more detailed data description.

The EC flux measurements will be compared with various data components of our methods for the:

- Validation of inputs: atmospheric variables;
- Validation of intermediate model outputs: energy fluxes (sensible heat flux, latent heat flux, soil heat flux);
- Validation of final model outputs: evapotranspiration, NPP, carbon sequestration; and
- Calibration of the model using the in situ atmospheric measurements;

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Figure 2: Location of the EC flux towers included in the calibration and validation analysis of the ETLook NPP and NEP estimates in South Africa.

Table 1: Information on the EC flux towers and measurements.

EC flux station				Measurements			
EC name	Longitude	Latitude	Vegetation type	Start date	End date	Frequency	Data source
GF-K	24.83985	-28.85648	Karoo vegetation	29-Jan-2020	31-May-2021	Hourly	EFTEON ¹⁹
GF-S	24.861117	-28.89060	Savanna vegetation	14-Jan-2020	31-May-2021	Hourly	EFTEON ¹
NT-A1	30.27928	-29.45134	Hass avocado orchard	07-Apr-2017	05-Sep-2019	Half hourly	University of Pretoria, University of KwaZulu-Natal ²⁰
NT-A2	30.26522	-29.44046	Hass avocado orchard	22-Sep-2017	05-Sep-2019	Half hourly	University of Pretoria, University of KwaZulu-Natal ²
NT-P	24.63189	-28.06972	Pecan orchard, Mixed cultivar	29-Apr-2019	17-Mar-2021	Half hourly	University of Pretoria ²

¹⁹ Data made available by Dr. Gregor Feigh, Manager Expanded Freshwater and Terrestrial Environmental Observation Network (EFTEON).

²⁰ Data made available by Dr. Nicolette Taylor, Senior Lecturer at the University of Pretoria.

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Indonesia

Decarbonisation from Compost and Biogas

Introduction

What is the realistic potential for agriculture, forestry, and other land-use sectors to reduce emissions from soils, vegetation and livestock and enhance the uptake of CO₂ from the atmosphere? This question will be answered by the LANDMARC research project, which officially started on the 1st of July 2020. Funded by the European Commission, the nineteen LANDMARC consortium partners work during the project period (2020-2024) on:

- Estimating the climate impact of land-based negative emission solutions, for example, in agriculture, forestry, and other land-use sectors
- Assessing the potential for regional and global upscaling of negative emission solutions
- Mapping their potential environmental, economic, and social co-benefits and trade-offs

What do we do with Land-based Mitigation Technologies (LMTs) in Indonesia?

In the Indonesia case study, agroforestry and soil carbon enhancement through biogas and compost are the main LMTs to be assessed in this project. The main objectives of this assessment are to calculate the potential carbon sequestration and improve MRV (monitoring, reporting, and verifying) schemes and tools at local and national levels. Both results will be utilised as policy input and recommendations in the policy-making process by engaging with key stakeholders in the Indonesian government. Three assessments combining quantitative and qualitative assessments are conducted to achieve both objectives.

1. LMT Earth Observation

The Indonesian case study aims to understand the impacts of Land-based Mitigation Technologies (LMTs) at the local level, which then will be upscaled to the national and regional levels. The research questions include the impacts of LMT implementation and how to assess LMT at the local and national levels. The Indonesia case study concerns the decarbonisation potential of **agroforestry, biogas, and compost** in Bali and the Flores Islands. Before identifying the decarbonisation potential of LMT, developing available LMT at the national level in the reference system is necessary as the initial step.

In our agroforestry and biogas case studies, we directly collect soil samples, analyse them concerning soil health (chemical and biogenic assessment) and compare the results with an area where LMTs are not applied (benchmark). This is to evaluate if the locations where LMTs are applied score better than usual regarding soil functions (GHG storage, (de-) nitrification, methane emissions, etc.). Also, we aim to run a remote sensing monitoring system with this in-situ data, so it will improve the MRV (monitoring, reporting, and verifying) scheme at local and national levels and the fit-for-purpose model by engaging key stakeholders in conducting economic and land models as the research contribution for the policy-making process.

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2. *LMT Modelling*

Next to the primary data collection in our case studies, we investigate the impact of scaling up an LMT portfolio to the national level consisting of (1) forestry, (2) peatland, (3) agriculture/agroforestry and (4) soil carbon enhancement based on domestic biomass. The impact of scaling up those technologies will be assessed via a qualitative assessment (see next point) and the application of simulation models. For this, we currently apply four different models:

- a) **E3ME** to assess the impact on the economy (GDP, employment), land-use change, and national emissions, and
- b) **ALCES** to visualise the impact of LMTs on land-use change and carbon sequestration.
- c) **LANDSHIFT** to stimulate direct/indirect land-use and land-cover change on regional, national and global levels for further analyses regarding environmental impacts, e.g., carbon sequestration, biodiversity, water extraction for irrigation or environmental footprint calculations.

3. *Qualitative risk and co-benefit analysis of LMTs*

In a series of semi-structured interviews, we ask stakeholders at local and national levels about the (perceived) risks and (co-) benefits of large-scale implementation of our LMT portfolio. We obtain information about how the implementation could be affected by a changing climate (e.g., more droughts, higher precipitation, etc.) and how we can benefit from it aside from its climate benefit (e.g., more biodiversity, employment, etc.). We ask regarding climate risks and sensitivities of agroforestry/afforestation, peatland rewetting, and organic fertiliser and biochar.

Earth Observation

We collect primary earth observation data from our agroforestry and biogas case study sites in the Indonesia case study.

Figure 40 Biogas and Compost case studies

Figure 41 Agroforestry case studies

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Earth Observation in Agroforestry

Afforestation of agricultural land is supported by agricultural policy to make agriculture more environmentally friendly. Both production forests – aimed at generating wood – and food forests - directed at producing food – can be realised. Promoting agroforestry in Indonesia could increase tree coverage absorbing as much as 30 million tons of carbon (Kahurani and Finestone (2017)). Integrating forestry and agriculture (our analysis focuses on cacao and coffee farms) delivers certain benefits over the conventional way of land use, such as:

1. Increase in spatial diversity and biodiversity

Agroforestry allows for a more attractive habitat for insects, birds and other animals. It enhances habitat diversity to support organisms in addition to naturally occurring co-benefits, such as enhanced nutrient cycling, integrated pest management, and increased resistance to diseases.

2. Increase in soil structure and health

Planting trees and shrubs into annual cropping systems can protect the exposed land and soil from wind stress and strong precipitation. The transition from agriculture to agroforestry can increase soil organic carbon by 34% on average (Pennsylvania State University., 2018). Additionally, agroforestry increases root diversity that feeds the living organisms within the soil.

3. Carbon sequestration and sink

Agroforestry permanently increases the absorption of CO₂ permanently from the atmosphere in soil organic matter and thereby stores it effectively, contributing to climate change mitigation.

4. Alternative sources of income

Agroforestry may generate an alternative income source for land users if benefits exceed costs. These benefits may originate from both product revenues and reimbursements for carbon storage.

5. Food Security

Agroforestry would work as a carbon sink in Indonesia and could have several other beneficial impacts on agricultural systems and food security. It can help systems adapt to greater climate variability by enhancing the structural and temporal diversity of the production system, promoting resilience to shifts in temperature, precipitation variation, and strong winds producing more favourable crop conditions.

The concept behind LANDMARC also involves collaborating with other comparable case studies. Novel agroforestry technologies are demonstrated at these pilot sites to facilitate the transition from traditional agriculture to climate-resilient agroforestry. Within the framework of LANDMARC, we will use innovative methods to assess changes in vegetation, land use, and climatic conditions utilising various Earth Observation (EO) tools, such as in-situ and remote sensing techniques, to monitor the potential and efficacy of agroforestry in reducing GHG emissions.

Figure 42 In-situ soil biogenic and chemical assessments

For the in-situ techniques, soil sampling for **chemical**, **physical** and **biological** assessment will be done in the agroforestry. **Smart soil sampling** will be satellite-based using better referenced and new spatial soil data collection to represent the area. The procedure consists of delineating 2-3 management zones by capturing the variability of soil and agroforestry characteristics based on the big data provided by the Copernicus program (Sentinel 1 and 2). *Sentinel 1* is normally used to study *soil texture* to execute smart soil sampling, and *Sentinel 2* is used to monitor chlorophyll and leaf water content using the *SmartAg app*.

SmartAg is a web-based app that can capture data using satellites (GIS), which can then be used for agricultural management and capture local evidence by taking georeferenced photos with a smartphone in an offline/online approach. This strategy will guide the sample in areas that will better represent the variability in agroforestry. The Indonesia CS tested the SmartAG app from Agroinsider by teaching farmers (citizen participation) in the Climate Field School (CFS) how to use the app and input the evidence as the real-time MRV (monitoring, reporting, and verifying) through photos to assess water stress and chlorophyll of the farm. After this smart sampling, in-situ total organic carbon content and other soil physical-chemical monitoring across different periods and over time will be measured in the different agroforestry locations. Furthermore, soil biological monitoring will be done by identifying soil microorganisms through *DNA-based molecular biology techniques*.

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Additionally, specific chemical assessments, such as N, P, K, pH, and C, will be done. Therefore, these techniques can be used as a proxy for detecting soil health and carbon stock quality and flow in agroforestry.

Figure 43 Smart Soil Sampling and Monitoring

Preliminary Results

This smart soil sampling uses earth observation/remote sensing to assess which location will be used for in-situ measurements based on the case study scenario. Additionally, the SmartAg app was presented and introduced in three Climate Field Schools (CFS) in Bali. There were 83 cacao and coffee farmers in total, and all farmers got a short training on how to use and take evidence using this app. Since water crisis and fertiliser management are two main issues in the location of farms, the app was useful for taking evidence of anomalies related to structure, productivity and water stress in the cacao and coffee crops. To manage the water or farm irrigation, there is Subak in Bali. They manage the water system for all farms, and Subak exists in all regions of Bali. This training is a good practice to include farmers using the MRV tool, and this app helps with the issues identified during the CFS.

Figure 44 Earth Observation and In-situ Measurement for Agroforestry

Moreover, there are four scenarios for conducting in-situ soil measurements for agroforestry farms for the Indonesia CS.

Table 7 Soil Sampling Scenario

Comparison		Consideration
Organic coffee/cacao farms	Non-organic coffee/cacao farms	Some coffee and cacao farms have horticulture plants (fruits, vegetables), so organic and non-organic fertiliser practices in one farm
Arabica and Robusta farms	Cacao farms	Different soil health and structure on agroforestry farms
Companion plant 1 of Coffee Farms	Companion plant 2 of Coffee Farms	Different areas will have different companion plants for coffee
Pongamia Pinnata		Pongamia is a potential plant for oil, bioenergy feedstock, alternative food, and others. This plant can contribute to carbon sequestration and nitrous oxide pollution reduction

We obtained two results from two university labs for analysing soil chemicals (C, N, P, K, and pH). This assessment result compliments the biogenic soil results to assess the impact of agroforestry on soil health and structure.

Modelling

Next to the primary data collection in our case studies, we investigate the impact of scaling up an LMT portfolio consisting of **(1) forestry, (2) peatland, (3) agriculture/agroforestry, and (4) soil carbon enhancement**. The impact of scaling up those technologies will be assessed via a qualitative assessment (see next point) and the application of models. For the LMT portfolio, we currently apply three different models:

- E3ME** to assess the impact on the economy, land-use change, and emissions;
- LANDSHIFT** to stimulate direct/indirect land-use and land-cover change on regional, national and global levels for further analyses regarding environmental impacts; and
- ALCES** to visualise the impact of LMTs on land-use change and carbon sequestration.

E3ME preliminary model results

E3ME is a macro-econometric model designed to assess global policy challenges. It is one of the most advanced econometric models in the world and is widely used for policy assessment, forecasting and research purposes. The model is owned and maintained by Cambridge Econometrics (CE). By applying E3ME in the Indonesia CS, we explore the impact of scaling up the whole LMT portfolio on bioenergy and land-use change, the economic impact in terms of the national GDP and labour market, and emissions at the national level.

The Indonesia CS collaborated with the CE team on another EU Horizon2020 project (TransRisk) between 2015 and 2018. The model assessed biogas development in Indonesia and some parameters which affected the development of biogas (employment, policy targets, GDP, etc.) till 2025. So, in this

Figure 45 E3ME Structure in the TransRisk project

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LANDMARC project, the assessment will continue and update from the previous results to expand the assessment to bioenergy. Land-use impact till 2060 as the Indonesian government set the Net Zero Emission (NZE) roadmap in 2060.

Next to LANDMARC, the Indonesian case study also connects with another EU Horizon2020 project, TIPPING+ (Enabling Positive Tipping Points towards Clean-energy Transitions in Coal and Carbon Intensive Regions). In this project, the Indonesia CS will collaborate with UniGraz to use the CGE (Computable General Equilibrium) model to analyse the energy demand and supply, including renewable energy, till 2060 with two scenarios in 2030 and 2060. The CGE model is another energy-economic model like E3ME, and the modelling result of CGE can be combined with E3ME model results for a more comprehensive economic analysis for LMTs. On the other hand, the E3ME model analysis can be added to the CGE analysis to assess Indonesia's renewable energy production and cost unit analysis for the energy system.

Regarding data requirements for the LANDShift and E3ME model, information about biomass types, location, and livestock potential is required. For E3ME, local data about CAPEX and OPEX, implementation timelines, and specific targets are required. Also, the Indonesia CS needs to provide the cost unit of bioenergy (USD/kWh or USD/MJ). We need a benchmark or assumptions to define the GHG emissions due to land-use change for generating renewable energy. For example, a benchmark of emissions related to the land use change resulting from 1 m³ of biogas production. Additionally, it is interesting to know if additional benefits or incentives could be provided by monetising the potential carbon sequestration & mitigation (e.g., via carbon markets). So, another parameter (e.g. USD/tonnes of CO₂eq) can also be added.

The first scenario for the modelling could be to look at the impacts of bioenergy (i.e., palm oil and crops) in terms of GDP growth, job creation, emissions reduction, and biomass feedstock. Then, the feedback from stakeholders will be collected to validate the model by updating the assumption and output variables.

Figure 46 Data of CO₂ Emissions in Indonesia (2019-2070) based on Sectors.

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Figure 35 shows the baseline of Indonesian carbon dioxide emissions under the baseline scenario of renewable energy and LMT implementation. Overall, a decrease in CO₂ emissions can be observed, mainly due to the increased use of renewable energy production. Hence, the significant reduction is from the energy sector, while emissions from other sectors (industry, transportation, and others) are not reducing notably.

LANDSHIFT Model

We use the LandSHIFT model for the national scenario studies and the LMT portfolio. For the Indonesia CS, LandSHIFT requires the following input to model the land-use change over a certain period:

1. The area that will be utilised for LMT implementation in the future is consistent with a scenario narrative (e.g. in the years 2030, 2040, and 2050). Areas measured in hectares are necessary at the national and sub-national levels. Historical area implementation rates are also useful since they provide a sense of reasonable expectations for the future expansion of areas. Suppose the information on these rates' framing conditions is available. In that case, it can be used as a discussion basis for constructing qualitative and quantitative components of LMT scenarios (scenario drivers).
2. For the spatial allocation of LMT regions under a given scenario, the model requires the following information:
 - a. The subnational unit or region of the country where the appropriate LMT option is viable (or not) to implement.
 - b. In addition, landscape and other spatial factors that can be utilised to distribute land use activities at the grid cell level would be valuable. This comprises information on parameters that, for example, facilitate or impede the adoption of LMTs at a certain place.

Figure 47 Forest Land Cover (Esri TopoMap) in Indonesia (2020). Source: <https://nfms.menlhk.go.id/peta>

Figure 48 Devegetation Map (Esri Imagery) in Indonesia (2020). Source: <https://nfms.menlhk.go.id/peta>

Based on Figure 47 and Figure 48, Landshift will analyse Indonesia's biomass and land cover. The forecasting of biomass feedstock, land cover, and devegetation rate can be done by the model. This result can be used as the input for the decision- and policy-making process for the LMTs implementation in Indonesia. In the Indonesia CS, we analyse hindering, delaying, and promoting all available LMTs at the national level (afforestation, peatland management, agriculture/agroforestry, and soil carbon enhancement).

Specifically, Landshift will model five big islands of Indonesia: Sumatra, Kalimantan, Java, Papua, and Sulawesi. Three of those islands (Sumatra, Kalimantan, and Sulawesi) are the big producers of crops and agroforestry, especially palm oil plantations. Since E3ME will analyse bioenergy and the input will be feedstock and bioenergy types, analysing the crop in Indonesia can be done through Landshift. Landshift can model food and crop demands using bottom-up data to estimate livestock numbers and crop production on each island.

ALCES application

The Indonesia CS invited the ALCES team to present the model in our 3rd Sustainability and Resilience Workshop funded by two EU Horizon2020 projects (TransRisk and GreenWin) in 2018. With the right data, Alces Online provides a spatiotemporal simulation model that can track the benefits, demand and supply of bio-energy options on regional landscapes. The model can also evaluate how dynamics can be affected by land use and climate change. The software can track **sustainable land use** worldwide and consider **economic, social, environmental, and demographical aspects**. While putting the energy sector into consideration, an integrated approach is adopted.

A set of scenarios was established to picture Bali's land and energy use (i.e. the simulations are preliminary and for demonstration purposes only). The key signals for the food sector are the susceptibility of existing crops and livestock to climate change and the loss of croplands to tourism infrastructure. Concerning transportation, GHG emissions and health implications (particulates) have been highlighted due to a rapid increase in motorcycles, commercial trucks, and car fleets. The infrastructure might be inefficient relative to current and future demand. Human population trajectories, settlement patterns, mean temperatures indicators, sea level rise, coastal inundation, tourism person-days (i.e. a tourism activity day and all that is involved in consumption and transport) or potential for cattle dung for biogas could also be assessed thanks to this solution. So, in LANDMARC,

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the Indonesia CS wants to continue and expand the assessment into all available LMTs in Indonesia by modelling Bali and one more island to cover all available LMTs (afforestation, peatland management, agriculture/agroforestry, and soil carbon enhancement).

In response to land-use scenarios, ALCES models changes in landscape composition and related variables (e.g., wildlife habitat and populations, ecosystem services, and economic performance). The model also monitors the response of landscape composition to several causes, including land use (forestry, agriculture, etc.), natural disturbance (e.g., fire, insects), and climate. Utilising user-defined equations that can be based on actual relationships or stakeholder preferences, simulated landscape composition is used to track indicator reactions. ALCES modelling in the Indonesia CS focuses on the following issues:

3. Are the LMTs that make up the portfolio compatible with each other?
4. To what degree could the LMTs be impacted by other land-use sectors, most notably urbanisation and mono-crop plantations?
5. How do the LMTs affect Indonesia's climate change, health, and socio-economic implications?

In our CS, we aim to involve stakeholders in designing the model (fit-for-purpose mode). In two sessions, the ALCES model and accompanying scenarios will be presented.

The first workshop will demonstrate the initial ALCES runs and explain the instrument to various stakeholders. This will provide an opportunity to explain the LMT portfolio, review the current situations, and provide an initial testing ground for determining how to assure the portfolio's utility for stakeholders and researchers alike. The second workshop will focus on co-creation with stakeholders, utilising both the inputs from the first workshop and providing stakeholders with the time and opportunity to align their perspectives with the outputs of the land-use simulation tool.

Figure 49 Fit-for-purpose Modelling

Qualitative Assessment

Climate Risk Assessment

The primary purpose of LMTs is to provide a 'climate service' by a) storing carbon (emission reductions relative to a "baseline" scenario in which carbon would have been emitted to the environment) or b) absorbing more carbon from the atmosphere (actual carbon sequestration). For an LMT to be climate-relevant, its net climatic impact must be permanent.

However, continued climate change is one of the most significant threats to LMTs that may limit or impede the delivery of climate services. Floods, droughts, and wildfires are well-known immediate climatic concerns or hazards. For instance, peat soil rewetting may limit the oxidation of soil carbon, but this climatic service may not be provided during growing and severe dryness.

In addition to climatic hazards, we evaluate the assessment of **significant risks, co-benefits, and trade-offs** associated with the national scale-up of LMT. Co-benefits might include variables such as product diversification when agroforestry is implemented. a) societal risks, such as a lack of social support to implement the technology by threatening societal groups and/or creating inequalities among them; b) technology/practice risks, such as technical challenges when implementing and/or scaling up the technology; and c) environmental risks posed by LMT implementation affecting the nature/environment including human, flora and fauna ecosystems.

The objective of the qualitative risk and co-benefit assessment is to identify and analyse with stakeholders the most significant socio-economic and environmental hazards, co-benefits, and trade-offs associated with expanding LMT. The obtained data will be utilised to further the construction of LMT country narratives and scenarios, which act as inputs for the applicable models, among other things.

The Indonesia CS interviewed and engaged with local, national, and regional stakeholders through some engagements, interviews, and discussions. From the stakeholders' engagements on the risk assessment survey, stakeholders give some inputs and feedback on the assessment and question structures. Results on climate risks of afforestation, agroforestry, peatland rewetting, organic fertiliser, and biochar were obtained during the interviews. Droughts and floods threaten agriculture, and food security is a top priority in Indonesia. Farmers will prioritise larger yields over environmental protection. Thus, they must recognise how these practices might benefit them; otherwise, they will likely not implement them.

Conclusion

By having three assessments (earth observation, modelling, and climate risk assessment), the expected results are to understand potential carbon sequestration and improve the MRV tools and practice by providing some pilot cases in agroforestry and soil carbon enhancement (biogas and compost). By connecting the result with the Indonesian Net Zero Emission (NZE) roadmap, the policy recommendation will be drafted as the policy input for the Indonesian policy-making process, i.e. national development plan and NZE strategies.

Data collection, modelling scenarios, and updating LMT narratives are still ongoing. We welcome any interested party that would like to contribute to our assessment!

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LANDMARC has received funding from the European Union's Horizon2020 Grant Agreement No 869367

Contact Us

Effective engagement of key stakeholders in LMTs enables a better understanding of LMT feasibility- its potential and barriers to scaling up and the development of more robust data collection assessment work. This a) helps develop better quality (and more feasible) LMT scaling up and implementation scenarios and b) improves the uptake of research results and findings in policy and practice.

LANDMARC relies on consultations with stakeholders through the country case studies and our regional engagement activities to link stakeholder knowledge to the application of earth observation techniques and climate, economic and land-use models.

We invite interested stakeholders to participate in our engagement activities to exchange our (preliminary) assessment results and to contribute to climate change mitigation by sharing their tacit knowledge with us.

Become now part of our project to contribute to climate change mitigation!

What we can provide:

Being part of the national stakeholder network allows you to connect to a broad network that includes actors from different backgrounds across agriculture, forestry, and other land-use sectors. Moreover, you can access additional data and literature and disseminate and exchange relevant results, insights and experiences with a broader group of national stakeholders. Furthermore, by being involved in this European-funded H2020 research and innovation project, you will improve your visibility in an international context. More specifically, we can provide the following:

- Background information about the applied models and earth observation tools
- Preliminary results from earth observation tool application and preliminary model runs
- Advanced country narratives explain our current view on LMT deployment in Indonesia.

How can you contribute?

We are currently looking for stakeholders across all sectors (LMT practitioners, landowners, NGOs, researchers, industry, public sector, etc.) to:

- **Conduct interviews** about climate risk assessment and narratives of LMTs implementation: (1) forestry, (2) peatland management, (3) agriculture/agroforestry, and (4) soil carbon enhancement.
- **Exchange information about Indonesian land-use datasets** to augment global data sources used for model initialisation. e.g., for the location of priority areas for afforestation and agroforestry.
- **Exchange economic data about the LMTs**, e.g., bioenergy cost information such as component costs of mono manure digestion incl. CCS, Biogas upgrading costs, the potential scale of anaerobic digestion of manure, etc.
- **Discuss technical information about** rates of organic and mineral fertiliser on conventional cropland in comparison to agroforestry plots (the amount of N is most important as it determines AF biomass growth).

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Nepal

Forestry, Agroforestry, Organic farming and rice management

Introduction

LANDMARC is a research project exploring the potential for storing carbon in soil by changing the way we use land. Together with our 19 partners from around the world, we are trying to understand the environmental, economic, and social co-benefits and trade-offs of different land use practices. The project period is 2020-2024.

Funded by the European Commission, the nineteen LANDMARC consortium partners are working together to:

- Estimate the climate impact of land-based negative emission solutions, for example in agriculture, forestry, and other land-use sectors
- Assess the potential for regional and global upscaling of negative emission solutions
- Map their potential environmental, economic, and social co-benefits and trade-offs

Here's what we are doing in Nepal

Using Earth Observation data to inform rice management

We are collecting soil samples from different crop establishment methods for soil microbial analysis. The crop establishment methods we focus on include i) dry direct-seeded rice ii) wet direct-seeded rice iii) seeding transplanted by rice transplanter and iv) traditional/manual transplanting. When we conduct soil microbial analysis, we will use next-generation DNA sequencing technology to investigate microbes related to GHG storage, nitrous oxide, and methane emissions.

We will also analyse satellite data, obtained from optical and synthetic aperture radar sensors, to map carbon associated with each ground scatterer. In this way, we validate the remote sensing data with the in-situ data, to develop a cost-effective method for monitoring the large-scale application of rice management technologies.

Modelling Four Land-based Mitigation Practices

We have developed a portfolio of four land-based mitigation technologies and practices (LMTs) that we think are particularly promising in the Nepali context. These are

- (1) Agroforestry
- (2) Forestry
- (3) Organic farming
- (4) Rice management

We arrived at this portfolio through a literature review and stakeholder consultation. Next, we will use simulation models and apply qualitative assessment techniques to assess the environmental, economic, and social co-benefits and trade-offs of the four land-use practices we identify in our portfolio.

We will apply the **ALCES** model to simulate the impact of this portfolio on land-use change and carbon sequestration. We will study the effect of these four land-use practices on ecosystem carbon, resource production, and biodiversity risk. We will use both the global data sets and local data for analysing their effect on carbon flux rates and to understand the risk of climate change on different land-use practices.

Qualitative risk assessment

We will also work with stakeholders to identify and analyse the key socio-economic and environmental risks associated with the large-scale deployment of the land-use practices identified in our portfolio. The data we collect from engaging with stakeholders will be used to develop national narratives and scenarios which will provide input for the modelling process.

We are currently conducting a series of semi-structured interviews with stakeholders to investigate the perceived risks that the large-scale deployment of each of these four land-use practices might pose. We are asking stakeholders about their experience of risks posed by the large-scale deployment of land-based mitigation technologies and practices (LMTs) at the national level, as well as any risks due to climate change.

Our preliminary analysis of the risk assessment survey showed that policy risk is important in all LMTs (see Table below).

Table: Preliminary results of risk perceived by stakeholders

LMT	Main highlights
Rice management/dry-seeded rice	Dry-seeded rice needs proper water management in the field, but the chances of LMT failure are rising due to the sudden flooding of fields, mainly due to an increase in uncertainty at the onset of the monsoon season. No government policy and institutional mechanism is set up for large-scale implementation of rice management technologies and practices.
Organic farming	Lack of proper policy support mechanisms
Agroforestry	Large potential, in particular in the mid-hill regions, but the government has no plans and programs for large-scale implementation.
Forest management	Forest fires are becoming more common in Nepal, but it does not receive the attention of policymakers due to no human casualties as only the government forests are affected.

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LANDMARC relies on consultations with stakeholders through the country case studies and our regional engagement activities to link stakeholder knowledge to the application of earth observation techniques and climate, economic and land-use models.

We invite interested stakeholders to participate in our engagement activities to exchange our (preliminary) assessment results and to contribute to climate change mitigation by sharing their tacit knowledge with us.

Become now part of our project to contribute to climate change mitigation!

What we can offer you

By being part of the national stakeholder network, you will be able to connect to a broad network that includes actors from different backgrounds across AFOLU sectors. Moreover, you can get access to additional data, and literature, and disseminate and exchange relevant results, insights, and experiences with a broader group of national stakeholders. Furthermore, by being involved in this European-funded H2020 research and innovation project, you will improve your visibility in an international context. More specifically, we can provide:

- Background information about the applied models and earth observation tools
- Preliminary results from earth observation tool application and preliminary model runs
- Advanced country narratives explaining our current view on LMT deployment in Nepal.

Where you can contribute

We are currently looking for stakeholders across all sectors (LMT practitioners, landowners, NGOs, researchers, industry, public sector, etc.) to:

- **Conduct interviews** about general risks and specific climate risks on the implementation and deployment of the individual LMTs (1) agroforestry, (2) forestry, (3) Organic farming and (4) rice management.
- **Discuss and exchange local data and technical information on Nepal land-use datasets** to augment global data sets for model initialization.

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Vietnam

Agroforestry

Introduction

What is the realistic potential for agriculture, forestry, and other land-use sectors to reduce emissions from soils, vegetation and livestock and enhance the uptake of CO₂ from the atmosphere? This question will be answered by the LANDMARC research project, which officially started on the 1st of July 2020. Funded by the European Commission, the nineteen LANDMARC consortium partners work during the project period (2020-2024) on:

- Estimating the climate impact of land-based negative emission solutions, for example in agriculture, forestry, and other land-use sectors
- Assessing the potential for regional and global upscaling of negative emission solutions
- Mapping their potential environmental, economic, and social co-benefits and trade-offs

What do we do with Land-based Mitigation Technologies (LMTs) in Vietnam?

The Central Highlands of Vietnam is the biggest Robusta coffee producer in the world with approx. 600,000 hectares of coffee, predominantly produced in high-input monoculture systems. Sustainable farming practices in combination with intercropping and agroforestry systems have received increased interest leading to substantial efforts by an interdisciplinary consortium of national and international partners to design sustainable farming systems.

1. LMT Earth Observation

In our **Agroforestry** case study, we use data from Earth Observation to identify the potential to scale the LMT. Based on Sentinel 1 and Sentinel 2, CIAT has developed land use maps to monitor key commodity crops with the potential for agroforestry. Furthermore, gridded climate data, such as ERA5-Land provide important indicators for the current and future climate suitability of coffee agroforestry systems.

We will compare the soil microbial diversity between different coffee systems (i.e., monoculture vs. agroforestry) with a particular focus on microbes involved in the carbon and nitrogen cycle as a proxy for LMT effects on greenhouse gas emissions and soil carbon sequestration. This is done in collaboration with Bioclear who will analyse the soil samples and synthesize the findings together with other agroforestry case studies around the world. Remote sensing approaches are being developed to scale out field-level findings to the landscape level.

2. LMT Modelling

Next to the primary data collection in our case studies, we investigate the impact of scaling up an LMT portfolio consisting of (1) agroforestry, (2) forestry, and (3) biochar. The impact of scaling up those technologies is going to be assessed via a qualitative assessment (see next point) and via the application of simulation models. For this, we currently apply the **ALCES** model to visualize the impact of LMTs on land-use change and carbon sequestration.

3. Qualitative risk and co-benefit analysis of LMTs

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In a series of semi-structured interviews and workshops, we ask stakeholders about the (perceived) risks and (co-) benefits of large-scale implementation of our LMT portfolio. We obtain information about how the implementation could be affected by a changing climate (e.g., more droughts, higher precipitation, etc.) but also how people and the environment can benefit from the LMT scaling aside from its climate benefit (e.g., more biodiversity, employment, etc.).

Earth Observation

In Vietnam, primary data is collected from coffee agroforestry study sites (see Figure 43).

Earth Observation – Agroforestry

Figure 50: Land-use transition pathways in Robusta coffee areas of Vietnam. Association of coffee with multipurpose trees, soil remediation techniques (i.e., biochar) and good farming practices.

Several public and private initiatives are supporting the transitioning of current practices typically with an unbalanced use of agrochemicals and irrigation water in coffee monocropping systems to more balanced integrated coffee intercropping and agroforestry systems. More diversified systems are expected to increase farmer resilience to economic and climatic variability and have been shown to provide overall higher returns. Intercropping and agroforestry in combination with best agricultural management practices such as soil conservation practices, integrated weed and nutrient management as well as pest and disease control and improvement in the multifunctionality of coffee growing landscapes through targeted landscape actions can:

1. Enhance biodiversity

Increase in habitat for soil microorganisms, insects, birds and other animals through reduced pollution risk and increased plant diversity

2. Improve soil health

Increasing the diversity and abundance of organic inputs (biochar, manure, compost, litter, etc.) and annual and perennial root systems improves soil structure, nutrient cycling, and soil microbial diversity

3. Reduces greenhouse gas emissions

Increases in nutrient use efficiency, biological pest control and lower use of agrochemicals

4. Increases carbon sequestration

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Increase in above- and belowground biomass as well as soil organic carbon

5. Diversified income and food security

Diversified production of timber, food, fuel, and fibre

6. Climate change adaptation

Improved microclimate through reductions in daytime temperature, increased humidity and conservation of soil humidity

The idea within LANDMARC is also to combine the learnings of other agroforestry systems in The Netherlands, Spain, and Indonesia. Within LANDMARC, we will apply innovative methods to assess changes in vegetation, land use and climatic conditions using different Earth Observation (EO) tools **including in-situ and remote sensing techniques to monitor the potential and effectiveness of agroforestry to reduce GHG emission.**

For the in-situ techniques, soil sampling for **chemical** (soil carbon), and **physical** and **biological** monitoring will be done. In-situ total organic carbon content together with other soil physical-chemical monitoring across different periods and over time will be measured in the different agroforestry and monocropping locations. Furthermore, soil biological monitoring will be done through the identification of soil microorganisms through **DNA-based molecular biology techniques**. Additionally, specific genes related to the C and N cycle will be used to target microbes involved in the emissions of GHGs. Therefore, these techniques can be used as a proxy for the detection of soil health and carbon stock quality and flow in agroforestry.

Modelling

Next to the primary data collection in our case studies, we investigate the impact of scaling up an LMT portfolio consisting of **(1) agroforestry, (2) biochar, and (3) forestry**. The impact of scaling up those technologies is going to be assessed via a qualitative assessment (see next point) and via the application of models. For the **LMT portfolio**, we currently apply the **ALCES** model to visualize the impact of LMTs on land-use change and carbon sequestration.

ALCES application

ALCES simulates changes in landscape composition and related indicators (e.g., wildlife habitat & populations, ecosystem services, & economic performance) in response to land-use scenarios. The model also tracks landscape composition in response to multiple drivers such as land use (forestry, agriculture, etc.), natural disturbance (e.g., fire, insects), and climate. Simulated landscape composition is applied to track indicator response through user-defined equations that can be based on empirical relationships or stakeholder preferences. In Vietnam, the ALCES modelling focuses on the following questions:

- 1. Are the LMTs that make up the portfolio compatible with each other?** Compatibility may be of concern because the expansion of the LMTs might compete for the same areas. The expansion of coffee and other perennial commodities has, directly and indirectly, led to deforestation. Further, diversifying coffee systems through intercropping and agroforestry might come at the cost of reduced coffee planting density and therefore lower production per unit of land, potentially requiring more land to maintain or increase coffee production from

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the Central Highlands. On the other hand, policy objectives of increasing forestry-based carbon sequestration might compete with other land uses.

2. While land use competition has already been an issue under current climatic conditions affecting the potential of different LMTs and related trade-offs, **climate change will likely shift the suitable areas of crops including coffee** with potential effects on the climate change mitigation potential of coffee agroforestry as an LMT. Agroforestry, however, also has the potential to adapt coffee systems to increases in temperature, therefore leading to potential synergies between climate change adaptation and mitigation. With ALCES we will explore different future scenarios and their resulting impacts on the potential of coffee agroforestry as an LMT.

Qualitative Assessment

Climate Risk Assessment

The main objective of an LMTs is to provide a 'climate service' by a) keeping carbon stored (emission reductions by moving from the "baseline" scenario in which carbon would have been emitted to the atmosphere), or b) by absorbing additional carbon from the atmosphere (actual carbon sequestration). To be climate-relevant the net climate impact of an LMT should be **permanent**.

However, **ongoing climate change is one of the key risks** to the LMTs which may limit or prevent the climate service delivered. Well-known risks are the immediate climate risks or hazards, like floods, droughts, and wildfires. For example, with increasing temperatures and changing rainfall patterns (e.g., extended dry season) some areas might not be able to continue supporting economical coffee yields or coffee of required quality, therefore, leading to land use change. If the proceeding land use stores less carbon and/or increases greenhouse gas emissions, the climate regulation service of the coffee agroforestry system will be lost. Increasing drought can also lead to water competition between coffee and associated trees resulting in the removal of the trees and a return to coffee monocropping systems. With severe droughts, water competition between different water uses (e.g., electricity, domestic, and irrigation) can be accentuated.

Next to the climate risks, we also consider the assessment of key risks, co-benefits, and trade-offs of LMT scaling up to the national level. **Co-benefits** are related to the diversification of products when implementing agroforestry, improved soil conservation and buffering of microclimate. In terms of other risks, than those directly related to climate change, there are e.g., a) **societal risks** such as a lack of social support to implement the technology by threatening societal groups and/or creating inequalities among them, b) **technology/practice risks** such technical challenges when implementing and/or scaling up the technology, and c) **environmental risks** posed by LMT implementation impacting the nature/environment including human, flora and fauna ecosystems.

Our goal of the qualitative risk and co-benefit assessment is to identify and analyse **together with stakeholders** the key socio-economic and environmental risks, co-benefits and trade-offs associated with scaling up LMT. The collected data will be used to advance the development of LMT country narratives and scenarios which among others serve as input for the applied models.

Preliminary findings identify agroforestry as a **cost-efficient LMT with several co-benefits to local communities**. However, there are risks to permanence with economic drivers (e.g., changes in

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commodity prices) potentially incentivizing coffee farmers to change to more profitable cropping systems with lower carbon sequestration potential or trees being removed without replacement. Climate change is another risk factor: While agroforestry can contribute to climate change adaptation by lowering the daytime temperature and increasing humidity, it can only help in adapting up to a certain temperature threshold and with sufficient irrigation water. The main adoption constraints are that transitioning costs and management complexity can be high. Furthermore, missing guidelines for intercropping and agroforestry have been identified as one of the limiting factors for widescale adoption.

Contact Us

Effective engagement of key stakeholders in LMTs enables a better understanding of LMT feasibility- its potential and barriers to scaling up as well as the development of more robust data collection assessment work. This a) helps develop better quality (and more feasible) LMT scaling up and implementation scenarios, and b) improves the uptake of research results and findings in policy and practice.

LANDMARC relies on consultations with stakeholders through the country case studies and our regional engagement activities to link stakeholder knowledge to the application of earth observation techniques and climate, economic and land-use models.

We invite interested stakeholders to participate in our engagement activities to exchange our (preliminary) assessment results and to contribute to climate change mitigation by sharing their tacit knowledge with us.

Become now part of our project to contribute to climate change mitigation!

What we can provide:

By being part of the national stakeholder network, you will be able to connect to a broad network that includes actors from different backgrounds across agriculture, forestry, and other land-use sectors. Moreover, you can get access to additional data, and literature, and disseminate and exchange relevant results, insights and experiences with a broader group of national stakeholders. Furthermore, by being involved in this European-funded H2020 research and innovation project, you will improve your visibility in an international context. More specifically, we can provide:

- Background information about the applied models and earth observation tools
- Preliminary results from earth observation tool application and preliminary model runs
- Advanced country narratives explaining our current view on LMT deployment in the Netherlands.

How can you contribute?

We are currently looking for stakeholders across all sectors (LMT practitioners, landowners, NGOs, researchers, industry, public sector, etc.) to:

- **Conduct interviews** about general risks and specific climate risks, co-benefits and trade-offs to the implementation and deployment of the individual LMTs (1) agroforestry, (2) forestry, and (3) biochar.

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- **Exchange information about Vietnamese land-use datasets** to augment global data sources used for model initialization. e.g., for the location of coffee monocropping and agroforestry systems, data on carbon stocks and biodiversity inventories as well as priority areas for afforestation.
- **Exchange economic data about the LMTs, e.g., agroforestry or biochar cost-benefit information** such as establishment and maintenance costs of agroforestry, production and application costs of biochar, etc.
- **Discuss technical information about** Rates of organic and mineral fertilizer in a conventional coffee system in comparison to integrated agroforestry plots (amount of N most important as it determines AF biomass growth)

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Canada

Wetlands management/preservation/restoration, and afforestation and reforestation

Introduction

What is the realistic potential for agriculture, forestry, and other land-use sectors to reduce emissions from soils, vegetation, and livestock and enhance the uptake of CO₂ from the atmosphere? This question will be answered by the LANDMARC research project, which officially started on the 1st of July 2020. Funded by the European Commission, the nineteen LANDMARC consortium partners work during the project period (2020-2024) on:

- Estimating the climate impact of land-based negative emission solutions, for example, in agriculture, forestry, and other land-use sectors
- Assessing the potential for regional and global upscaling of negative emission solutions
- Mapping their potential environmental, economic, and social co-benefits and trade-offs

To do this, the LANDMARC project researches the feasibility and impact of land-use-based mitigation technologies and practices (LMTs), finding sustainable, long-term, community-supported solutions for land-based climate mitigation.

LANDMARC in Canada

In the Canadian case study for LANDMARC, we explore a portfolio of land-use-based mitigation options in Alberta's Lower Athabasca region (LAR). The main techniques and practices that the Canadian case study focuses on are (i) Wetland management/preservation and restoration; and (ii) Afforestation and forest management.

Our approach takes stakeholder engagement through interviews and workshops as the core aspect of designing and implementing stakeholder-relevant activities. Co-developing knowledge with stakeholders helps us set up models to understand the social, economic, and environmental possibilities of the LMTs, as well as the risks and uncertainties around their implementation and scale-up. We will also employ soil sampling techniques to determine further the effects of implementing the climate mitigation technique.

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Stakeholder engagement

During the starting phases of the project, the main activities of the Canadian case study were outlining potential LMT portfolios for Canada, developing the LMT narratives, and defining the scope of the case study. The definition of the scope of the case study required interaction with academics and representatives of indigenous communities and one NGO, the Canadian Energy and Climate Nexus (CECN). The primary outcomes of the stakeholder engagement activities are summarized below:

- **Discussions with academic generalists:** through discussions with three academics, we could check our preliminary findings through a literature review about LMT potential for Canada, expected climate risks, and policy contexts.
- **Meetings with indigenous communities:** We had various meetings with Indigenous rights holders and the sustainability managers of two indigenous communities in the LAR. During these meetings, we could discuss the communities' priorities and needs while also reviewing the scope of the case study. Through these discussions, we pivoted our scope towards wetland/peatlands restoration since these ecosystems have essential impacts on the livelihoods and health of these communities. However, this contrasts with the findings around technical potential, which ranked wetland/peatlands very low regarding climate change mitigation potential and are not clearly outlined as priorities in the national and regional policies. Therefore, we shifted our approach to include this LMT as a priority.
- **School of Public Policy webinar:** We participated in a webinar titled: *"Soil Title: Soil Carbon Sequestration: What is it, and could it actually work?"*, organized by the School of Public Policy of the University of Calgary. The scope of the webinar was focused on soil carbon storage, what exactly it is, how it changes what we can do with the land and what the potential is to help Canada reduce its agricultural GHG emissions. During this webinar, we engaged with around 70 participants, mostly related to the private sector or government in the agricultural sector. We corroborated that agroforestry as an LMT is at a very early stage in Canada and made connections to further explore and collaborate on LMTs in Canada.
- **Risks, opportunities, and capacity gaps interviews:** During 2022, we held 13 interviews with stakeholders regarding the risks survey through individual interviews covering LMTs in Alberta, Canada. These took the form of semi-structured interviews, looking into aspects of climate sensitivity of LMTs, such as extreme weather, positive and negative impacts from implementing LMTs, and societal challenges and opportunities – for instance (the lack of) policies that might support LMTs from a local to a national level. We will expand on these interviews in the workshops planned for the fall (see below).
- **Partnership with CECN:** We had several meetings with CECN, a local NGO focused on supporting initiatives centred around sustainability advances that involve sectors that traditionally have conflictive perspectives. With this NGO, we have been exploring synergies and ways to collaborate to further explore sustainable business models for LMTs that could enable economic alternatives for indigenous communities while also offering ways for communities and economic sectors to assess

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LMT opportunities at an appropriate level with other natural resource exploitation. Now ILS and CECN are partnering to support a community-led pilot project to experiment and test our new methodologies for deploying LMTs that are environmentally and financially sustainable.

What have we learned?

The main takeaway from our initial stakeholder engagement was that we needed to include peatland preservation, management, and restoration in the LMT portfolio. While there is a relatively low technical potential for climate change mitigation, it became clear that this area was important among the different stakeholders. Directed by this new knowledge, we shifted our approach to making peatlands and oil sands an integral part of the Canadian case study.

Thanks to our stakeholders, we gained initial insights about the different climate risks, barriers, and opportunities for the different LMTs.

Climate risks

Prominent risks that were often mentioned are drought and wildfires. Extreme events in the Canadian provinces in recent years highlighted this. More generally, there was a concern about the permanence of the different LMT options – in other words, How can we ensure that the actions we are doing now for climate change mitigation will keep being effective for the decades (and centuries) to come?

Industry, policy, and politics

There was also concern about the focus on reclamation rather than restoration in the oil sands region of Athabasca. Currently, most efforts are focused on recovering land capacity (reclamation) rather than restoring the ecosystem's original function (restoration). Lands not being put back in their original state are not aligned with the environmental and social history of what was on that land before and was promised to the Indigenous communities living in LAR. Canadian environmental management is a difficult policy topic – with strong national and provincial actors and local stakeholders with strong rights to the lands and their use.

Technical complexity

Stakeholders noted that while there were several reclamation or restoration projects, knowledge of how to restore these often needed to be improved. For example, in some areas where wetlands had been drained, uplands were put in. Some areas are being turned into pit lakes. Local community knowledge was often requested but needed to be implemented or understood fully.

Financial barriers

The successful implementation LMTs will also need to serve the local communities. While not directly addressed, we note that wetlands preservation in the oil sands region, a critical approach to keep carbon in the ground, also has an extremely high opportunity cost if the oil market remains as profitable as it has

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been. Therefore, we have started researching viable valuation and compensation schemes to see if there are alternative ways forward.

The preliminary risk assessment from literature and stakeholder inputs shows that many areas could hinder the deployment and scale-up of the LMTs in the area. Therefore, a comprehensive plan must be in place to test the assumption and de-risk the technologies and strategy to enable LMTs to mitigate climate change impacts successfully. Any effort must consider the priorities and needs of Indigenous communities in the area and those from the industrial sector, government, and other local communities highly dependent on resource extraction activities.

What is next for stakeholder engagement?

The Canadian case study team will hold our 1st workshop in the fall of 2022 in cooperation with local NGOs and communities. These will further help us understand the context, risks, opportunities, and feasibility of the different LMTs, and provide us with different perspectives on how these are understood. A 2nd workshop is planned for early 2023, using the ALCES land-use model to explore scenarios for other mitigation portfolios through stakeholder experiences, perceptions, and knowledge. Later in 2023, we plan to host the 3rd workshop to engage with stakeholders at large and seek investment to support the pilot project financially.

- **Ongoing** - We will continue engaging with stakeholders throughout the entire run of the project through interviews, knowledge sharing, and other activities.
- **Workshop 1 - 2023:** The first workshop will be a focus group in Alberta, Canada. This workshop will be used to gain insights into stakeholder narratives and scenarios and to make sure that our direction with knowledge gathering, modelling, and knowledge sharing is correct. We will communicate with local and provincial stakeholders and keep the workshop small, with about 10 to 20 representatives.
- **Workshop 2 - 2023:** This workshop will take our findings and apply them to the ALCES model in cooperation with the stakeholders. The ALCES model is a land-use simulation tool that we use to simulate different LMTs. We can use this on the fly to respond to workshop outcomes, explore the scenarios with the present stakeholders and respond to their knowledge needs and wishes. Furthermore, we will use the model to bridge the different stakeholder scales, trying to understand what works at a local level to what works at a national level.
- **Workshop 3 – 2023:** This workshop will be hybrid and/or online, focusing on national stakeholders. We aim to use this workshop to verify earlier findings, explore the narratives and scenarios that stakeholders have put forward, share our knowledge with those interested, and seek financial and other support to deploy our pilot site.

If you would like to be involved in a workshop or contribute your knowledge and expertise through an interview, don't hesitate to contact us.

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Modelling and valuation

Projecting local and national impacts

From the perspectives captured from the stakeholder interactions, we have developed a set of scenarios to evaluate using different modelling tools to understand further the impacts of scaling up the ecosystem restoration efforts in LAR. For our LMT portfolio, we currently apply two models.

- a) **E3ME:** We aim to assess the impact on the economy (GDP, employment), land-use change, and GHG emissions at the national scale if community-led restoration efforts based on Indigenous and local knowledge were to be deployed in LAR. E3ME is a macro-econometric model designed to assess global policy challenges. It is the most advanced econometric model in the world and is widely used for policy assessment, forecasting, and research purposes. The model is owned and maintained by Cambridge Econometrics.
- b) **ALCES Flow:** We aim to evaluate the local impact on GHG emissions and co-benefits and trade-offs (land-use change, biodiversity, water, etc.) in using this tool. ALCES Flow is a decision support tool for the comprehensive assessment of cumulative effects, and it was developed by ALCES Landscape & Land-Use Ltd., based in Canada. ALCES' primary role is to facilitate scenario analysis, whereby landscape simulations are completed to compare the benefits and liabilities of possible futures.

With these powerful tools, E3ME and ALCES Flow, we are currently evaluating the comparison of restoring already damaged areas with a scenario where no areas are restored. Also, we are exploring a scenario where market changes add constraints to oil production in LAR, and the boreal forest ecosystem restoration and protection could represent a revenue generation sector. Also, we are incorporating stakeholder inputs as well as alternative indicators relevant to Indigenous rights holders. Preliminary results are expected by the end of 2022 (E3ME) and Q1 2023 (ALCES).

How to account for and value the benefits of LMTs

In most cases, resource extraction activities in LAR require a complete degradation of the host ecosystem. This has impacted the environment and livelihood of Indigenous and Local communities. The companies and institutions involved in resource extraction have made efforts for decades to mitigate negative impacts. However, restoring the original function of the boreal forests in LAR has proven difficult and costly. There has yet to be a large-scale success in ecosystem restoration efforts in LAR.

Determining the value of an LMT is complex due to a large number of variables to consider for valuation methods. Depending on the geographical location where an LMT is implemented, each variable will be impacted differently, playing a different role in determining the solution's value. Due to this complexity, numerous valuation methods and frameworks for nature-based solutions exist throughout the literature.

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However, most cultural and social factors still need to be adequately accounted for to reflect ecosystems' human and spiritual importance in local and Indigenous communities.

Overall evaluation and valuation of LMTs are highly context-specific, based on many assumptions, and thus come with high uncertainty. The same counts for the valuation of ecosystem services. Because of the high context-specificness of LMTs, it becomes much more challenging to create a framework that can evaluate various approaches. Also, research about the dynamics of ecosystems and their influences on things has yet to be fully understood, adding to the uncertainty of these valuations of ecosystem services.

Proper accounting also requires adequate monitoring and reporting. In collaboration with our project partners, we are also assessing the concepts of “climate responsibility,” how to properly account for GHG emissions reduction and carbon offsets credit generation, and how to deliver this value to local and Indigenous communities. Finding ways to generate value from LMTs would provide a budget to finance our transformation to a net-zero society.

In our case study, we are currently reviewing different ways to assess the impacts of LMTs from environmental, economic, and social perspectives, define a quantifiable value to those impacts, and enable this value can be appropriately reflected when deciding about land utilization. In addition, we are evaluating the necessary policy innovations required to accelerate this transformation. A proper accounting of the various ecosystem services could give decision-makers the opportunity and tools to evaluate options more fairly and better aligned with our sustainable development goals.

Earth Observations

Community-based environmental monitoring (CBEM)

For this case study, we will work with environmental wardens of an Indigenous partner community to identify plant species, biodiversity indicators, water levels, weather patterns, and appropriate locations to conduct the pilot study. CBEM involves a periodic record of the environment led and run by community members. CBEM information will be processed to codify and co-develop with community members the input data necessary for the case study.

Soil sampling

Soil samples in the area of study will be collected and analyzed for soil chemical/physical analysis and soil biological analysis in EU-based lab facilities (the Netherlands) in collaboration with BIOCLEAR. The samples will be taken from specific plots/sites, including forests and grass/agricultural lands, to determine: Organic matter, quality of SOM and organic carbon, Nutrients (N, P, K S etc.), pH; clay, sand, silt%; and other parameters of relevance. These indicators are relevant to identifying the initial conditions of the land to be restored, and the progression in soil quality as the restoration progresses.

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A sample kit (developed and compiled by BIOCLEAR) will be sent to the sampling sites. We will work with community members to select sampling sizes and discuss the obtained results to verify if the indicators align with what is known from an Indigenous and traditional knowledge perspective.

Implementation and Pilot

The main goal of our case study is to demonstrate the potential of community-led LMT deployment in the LAR as a climate mitigation and adaptation strategy for Canada and the world. Therefore, we are currently developing a pilot project that involves the co-deployment of our methods with Indigenous and Local knowledge (also Traditional Environmental Knowledge) to prove its benefits and de-risk the technology and deployment innovations looking towards further scale-up.

Indigenous rights holders will lead this pilot project with our support for knowledge co-development. The pilot project should function as an innovation hub that allows for the proof of concept and develop the internal capacity to later bring to other communities and jurisdictions. Our proposed pilot has five main pillars: (i) Food and seedlings production, (ii) Land restoration, (iii) Function monitoring and accounting, (iv) Education and learning, and (v) overall strategy and oversee. A diagram of the proposed pilot is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Community-led LMT innovation hub proposed for LAR, Alberta- Canada.

In collaboration with CECN, one Indigenous community, and key expert stakeholders, we evaluate the proper deployment strategy and financial model and identify the team capable of delivering this vision. We are also receiving advice from Elders and land restoration experts to develop the most appropriate plan for the goals set. We aim to present a full proposal to funding agencies and private investors to raise funds to initiate the planning and implementation phase in 2023.

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Effective engagement of key stakeholders in LMTs enables a better understanding of LMT feasibility- its potential and barriers to scaling up and the development of more robust data collection assessment work. This (a) helps develop better quality (and more feasible) LMT scaling up and implementation scenarios and (b) improves the uptake of research results and findings in policy and practice.

LANDMARC relies on consultations with stakeholders through the country case studies and our regional engagement activities to link stakeholder knowledge to the application of earth observation techniques and climate, economic and land-use models.

We invite interested stakeholders to participate in our engagement activities to exchange our (preliminary) assessment results and to contribute to climate change mitigation by sharing their tacit knowledge with us.

Become now part of our project to contribute to climate change mitigation!

What we can provide:

Being part of the national stakeholder network allows you to connect to a broad network that includes actors from different backgrounds across wetland management, preservation and restoration, afforestation and forest management, BECSC, and other land-use sectors. Moreover, you can access additional data and literature and disseminate and exchange relevant results, insights, and experiences with a broader group of national stakeholders. Furthermore, by being involved in this European-funded H2020 research and innovation project, you will improve your visibility in an international context. More specifically, we can provide the following:

- Background information about the applied models and earth observation tools
- Preliminary results from earth observation tool application and preliminary model runs
- Advanced country narratives explain our current view on LMT deployment in Canada.

How can you contribute?

We are currently looking for stakeholders across all sectors (LMT practitioners, indigenous communities, landowners, NGOs, researchers, industry, public sector, etc.) to:

- Participate in interviews
- Exchange information about Canadian land-use datasets
- Exchange economic data about the LMTs
- Discuss technical and financial information

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Venezuela

Indigenous Fire Management and Agroforestry in dry, semi-arid and arid lands

What is the potential for agriculture, forestry, and other land-use sectors to reduce emissions from soils, vegetation and livestock and enhance the uptake of CO₂ from the atmosphere? The **LANDMARC (Land-use based mitigation for resilient climate pathways)** research project aims at providing answers to this question. Starting on the 1st of July 2020, this four-year project funded by the European Commission gathers 19 partners from 16 countries of five continents to work on:

- Estimating the climate impact of Land-based Mitigation Technologies (LMTs), for example, in agriculture, forestry, and other land-use sectors.
- Assessing the potential for regional and global upscaling of negative emission solutions.
- Mapping their potential environmental, economic, and social co-benefits and trade-offs.

Figure 1. Location of the LMT sites of the Venezuelan LMT portfolio. 1) Vegetation map of Venezuela and LMT study sites (Venezuelan map adapted from Huber and Alarcón, 1988), 2) Different views of traditional Indigenous fire management in Canaima National Park, 2a) Indigenous patch mosaic burning (PMB) practices in savanna-forest borders to avoid the spread of wildfires into the forest (Photography by Suzette Flantua), 2b) Conuco with *Manihot esculenta* (cassava) crops (area under shifting cultivation practices established through Indigenous fire controlled practices)(Photography by Maiquel Torcatt), 3) Agrosilvopastoral Venezuelan practices in Falcón state. 3a) environmental authorities providing technical and financial support to rural communities to develop artisanal ditches to stop erosion and promote soil and vegetation recovery (Images credits: <http://www.minec.gob.ve/inspeccionan-avances-para-el-manejo-integral-de-la-subcuenca-del-rio-tupure-del-estado-falcon/>), 3b) a local cocuy producer showing the establishment of agave plantations under native trees shadow to avoid deforestation 3c) tabulated and semi-tabulated goat herds management systems of small producers in semi-arid lands, 3d) Hybrid plantation systems of rainfed crops established in San José de Cocodite, Paraguaná peninsula, Falcón state. Plants of maize (*Zea mays*), pira (*Amaranthus sp.*), pumpkin (*Cucurbita maxima*), and black beans (*Phaseolus vulgaris*) are planted together in small productive units among native legume trees of cují (*Prosopis juliflora*), and cardón cacti (*Stenocereus griseus*) (images courtesy of INFALCOSTA, 2022). 4) Agroforestry practices in Yaracuy, Venezuela, 4a) Multi-layered agroforestry system in DANAC (Google Earth, 2005), 4b) DANAC Multi-specific agroforestry forests or MAF Program: system of bamboo (*Bambusa vulgaris*) and guadua (*Guadua angustifolia*) trees, associated with short-cycle crops.

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LANDMARC assesses a wide range of LMTs operating in different contexts (e.g., climates, land use practices, socio-economic etc.) and spatial scales from Asia, Europe, Africa, and North and South America.

The COBRA Collective (UK), in cooperation with Universidad Simón Bolívar, leads the Venezuelan case study (CS6) to explore the potential of Indigenous Fire Management in humid tropical forest–savanna mosaics, and Agroforestry in arid and semiarid lands and dry tropical forests as two key LMTs to reduce emissions impact in the country and the region (Figure 1).

This case study focuses on Indigenous ways of fire management as an LMT to prevent catastrophic wildfires and preserve large carbon sinks in Amazon forests. In addition, the COBRA Collective has led the regional case study for the Americas scaling up experiences and brought together intersectoral stakeholders in defining challenges for new LMTs based on integrated fire management with an intercultural vision.

Data and methods

The Venezuelan case study has gathered published data and experiences and performed interviews and workshops for assessing LMTs at the national and regional levels using tools and models provided by other LANDMARC partners. During this process, we have engaged with national and regional stakeholders from Indigenous communities, government agencies, public and private practitioners, experts from academic and research institutions, managers from national and international NGOs, and international cooperation agencies.

Interviews with national and international experts and a thorough literature review have allowed us to identify and characterise Agroforestry and Indigenous Fire Management as key LMTs for Venezuela and their potential risks. A set of data collection and analyses of earth observation, simulation modelling, stakeholder engagement, and qualitative assessment (Figure 2) has been implemented in cooperation with other LANDMARC partners to explore the LMTs at local and national levels. and explore the potential of Indigenous Fire Management LMT at the continental level (Box 1). Special efforts have been devoted to promoting stakeholder engagement, gathering expert knowledge and experiences, and sharing LMTs information among managers and academics.

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Figure 2. a) and b) Examples of participative and cooperative methods using audio-visual techniques (rich pictures, storyboards, etc.) implemented in activities of case study CS6 of the LANDMARC project. Stakeholder participation will support c) ALCES model simulation, d) characterisation of the LMT, and e) interpretation of Earth Observation. Previous experiences showed how powerful participatory tools are to achieving engagement and commitment of local and regional stakeholders, particularly in conflicting socio-economic and environmental contexts such as those affecting the Latin American region.

Box 1. Activities to achieve case study (CS6) goals (local, national, continental level):

- 1- Characterisation of the ecological and human dimensions of Indigenous LMTs related to Indigenous fire management for agricultural purposes and forest protection in CNP.
- 2- Implementation of Earth observation technologies to estimate the effectiveness of Indigenous LMTs.
- 3- Estimation of co-benefits and trade-offs, climate vulnerability, and scaling potential of Indigenous LMTs. A suite of climate and land-use simulations will be applied to better understand this system.
- 4- Strengthen the undergoing transformative process of national policies about fire management in protected areas and climate change in Venezuela. We created opportunities for open discussions and exchanges to develop viable continental narratives and scenarios of fire management as a LMT in Latin America.
- 5- Promotion of intercultural and participatory policies for LMTs and engagement with local, regional, and continental stakeholders in the Latin America already working on implementing negative emission solutions based on Indigenous or local fire management practices.

Although the forest policy and legislation plan in Venezuela envisage reducing forest wildfires by 50% by 2030 throughout the territory (República Bolivariana de Venezuela, 2017a; República Bolivariana de Venezuela, 2019), new paradigms regarding the formulation of more effective fire policies based

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- A preliminary modelling ALCES scenario of Indigenous Fire Management LMT; we have provided data to our LANDMARC partner to explore the impacts of scaling up an Indigenous Fire Management approach using the ALCES model, which is applied to visualise the impact of this LMT on land-use change and carbon sequestration.

Figure 4 shows the advances in the formulation and data collecting of the landscape and carbon system that ALCES is modelling. This diagram is based on the following premises: *In the absence of LMTs, the drivers of land use and disturbance (wildfire) alter the area of natural and anthropogenic land cover types, impacting ecosystem carbon flux and other economic and environmental values. LMTs and LMT portfolios affect ecosystem carbon by a) influencing landscape composition through the conservation of natural ecosystems, fire management, afforestation, and reforestation; and b) influencing ecosystem carbon flux rates associated with agricultural land through sustainable agricultural practices.*

Figure 4. An overview of the landscape and carbon system that ALCES is modelling.

- Earth Observation (EO) tools using satellite images from the Copernicus program data/services from European Space Agency (ESA) will be applied to analyse the Venezuelan CS6 Indigenous Fire management in space and time to assess changes that have occurred due to different fire management practices in Canaima National Park. A set of tools that are part of the Carbon Map Tool and Biodiversity Tool, which are being developed under the scope of Landmarc, will be applied using vegetation spectral indexes (derived from Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 satellite data) to characterise, monitor, verify and report vegetation and soil carbon of Venezuelan CS.
- A field trip to Canaima National Park to develop intercultural workshops with the Kavanayén Pemón Indigenous community to facilitate the process of validation with the Elders Council of Kavanayén Pemón Indigenous community about fire and burning practices, and other traditional practices, material collected by young researchers from the Indigenous community of Kavanayén through the interviews with grandparents. The documented material will be compiled into a book to be published with the support of TUD LANDMARC partner.

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Figure 5. Cover of the material compiled and documented on traditional indigenous land-use practices by the Indigenous researchers of Kavanayén, Parque Nacional Canaima, currently reviewed by the community's council of elders.

- Sixteen expert stakeholders were interviewed (Indigenous leaders, researchers, international organisms' representatives, NGOs members, private landowners, and civil servants).
- Capacity building activities:
 - Coordination of the National Working Group on Integrated Fire Management in Venezuela (Grupo de Trabajo MIF-VEN)
 - Two international expert panels on Fire Management with practitioners and academics organised with the Venezuelan Forest Fires Fighters Brigades (organised by MIF-VEN)

- One international Cycle of 5 Training Webinars (as scientific advisor and oral presentations and roundtable coordination): Fire Management at UNESCO Sites - during September 2021, organised by the Platform for climate change, risk and resilience at UNESCO Sites in Latin America and the Caribbean, Uruguay office. For more complete information see: <https://www.unesco.org/en/articles/climate-change-unesco-commits-new-approach->

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[integrated-fire-management-region](https://es.unesco.org/fieldoffice/montevideo/CambioClimatico/Recursos)

and

<https://es.unesco.org/fieldoffice/montevideo/CambioClimatico/Recursos>

- Dissemination activities:
 - Four peer-reviewed articles (2 published and two submitted); five peer-reviewed book chapters; and one contribution to a UNEP book published.
 - Two participatory videos of intercultural actions and Indigenous values for a new fire management approach (in the editing phase)
 - Participation in three national events (a poster presentation at the 1st Biodiversity International Congress, Venezuela, Dec. 2021; conference at the IV Agro-ecology Venezuelan Congress, Nov. 2022; invited conference at X Simposio Sobre Reforma Agraria e questões rurais. Mudanças climáticas, mundo rural e precarização de políticas públicas, Brazil. 10/11/2022)
 - Invited member of the Conference Committee and participant in the international event Fire Across Boundaries: Connecting Science and Management - 4-7 October 2022, Florence (Italy):
Activities carried on:

- **VIRTUAL PLENARY: Indigenous and local ecological knowledge.** *Moderators:* Bibiana Bilbao (Simón Bolívar University, Venezuela)/Mary Huffman(The Nature Conservancy, USA) (<https://fireacrossboundaries.org/keynote-speakers/>).
- **ROUNDTABLE: From data to action: A way to reduce wildfires: progress in Latin America.** *Coordinators:* Bibiana Bilbao (Universidad Simón Bolívar, Venezuela), Dolors Armenteras (Universidad Nacional de Colombia). *Guests and organisations:* 11 representatives (researchers and fire practitioners) from 9 Latin-American academic and governmental institutions
- (<https://whova.com/embedded/session/lce8T8z4xCbuW0I4Wycl5D74VADl3Ykxy4FjRGF6oLw%3D/2646824/?widget=primary#>)
- *Oral presentations*
- **Indigenous fire management as a valuable climate change land-use-based mitigation technology** (Oral presentation- in person) Bibiana Bilbao, et al. (Oral presentation with LANDMARC partners: <https://whova.com/embedded/session/lce8T8z4xCbuW0I4Wycl5D74VADl3Ykxy4FjRGF6oLw%3D/2646753/?widget=primary>)
- **Fire management strategies in Latin America: New challenges and opportunities for policymakers in changing climate scenarios.** Bibiana Bilbao, et al.

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<https://whova.com/embedded/session/lce8T8z4xCbuW0I4Wycl5D74VADl3Ykxy4FiRGF6oLw%3D/2646806/?widget=primary>

Qualitative risk and co-benefit analysis of LMTs

The main objective of LMTs is to provide a 'climate service' by keeping carbon stored (emission reductions by moving from the "baseline" scenario in which carbon would have been emitted to the atmosphere) or by absorbing additional carbon from the atmosphere (actual carbon sequestration). To be climate-relevant, the net climate impact of an LMT should be permanent.

However, ongoing climate change and societal, technological, economic, and environmental conditions pose risks to the LMTs and may constrain, limit or prevent the climate service delivered.

We analysed together with stakeholders the key climate, socio-economic and environmental risks, co-benefits and trade-offs associated with scaling up Indigenous Fire Management and Agroforestry LMTs in Venezuela.

In a series of semi-structured interviews, we asked stakeholders about the (perceived) risks and (co-) benefits of large-scale implementation of our LMT portfolio. We obtained information about how the performance could be affected by a changing climate (e.g., more droughts, higher temperatures, etc.) and how we can benefit from it aside from its climate facet (e.g., more biodiversity, employment, etc.). Our surveys showed that increases in maximum daily temperatures, droughts, and wildfires are some of the key risk factors already perceived by stakeholders in Venezuela. Fixed erroneous socio-cultural beliefs and inadequate policies revealed as the most relevant restrictions for the adoption of Indigenous Fire Management and Agroforestry LMTs practices.

The collected data and the results of a thorough literature review were used to develop LMT country narratives and scenarios, which serve as input for the applied models.

Some of our preliminary findings

Type of Outcome	Land Management Technology (LMT)	
	Indigenous Fire Management	Agroforestry

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<p>General Co-Benefits & Risks</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Indigenous traditional fire practices such as patch mosaic burning in savanna-forest borders avoid the spread of wildfires into the forest. • Indigenous swiden agricultural practices including controlled burning are crucial for the soil fertilization process. • Firefighting bodies in Venezuela and Brazil have adopted Indigenous fire practices, working together with Indigenous people in their ancestral lands, and adopting these learnings to new spaces. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A set of good practices of land management in arid and semi-arid lands (very dry and xerophytic forests) of Venezuela has been developed and applied in the past 40 years. These LMTs aim mostly at avoiding land desertification, soil loss or soil salinization, as well as preserving biodiversity and underground water resources. • Agroforestry systems in arid and semiarid lands include a) Mixed agricultural systems based on native tree forest species + local traditional crops + photosynthetic CAM novel crops (e.g. <i>Prosopis juliflora</i> + <i>Cajanus cajan</i> + <i>Aloe vera</i>); b) Tabulated & semi-tabulated goat farming; c) Traditional management practices for soil (+water) conservation such as artisan ditches, and other rainwater harvesting techniques. • Some small farmers have successfully adopted these practices in Falcón and Lara state arid and semi-arid lands, but they are not widespread yet. • Agroforestry systems in high forest value plantations in dry lands of Venezuela. These systems have been experimentally adopted by private landowners.
<p>Climate Sensitivity</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Future climate scenarios foresee an increase in maximum daily temperatures and droughts in the country, especially in the northern region of Venezuela. Maximum daily temperatures of up to 47-50°C have already been recorded in the field in Falcón state in the past three years. Under these conditions, severe losses of vegetation cover, biodiversity, and soil fertility will certainly occur. • All these agroforestry practices have been evaluated as resilient to the negative effects of climate changes in these areas, although extended and recurrent severe drought events may affect them. 	
<p>Socio-economic</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Economic constraints such as lack of financial support and socio-cultural issues of local farmers seem to be the major risks affecting the adoption of these technologies. • Selection and promotion of suitable crops and agroforestry systems according to local socio-environmental conditions should be explicitly included in the agricultural portfolio of funding institutions. 	

Contact Us!

We are currently looking for stakeholders across all sectors (LMT practitioners, landowners, NGOs, researchers, industry, public sector, etc.) to:

- **Take part in interviews and discussions** about general risks and specific climate risks, co-benefits and trade-offs to implementing and deploying the individual LMTs of agroforestry and Indigenous fire management.

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- **Exchange information about land-use datasets** to augment global data sources used for model initialisation and priority areas for agroforestry.
- **Exchange economic data about the LMTs**, e.g., agroforestry information such as component costs of their implementation, expected and actual returns, etc.
- **Discuss technical information and experiences about** Indigenous fire management and Agroforestry implementation.

LANDMARC relies on consultations with stakeholders through the country case studies and our regional engagement activities to link stakeholder knowledge to the application of earth observation techniques and climate, economic and land-use models. **We invite interested stakeholders to participate in our engagement activities to exchange our (preliminary) assessment results and to contribute to climate change mitigation by sharing their knowledge with us.**

Become now part of our project to contribute to climate change mitigation!

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